

**МИНИСТЕРСТВО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И НАУКИ
ДОНЕЦКОЙ НАРОДНОЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЕ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЕ
ВЫСШЕГО ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ
«ДОНЕЦКАЯ АКАДЕМИЯ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ И ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ СЛУЖБЫ
ПРИ ГЛАВЕ ДОНЕЦКОЙ НАРОДНОЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ»**

Факультет стратегического управления и международного бизнеса

Кафедра иностранных языков

*Мир глазами молодёжи. Актуальные проблемы
страноведения и культуры в современном мире*

**МАТЕРИАЛЫ РЕСПУБЛИКАНСКОЙ СТУДЕНЧЕСКОЙ
НАУЧНОЙ КОНФЕРЕНЦИИ ПО СТРАНОВЕДЕНИЮ**

(Донецк, 12 декабря 2019 г.)

Донецк

2019

УДК 008:911.7(063)

ББК Ч1+Д890

М63

М63 Мир глазами молодёжи. Актуальные проблемы страноведения и культуры в современном мире : материалы Респ. студ. науч. конф. по страноведению (Донецк, 12 декабря, 2019 г.) / Минобрнауки ДНР, ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС», Факультет стратегического управления и международного бизнеса, Кафедра иностранных языков. – Донецк : ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС», 2019. - 286 с.

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СЕКЦИЯ 1. АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ СТРАНОВЕДЕНИЯ И КУЛЬТУРЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ (АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ЯЗЫК)

PROBLEMS AND PERSPECTIVE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN DPR

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Donetsk People's Republic needs to form a tourist image of the capital of the republic. To create such an image and develop a tourism brand of the republic the generally accepted approaches in the world should be used. The brand should be clear to both local tourists and foreign guests, and should also reveal the vivid features of the republic and its capital.

Information about the republic and its capital, its tourism potential should be spread not only between citizens of the DPR, but neighboring countries as well. For this purpose it is advisable to follow such important events, like world tourism FITUR exhibitions (Madrid), the activity which is coordinated by the World Tourism Organization (WTO). Popularization of tourist opportunities of the city is one of the ways to increase its tourist attractiveness.

However, attracting tourists and creating a tourist image of the republic is different, since the latter requires the creation of a modern tourist infrastructure that meets international standards, high quality services and the availability of attractions, as the main incentive to visit the city.

An example of a promising direction for creating an innovative tourism product within the framework of the DPR is the project of the Legends of Azov Region developed by the Donetsk Institute of Travel Industry, which, according to the project, is adjacent to the Stone Graves reserve. World experience shows that theme parks are organized on a free territory within a two-hour reach of large settlements.

This project can serve as an example of the formation of the tourism industry in the republic. [2]

There are no modern amusement parks in the DPR. It would be possible, for example, to create a large-scale entertainment attraction in accordance with advanced world technologies in the territory of the Shcherbakov park, which is traditionally a place of recreation and entertainment for citizens.

The republic also faces the necessity of improving excursion services, which is supported by the Donetsk Museum of Local Lore and the Donetsk Institute of Tourism. But in Donetsk there is no tourist information center, which could provide a schedule of cultural and entertainment events and supply booklets, brochures, maps, city plans and other things to improve the tourist image of the city. Along with traditional excursion programs, the development of industrial tourism deserves attention, since large metallurgical plants and deep mines can create special effect of original attraction. Such tourism facilities open up new opportunities for travel agencies. However, due to the fact that tourism in the republic is not sufficiently developed, many tourism enterprises avoid taking up the industrial direction in tourism and prefer to work in the worked out areas. It would be a good idea to turn one of the closing mines into an object of tourist attention, investing some money in its reconstruction. [1]

Recommendations for the development of tourist and recreational resources in the DPR:

1. Creation of an artificial ski complex, which will attract the number of tourists.

Such special indoor ski resort infrastructure creates all-weather conditions for skiing and entertaining. An example of such projects is the opening of the first indoor ski resort in Japan, Belgium, Vienna, as well as an attempt to recreate the atmosphere of indoor ski slopes. Meanwhile, all these projects had many significant drawbacks: high cost, long construction time, lack of suitable materials to create a real analogue to natural snow cover. Attention should be drawn to a different solution while organizing the skiing activity. These are less known, but more widespread slopes with artificial synthetic cover, which have a number of attractive characteristics like reasonable price similar equipment like the ones used for skiing on natural slopes or tracks. All this makes the skiing activity significantly attractive.

2. Cleaning and arranging the city beaches for the summer season, creating all the necessary conditions for recreation, including water treatment facilities.

Well equipped city beaches and recreational resources have great potential for tourists. But the project needs investments. To attract funding a fee for using the beach facilities should be introduced.

3. The creation of singing and dancing fountains, which are very popular among tourists in all corners of the world, is promising. Bright colors, pleasant music and relaxing atmosphere will make tourists from other countries come and watch this magnificent performance (like in Dubai, Barcelona, Batumi, etc.).

4. Reconstruction of the Ferris wheel and the creation of new attractions.

Today, most of the attractions of our cities have ceased to function. Bringing them to work or creating new attractions is an important responsibility of the tourism and recreation sector. Extending the working hours of the attractions until 22:00 hours sounds promising.

Summing up the above, we can conclude that tourism is one of the ways of filling local budgets and therefore it is important to create conditions under which outbound tourism and cash outflows would be lower than revenues from domestic and inbound tourism to a region. This requires a set of measures both to protect the environment, and to create favorable conditions in terms of expanding recreational nature reserves and developing the corresponding tourism infrastructure on an international level.

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MOVEMENT OF METALHEADS IN YOUNG PEOPLE'S CULTURE

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Metalist's (metalhead's) movement is a subculture inspired by metal music that appeared in the 1970s.

The subculture is widespread not only in Northern Europe, but also in Russia, Ukraine, Belarus, North America. There is a significant number of its representatives in South America, Southern Europe and Japan. In the Middle East, except for Turkey and Israel, metalheads (like many other "informals") are few in number.

The word "metalheads" is Russian derived from the word "metal" with the addition of the borrowed Latin suffix "- ist". Initially, it meant tinsmiths, metallurgy workers. The metalist in the meaning of "heavy metal fan" came into use in the late 1980s.

Each language has its own derivatives of the word metal to denote its fans. In Spanish – "metalero", in Italian – "metallaro", in Finnish – "hevari" (from the word "Heavy"), in Polish – "metalowcy".

The metalhead's subculture appeared in the early 1970s in Europe and quickly conquered the whole world thanks to its main attribute - music. This music includes all the heavy styles, such as heavy-metal, gothic-metal, death-metal, rock. The most popular metal bands are: Iron Maiden, Accept, Metallica, Halloween, Gamma Ray.

In Russia, they appeared by the end of the 80s, the first metal-festival was held in Moscow in 1989. The stereotype of metalheads as unwashed, hairy, foul-language and aggressive teenagers, of course, is false - this is an example of the worst representatives of the subculture. Basically, metalheads like heavy music, tattoos, noisy concerts and alcohol (but not drugs). Of course, due to the philosophy of independence and freedom, teens join metalheads, but often a subculture develops into a lifestyle. At concerts outside of Russia, one can meet metalhead pensioners or

even families. Metalheads of the age are most often serious entrepreneurial people, businessmen or creative personalities.

Most metalheads, when they are buying tickets for a metal band concert, prefer not a seating area, but a dance ground. During the concert, the audience on the dance floor behaves extremely emotionally: dancing, jumping, shaking their heads (“headbanging”), singing along, shouting loudly, showing a “goat”, often girls are put on the shoulders of men. Musicians support this behavior of fans: often the vocalist turns the microphone into the hall so that the audience sings a few lines; sometimes one of the spectators is dragged onto the stage for a short time; after the concert, the musicians throw picks and drumsticks into the crowd.

Many metalheads can play the guitar or other musical instruments. Some are members of amateur metal bands.

Unlike some other subcultures, the metalhead’s subculture lacks a pronounced ideology and concentrates only around music. Nevertheless, there are some features of the worldview that can be called typical for a significant part of metalheads. The texts of metal groups propagate independence and self-confidence, the cult of “strong personality”. For many metalheads, subculture serves as a means of escapism, alienation from the "gray reality ", a form of youth protest.

To conclude, some researchers claim that listeners of hard rock and metal have a higher craving for aggression and depression. However, psychologists say that this is not a consequence, but the reason for the passion for heavy music. Moreover, respondents who showed negative trends felt better and more confident after listening to their favorite music. According to them, heavy aggressive music helps them to pour out negative emotions, not to accumulate them in themselves. Thus, some metalheads consciously or unconsciously use metal as a means of psychotherapy.

TRADITIONAL HOSPITALITY IN BELARUS

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In the field of tourism, it is important to know the features of hospitality, culture and tradition. And in this article we will look at the features of one small but quite interesting country known as "White Russia".

The name Belarus probably derives from the Middle Ages geographic designation of the area as "White Russia." Historians and linguists argue about its etymology, but it was possibly used as a folk name referring to northern territories. Historic sources mention Belarus during the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries as a geographic name; it later gained specific political meaning, including nation-state identification.

Although Belarusians are the dominant ethnic group in the country, the culture includes people of various ethnicities such as Lithuanians, Poles, Ukrainians, Russians, Jews, and Tartars. The richness and blend of the culture reflects the complexity of ethnic interactions at this region.

Belarus, country of eastern Europe, is completely surrounded by land. But despite this, Belarus attracts a sufficient number of tourists. It is also important to admit major cities of Belarus: Minsk (capital), Gomel, Mogilev, Vitebsk, Grodno, Brest.

Urban centers such as Minsk have been important in the development of Eastern European architecture since the eleventh century. Important religious monuments include the Saint Sophia Cathedral in Polotsk (begun in 1044), and churches such as Saint Euphrocine - Saviour Church in Polotsk, the Annunciation Church in Vitebsk, the Saint Boris and Gleb Church in Grodno (all built in the twelfth century).

First impression of Belarus and its capital Minsk is delighted. "Sardeckna zaprashayem!" is the traditional expression used when welcoming guests, who are

usually presented with bread and salt. Shaking hands is the common form of greeting. Hospitality is part of the Belarusian tradition; people are welcoming and friendly.

During my stay in Minsk I visited various sights of the city, such as the Upper Town, Trinity Suburb, Islands of Tears, Independence square. Withal there are many buildings of the Stalin era, historical battle fortifications and untouched forests. One of the main attractions is the State Museum of the History of the Great Patriotic War [1].

The architecture of the central part of the capital is unique because it combines the styles of different centuries. In recent years, the historical center of Minsk has got its original appearance and its famous Town Hall in particular.

And now I'd like to focus on Trinity Suburb it is the city center, home of large administrative buildings and old churches, it is the only area left undamaged during the Second World War. The typical houses in a range of colors are reflected in the waters of the little Svislach river.

Walking through the historical part of the city was very interesting and fascinating. Each building has its own unique style and it can't do without attracting attention.

Of course, we cannot do without shopping in such malls as "Stolitsa" and "Galleria".

"Stolitsa" mall is one of the unusual shopping centers, because it is located underground. The mall features more than 130 shops and boutiques, which occupy 3 levels, kiosks, cafes, kids room, photo services, bank offices, public catering, entertainment etc.

At the weekend we visited the amusement Parks and the famous Minsk water Park "Lebyazhy". Chelyuskintsev Park and Gorky Park are very popular among Belarusians, because it is an exciting place of rest for the whole family. The parks provide a range of activities both for adults and children and animators take the lead in it.

Also I can't do without saying of a very important issue Belarusian cuisine. Belarusian eating habits are not very different from those of people in other Eastern

European cultures. They usually have three main daily meals, and staples include red meat and potatoes. Favorite Belarusian dishes include borscht, a soup made with beats that is served hot with sour cream; filet à la Minsk and Minsk cutlet; potato dishes with mushrooms; and pickled berries [2].

Finally, I want to mention Belarus is country with a highly developed infrastructure and hospitality. Visiting this country you will have only positive impressions.

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OPTIONS OF OVERSEAS TOURISM PROMOTION

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International tourism and tourism related economic activities play an important role in the sustainable development of countries. Overseas tourism is becoming more and more required and popular because of a number of benefits. First of all you have a chance to meet new people, new culture, enjoy picturesque and exotic views, gain useful skills and experience, kill your fears and get exciting impressions for the rest of your life.

A research provides the statistic data that international tourism is even more economic than domestic one. As a matter of fact nowadays tourist industry in Donetsk faces some difficulties. But in spite of this there are more than forty travel agencies in our city. Our citizens have a rang of options for overseas travels.

I would like to share my experience of working in Donetsk travel agency «Geography» as a tourism manager. The result of our work is a rich experience in tourism, the creation of a professional team, the deserved trust of partners and the recognition of customers. We always remember our obligation to partners and tourists, having a reputation as one of the most reliable travel companies: our travel agency is responsible for choosing tour operators for joint activities, and our company's readiness to provide real assistance to tourists and subagents in any problematic situations.

Any trip is based on the elaboration of the plan. If we are talking about the so-called «Package tour», all the details are thought out by the travel agency and the host party. In this case, all that is left to such a traveler «Pack your bags and hit the road».

One of the most important responsibilities of travel agency's activities is to attract our potential customers attention to available tourist destinations and bring the profit to the agency.

Truly speaking promotion of tourist destination takes a lot of careful planning. First you have to decide exactly what your region offers to visitors- the weather, the natural features (beaches, mountains, scenery), the culture, historical buildings, landmarks,etc.

Next, you need to identify your target market. This means knowing who your customers are. What are they interested in? How much money will they spend ?

Then you need to decide on the objectives for your campaign. Are you trying to attract new visitors, keep your existing customers, or raise awareness about your region?

And at last , you need to plan your resources- this means how much money, how much time , and how many people. Think about all the activities within your campaign, give each one a budget (money), a schedule (time), and the people to make sure it happens.

Finally, it should be mentioned that tourism is one of the fastest-growing industries in the world. It offers some exciting careers and a lot of jobs satisfaction.

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HOW TO KEEP OUR PLANET GREEN

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Since ancient times Nature has served Man, being the source of his life and economists have long thought of the environment as an unlimited source of resources. For thousands of years people lived in harmony with the environment. But with the development of civilization man's interference in nature began to increase. The by-products of people's activity pollute the air we breathe, the water we drink, the fields where crops are grown.

The most urgent environmental problems are acid rains, global warming, toxic pollution of atmosphere, the ozone layer, logging, contamination of underground waters by chemicals, destruction of soil which brings threat to flora and fauna.

One of the most important problems is pollution of the seas and oceans. They are filled with industrial and nuclear waste, chemical fertilizers and pesticides. The Mediterranean is already nearly dead; the North Sea is following. The Aral Sea is close to extinction. Nearly half of the lakes in North America are polluted by

chemical wastes, often dumped by the companies. Polluted water kills fish and other marine life. If nothing is done about it, we won't be able to preserve that life.

Another big problem is air pollution. With the development of crowded industrial cities which put huge amounts of pollutants into small areas, the problem has become urgent. Every year world industry pollutes the atmosphere with about 1000 million tons of dust and other harmful substances. These emissions have disastrous consequences for our planet. They are the main reason of the greenhouse effect and acid rains. Factories, though providing job and necessary goods for people, pollute the air and the water. On polluted soil food cannot be grown. In addition, environmental pollution spoils the natural beauty of our planet.

Automobiles and other new inventions which throw emissions into the air constantly degrade pollution. Many cities suffer from smog.

By the way, one of the most serious environmental problems of many British cities is smog. It's a kind of thick fog, mixed with the smoke from factories and fireplaces in private houses. In autumn and in winter it is so thick that cars sometimes run into one another. Unusually thick smog in London in 1962 caused the death of some 4000 people.

For many people, the most alarming of all human assaults on the environment is the contamination of air, earth, and water from dumping. Evidence of dumping can be found everywhere, done by individuals and large corporations alike. Hong Kong dumps more than 1,000 tons of plastic a day. Americans throw away 16 billion disposable diapers each year. Open sewage drains and landfills are common sites in many parts of the world.

In a small Malaysian village, babies are born deformed and children die of rare illnesses, which their doctors claim are caused by exposure to radiation from a multinational company that set up business in this small community.

The rapid reduction of forest land around the globe appears on every list of critical environmental issues. Its effects are of importance to all living things. Forests absorb carbon dioxide from the air and supply oxygen. They are home to fragile

plants and fascinating creatures, and they have provided people with fuel, food, and shelter for centuries. But with the growth in human population, forests have been converted into farms, commercial enterprises, and industrial developments.

It is estimated that every year 6.3 million hectares of tropical forest alone are cleared for agriculture and that 4.4 million hectares are used in commercial logging. Big corporations buy large chunks of forest in order to cut down and export timber to Europe, Japan, and North America. One-tenth of all the timber for this market comes from tropical forests of such countries as Brazil, Indonesia, Malaysia, and the Philippines [1].

In Russia and the former Soviet republics there are environmental areas which require special attention. Some of them are the Aral Sea, Lake Baikal, the Kuzbass, Semipalatinsk and Chernobyl. The reasons are the following:

1. Cotton growing in the region of the Aral Sea has used huge quantities of water, and the level of the sea has fallen by 14 yards.
2. For decades nuclear weapons were tested near Semipalatinsk, and the ground is contaminated with radiation there.
3. More than twenty years ago a pulp-and-paper factory was built on the shore of Lake Baikal. As a result of the pollution, more than 50 per cent of the world's purest water has been ruined. The whole ecological system of the lake has changed greatly.
4. The consequences of this explosion at the Chernobyl atomic power-station which took place in April 1986 are tragic for Ukraine, Byelorussia and other nations. Most territory of Ukraine and about 18 percent of the territory of Byelorussia were polluted with radioactive substances. The inhabitants of the nearby towns and villages had to be evacuated. Some of them died and some became disabled.

So, we can see that environmental problems are no longer problems of one particular country or nation.

Here is the result of the survey on the amount of pollution in Donetsk region which presents information collected over the past three years:

Ecological problems	Pollution Index
AirPollution	75.00 high
Water Pollution	80.00 very high
Drinking Water Pollution	65.00 high
Garbage Disposal	45.00 moderate
Saturation of parks and green areas	40.00 moderate

Environmental protection is of a universal concern. That is why serious measures to create a system of ecological security should be taken. Some progress has been already made in this direction. As many as 159 countries — members of the UNO — have set up environmental protection agencies. Numerous conferences have been held by these agencies to discuss problems facing ecologically poor regions including the Aral Sea, the South Urals, Kuzbass, Donbass, Semipalatinsk and Chernobyl. An international environmental research centre has been set up on Lake Baikal.

Many people belong to Green organizations in countries all over the world. Groups like "Green Peace" have already helped to stop some animals hunting and forced Government to make environmental laws tougher.

The news is good that many countries are working hard to reduce acid rains. Scientists are trying to figure out ways to make coal burning cleaner. As a result in many countries the amount of sulfates in the air has dropped and less acid rain is falling.

A lot of care is taken about water pollution problem, too. Some rivers and lakes have been made much cleaner. And there are big plans to clean up other bodies of water.

What else can be done to protect nature?

I believe that environment disasters can be avoided if people broaden ecological education and try to understand that the beauty of nature which is extremely fragile. Governments must be prepared to take action against pollution and, probably, introduce financial measures to make plants and factories use effective filters to reduce contamination of the air.

Recycling waste and rubbish, which received ever-greater care in Europe, should be accepted by other countries. Cans, paper and empty bottles and other things are accumulated in the environment. Today some companies have started projects which benefit energy saving recycling and refused some product packaging. Such practices should be appreciated all over the world.

Natural resources should be used economically because their stocks are not unlimited.

It's a good idea to protected and extended green zones around big cities.

So, we see that the humans have started doing much to preserve the environment. But these are only the initial steps. There is still much to be done. A lot of efforts should be taken to protect nature, to save life on the planet not only for the sake of the present but also for the future generations.

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DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL SKILLS THROUGH TOURISM ACTIVITY

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The paper deals with approaches to developing professional skills through the experience of working in hospitality and tourism industry. To become successful and efficient sphere of tourism a number of professional skills is required, the most essential ones may be as follows:

1. Customer service skills. Above all else, the one thing that can make or break you in hospitality is your ability to meet customers expectations. Remember: the more positive the experience you provide, the more likely you are to receive good feedback – and a good tip, too.

2. Cultural Awareness

In hospitality, a large percentage of the customers you face (and, indeed, people you work alongside) will be from abroad. As a result, your ability to be culturally aware and adapt to attitudes and norms that are different from your own is crucial to building a successful career.

3. Communication Skills

Strong communication skills are highly valued in every industry, but especially so in hospitality and tourism. Each day, you will be dealing with people from a variety of backgrounds, ages, nationalities and temperaments, so it is important that you can communicate in a way that is both clear and understandable, as well as representative of your employer's brand.

4. Multitasking Skills

One of the reasons why hospitality can be so difficult to work in is because it's almost always hectic. In most cases, there's no such thing as a quiet day in the office and, therefore, the ability to multitask and handle several tasks at once will serve you well. This means learning how to prioritise and manage your time effectively, while

you'll also need to be able to handle pressure and remain calm when things get chaotic.

5. Work Ethic

If you're going to work in hospitality, then regardless of your role, you're going to have to work hard. All while maintaining a cheerful and friendly façade in front of customers.

6. Teamwork Skills

Working in hospitality and tourism you are always a part of the team and it's very important to be able to do well with others especially during busy periods.

In hospitality, regardless of your role, you will always only ever be one cog in a much larger machine. Whether it's within a particular hotel department, in a busy kitchen or as part of the bar staff, you need to be able to work well with others, especially during busy periods.

7. Problem-Solving Skills

the ability to think on your feet and solve problems quickly can save yourself a lot of potential hassle.

8. Language Skills

language skills are a huge bonus in this field because they allow you to communicate with a wider range of clients. Language skills can also benefit your career in the long term, too.

From my childhood I have studied English ,because I know how important it is for me. Without it I couldn't feel so comfortable. English is an international language not only in business, education, science and technology, but first of all in tourism. Regardless of what language is spoken in a particular country , the role of the English language remains very important.

Two years ago I understood that I want to get some experience abroad. I found a position of hostess in the Rixos Sungate hotel in Turkey. My duties as a hostess were to meet the guests, to check the reservations, to help with choosing a table, to give some advice on a menu, to solve the troubles if they occurred. My working day lasted from 4 p.m. to 12 a.m. For me it was very interesting: every day I met new

people from all the world. I made friends with some people from our team, a lot of them spoke English. So I had good experience.

I became more stressful, responsible, independent, I studied new things and got new skills.

My experience in tourism sphere made me sure that, first of all, you need language skills as a basis for work abroad and career promotion. Without it you can't even understand what you have to do. All other skills are definitely necessary and interlinked.

In conclusion I would like to focus: if you possess the above mentioned skills, there's no reason why you can't be successful. Whether it is for a part-time summer job or an entire career, the basis of everything you will need is the same.

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THE PROBLEMS OF COUCHSURFING AS A KIND OF SELF - ORGANIZED TOURISM

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Back in 1999, "hacker" and traveler Casey Fenton had no idea that his idea for a website to connect travelers with locals would be so popular. He was simply looking for an inexpensive way to visit Iceland. When the site launched in 2004, it had lots of people asking: What is couchsurfing?

Roughly two years later, the website became such a popular tool for budget travelers that it crashed. Much of the database and registered-member information were lost. Through the help of volunteers and donations, the site was rebuilt from the ground up to be more scalable.

Today, the newly resurrected Couchsurfing.com site has a community of over 15 million travelers and 400,000 hosts; lasting friendships and great experiences are formed there every day.

Even with using a few tricks to save money on accommodation, sleeping costs typically end up being the biggest expense for budget travelers. The idea behind couchsurfing is simple: "Couchsurfers" leverage the hospitality of friendly people around the world who open their homes to travelers—an act of kindness that dates back millennia.

Money shouldn't be exchanged, but bringing a host a thoughtful gift is good road karma. A trinket from your home country or bottle of wine will work, however, neither are expected. If turning up empty handed, offer to cover a meal or the groceries to cook at home.

What is expected from you as a couchsurfer is a little interaction. Just as when hitchhiking, the recipient of a freebie should interact with hosts, not just use them for

convenience. Don't remain aloof or so busy that your host winds up feeling used or neglected. A big part of the couchsurfing experience is having a local available for giving advice that can't be found in the guidebook. Their insider recommendations can save you money and enhance your trip.

Although staying with complete strangers seem inherently dangerous, particularly if you watch the nightly news, the social-network system on Couchsurfing.com is designed to weed out bad hosts and guests. A lot of emphasis (tips, suggestions, etc) is placed on safety—for obvious reasons.

First, you can choose what type of host with whom you wish to stay (e.g., male, female, family, etc). You can get a feel for their personalities and interests based on their public profiles. The more time and information put into your own profile, the better. Couchsurfing.com recommends having conversation (through the Couchsurfing website) and asking relevant questions before agreeing to stay with a host.

Before choosing a host, you can see reviews left by other travelers who stayed before you. If the public reviews don't provide enough confidence, you can even contact those travelers privately to see if they had a good experience and would stay with a particular host again.

Couchsurfing.com once made use of a vouching system to increase safety. A multi-level account verification system prevents people from dumping old profiles and starting new ones if they get a bad review. Sticking to verified, experienced hosts is one way to increase safety. The app allows people to photograph their government IDs to gain verification [1].

To sum up, couchsurfing is pig in a poke due to lots of reasons including peoples' habits, characters and even emotions. It seems a little bit of nervous to find something in common with people who you stay with on couple days. On the other hand, the thing is not even in free accommodation – a traveler who looks for

adventures would never change low-cost bedroom on communicating with local people and observe their traditions, native language and whole country's atmosphere.

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MODERN CULTURE: DEVELOPMENT IN THE DONETSK PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC

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The giving paper is aimed at highlighting of the main approaches and principles of all cultivating modern culture nowadays.

The Donetsk People's Republic is faced the issue of forming a worthwhile, future-oriented policy in the area of culture and the functioning Ukrainian, Russian and other languages. This problem requires a response of society to at least three questions: what is culture? What does modernization of culture mean? What is modern culture?

By this time, such uncertainty led to stagnation in the sphere of culture and conflicts in definition the areas of language functioning , the loss of cultural contexts.

Throughout the formation of the Donetsk People's Republic, we have been observing a reduction in the cultural context, deterioration in quality of cultural offers, stagnation of cultural industries, the mastery of market culture by foreign cultural industries, inefficient squandering of cultural resources of the Republic, which should be aimed at the effective development of the cultural context and even the expansion of cultural industries abroad .

Culture in the broad sense of the word is: religion and morality; values and ideals; knowledge and views; ideas and traditions; and lifestyle in in general.

In such a broad sense, the word culture defines the identity of a particular human society, ethnic group, folks, nation, region or continent. It distinguishes such societies among other human societies and their cultures as a manifestation of alternative integrity. This integrity contains history, the idea of values, the experience of one's own identity and the identity of others, as well as goals in relation to the present and the future, the expectations and visions of various communities.

Culture determines the identity of a particular human society, in our case.

We suggest starting work on the modernization of culture in the Donetsk People's Republic with a SWOT analysis of cultural resources, opportunities, and the competitiveness of the cultural paradigm of modern society. The analysis should refer to a much wider range of problems, for example, work culture, trust level, capacity for cooperation, social capital, etc.

At the same time, we must take into account that the adoption of new values is synchronized with the emerging of a new generation. We will also gain the benefits of modernization after we make the first move towards a global (or world-wide) and high-quality study of English language. Scientific-cultural take-off can be realized in the best conditions only after 20 years.

Therefore, the modernization program of culture should be designed for the future prospect, and not only for the maintenance of stagnant cultural institutions.

The growth of social capital (including in the cultural sphere), the continuation of the tradition to preserve identity, the implementation of new values, especially for young people, should be aimed at modernization of cultural sphere, which is construed broadly:

- preservation of cultural diversity;
- the development of cultural industries;

- implement a cultural policy based on such factors as: governmental authorities; self-governing bodies, where most of the cultural product is created;

- personified sponsorship;

- business in the field of culture (film industry, show business, circus, etc.)

– implement a cultural policy, legislatively distributing the bailiwick of all these participants in the market for creating a cultural product.

Summarizing all above mentioned information, we may make up the following conclusion.

The state will not be able and can no longer control or support all spheres of culture (cinema, show business, circus, etc.).

It is affair of a state to regulate the market for cultural offers and support extremely unique cultural phenomena, as well as the educational sphere.

SPEECH ETIQUETTE AS ONE OF THE PROBLEMS IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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English seems an easy language, but people have some problems when they learn it. One of these problems is speech etiquette. Direct address, greetings, closings and introduction are the basis of speech etiquette.

When you greet somebody, you call him by his first name, surname and title. You can also use official form: the title and surname (Dr. Brown, Professor Jones). But Americans do not like official forms and use first names. As a rule they say: «Why don't you call me...(first name)?»

Greetings

The words of greeting usually do not have literal meaning. People say: «good afternoon», even if the day is bad.

To the greeting: «How are you? » The British and Americans always answer: «Fine, thanks. How are you? » But in the answer a stress is on the word you.

Closings/Leave – takings. Preclosings

As a rule people do not stop a conversation suddenly. It is not polite to stand up, say: «Good bye» and leave. Usually people say preclosings before leaving.

For example:

- Well? It's getting late.
- I really must be going now.
- Maybe we could get together sometime.

There are people who ignore preclosings. If you are with friends, is not a big problem. But, in official conversations, ignoring preclosings is rude. Introduction.

Official introduction: first of all, the first name and surname are given (sometimes also the title) of the person whom we are introducing. Then we give a short information about this person.

Sometimes people have to introduce themselves.

American «OK»

Remember when we can use OK:

1. Instead of «You're welcome» when somebody says to you: «Thank you». Also we can say «Welcome» or «Sure» instead of «You're welcome».

2. When you answer the greeting: «Hello! How are you?» you say: «Thank you I'm OK». You say «OK» even when you feel bad.

3. When you agree with somebody or when you are pleased with something you also say «OK».

4. When you talk about your health.

5. «OK» is a synonym of the word combination «All right».

«Sorry» and «Excuse me»

Excuses are the biggest problem for our people especially in the USA because Americans ask for excuses all the time. But when should we say «Excuse me» and when «Sorry»? it is very easy. You say «Excuse me» when you intend to interrupt somebody and you say «Sorry» when you have already troubled somebody.

How to get off the bus?

«To get» is a word used in many ways. But we are interested in the form «to get off». One of the meanings of this verb is to get off the bus, train and other transport. In Great Britain and in the USA, we should not ask: «Are you getting off?» It is not appropriate to ask somebody about personal affairs. We should say: «Excuse me, I'm getting off».

«Yeah» and «Yes»

«Yeah» and «Yes» in American English. We often hear in from Americans but now we can safely say «Yeah» in Great Britain. «Yes» is used in Britain only in writing now.

How to speak when you call somebody?

When you call friends you may talk as you want. If it is a conversation with an unknown person, your teacher, your friend's parents, etc., first of all you should tell your name and greet them. If the person you are calling is out, you should say: «Could you take a message for ...(name)?».

Speech etiquette is an important part of national culture. If we do not know the speech etiquette of the country and say something wrong, it will be an insult. That's why we should learn it. We should practice with people who know speech etiquette well. English and American movies and books will also help us with this problem.

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ORGANIZATION OF CULTURAL AND LEISURE ACTIVITIES OF THE ELDERLY (THIRD-AGED) PERSONS

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The ageing of population is an obvious consequence of the process of demographic transition. The Donetsk People's Republic is also facing a steady growth of the number of elderly people, which a result of the decline in fertility and mortality, better medical and health care and improvements in the overall quality of people's life. Reaching a senior age and retirement opens a new period person's life. Being active throughout the major part of one's lifetime has an important influence on overall health and well-being.

A review of current literature indicates that people who participate in sports clubs and organized recreational activity enjoy better mental health, are more alert, and more pliable against the stresses of modern living. Engaged in recreational

groups and socially supported physical activity is shown to overcome stress, anxiety and depression.

Physical activity and tourism offer a perfect way to satisfy most needs, which determine successful ageing. Accordingly, giving elderly people opportunities to be active and encouraging them to lead an active life should not only be one of the highest priorities of the social policy of the state or local authorities, but also a deliberate action of the society as a whole.

When preparing their offer, providers of tourist and leisure services ought to take into account the specific features of the target group, and be conscious that seniors:

- are demanding buyers and expect that their consumer experience will be respected;
- seek high-quality products and services;
- seek what is healthy and natural; they want to know the origin of the product they wish to buy; they are not attached to any particular brand;
- want to fully utilise their time;
- appreciate all that help them save their time;
- want to feel confident about their health, appearance, clothes and contacts with other people;
- fear being laughed at and they are sometimes ashamed of their appearance;
- need solid arguments when deciding whether to buy a product or engage in some activity;
- are not very sensitive to mass media advertising; to reach them, other communication channels should be used (mainly the so-called personal channels: doctors, nurses, family members, friends, moral authorities belonging to the same generation);
- may have problems using modern technologies (mobile phone, computer, Internet), or understanding instruction manuals and marketing materials; they should be treated with all due understanding and patience;

– seek authenticity and genuineness, they look for their “roots”, and they are interested in cultural heritage and tradition;

– manage their time in a different way than professionally active individuals; they prefer to engage in various activities in the mornings and on weekdays;

– expect that service providers will adapt their products to the limitations caused by poor health, failing eyesight, or lower mobility (e.g. larger font in advertising brochures, leaflets and catalogues; comfortable means of transport; elimination of architectural barriers).

Respecting the specific features and expectations of the clients (seniors) in a leisure offer will undoubtedly result in the situation that this particular social group will find more satisfaction in leisure services, which in turn, can motivate them to engage more actively in recreation in the physical, cultural and social dimension.

THE WORLD IS SPORT

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Sport is a very important thing in the life of millions people. Sport makes people healthy, stronger and more organized. A person’s life is quite short and you should not spend it on useless things, such as drinking alcohol or drugs. Everyone can take care of their health, and this concern lies not only in a healthy diet, but also in sports.

There are many sports that will keep an adult in shape, and a child to develop and shape a sports physique. It all starts from childhood, a love of sport should appear precisely in these years. When a teenager is passionate about sports, there is much less chance that he will fall under the bad influence of the street. Exercising in any

sport, in addition to being in good physical shape, also teaches discipline. For example, having given a child to play sports, it will immediately become noticeable that he is acquiring a certain discipline and is always ready to be responsible for his actions and actions. Sport can change the lives of adolescents, as well as adults, but it's more logical to talk about children, because they are the country's hope and support and I would not want the younger generation to lead an unhealthy lifestyle.

First of all, from childhood, a child should be encouraged by parents to play sports, and it is important to understand that playing sports should be pleasant. After all, the factor that the child is forcibly driven to the sports section will have a very bad effect. You need to understand what the child likes. Do not torment him, for example, boxing, maybe the child wants to engage in team sports. And it doesn't matter at all, maybe a person likes chess or billiards. And this is also good, because the child will not disappear on the street and is unlikely to get into some kind of trouble. In sport, we make new friends. Sport increases our activity, taking us beyond the framework of the familiar world, and sometimes it changes our quality of life so much that many friends are amazed at the changes that have occurred. And the best part is that you gradually start to get drawn into this new living space, and you like it.

Speaking of myself: I like to do sport. Sport helps us to harden and become healthier. The world of sports is diverse: football, basketball, volleyball, swimming, etc. I love active entertainment. As far as I can remember, I always played a variety of outdoor games. And I got incredible pleasure from it. It is not necessary to be a professional athlete in order to benefit and enjoy playing sports. Many of the people run in the mornings, someone goes to fitness, someone plays soccer or does karate. The main thing is to like it. And at the same time, it makes you physically strong and self-confident, and also makes it possible to meet many interesting people.

My favorite sport is ballroom dancing. There is nothing more beautiful kind of sport in the art world. Ballroom dance is the embodiment of music; they are reflected in movements, figures and compositions. It is impossible to be indifferent to dancing, because currently there are a huge number of different directions, and

everyone can find exactly what is interesting to him. Such diversity is due to differences between peoples of different countries and different eras. Each dance is special and reflects the character and behavior of a person. Dancing helps: improve mood; gain self-confidence; instilled composure; improve relationships with other people; to know your own body; learn to manage it; improve posture, cardiovascular and respiratory systems; boost immunity; to be slim, flexible, strong and fit.

I have been going in for sport such as ballroom dancing for 5 years. Mom supports my endeavors, so she takes me to contests and various competitions. Dance is a part of my life, I really like dancing and consider myself an absolutely happy person.

Nowadays, ballroom dancing is very popular, they host tournaments around the world. Sports ballroom dancing is divided into 2 programs: European and Latin American. The European program includes: slow waltz, tango, Viennese waltz, slow foxtrot, quickstep (fast foxtrot).

In Latin American: samba, cha-cha-cha, rumba, paso doble, jive.

European program. Ladies should wear special, eligible ball gowns. Cavaliers should be dressed in tailcoats of black or dark blue color and wear a bow tie.

Latin American program. Ladies dresses are usually short, very open and tight (in accordance with the same requirements). Cavalier suits are also very tight-fitting, often (but not always) black. The meaning of such suits is to show the muscles of athletes.

In conclusion, I would like to note that each sport is important in its own way, especially in the life of adolescents. Those who play sports lead a healthy lifestyle, control their weight and follow a diet, usually more cheerful and less susceptible to disease. While those who prefer fast food and do not play sports are more prone to obesity and are at risk for cardiovascular disease. In my opinion, sport is important for healthy spending free time, Sport makes people strong and happy cheerful.

PECULIARITIES OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN SOME EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

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Over the past few decades, the landscape of higher education in Europe has changed dramatically. To respond to social, technological and cultural changes, higher education has transformed from an elite to a mass and, finally, to a universal one.

In Europe, there are a lot of different, but equally recognized approaches, providing a wide range of institutional goals, values and positions within the curriculum, design and delivery, skill levels, research, development and community involvement. More attention is paid to meeting the needs of society, the characteristics of graduates' employment and the increasing role of higher education in the framework of the lifelong learning concept and communication with relevant structures.

Each state's higher education system has advantages and disadvantages. However, all the advantages are subjective, so we will highlight only objective features. Let's look at the peculiarities of higher education system in four leading European countries: the UK, Germany, France and Italy.

The UK Department of Education grants applicants the right to choose a university, a technical institute, or a college. Colleges of higher education allow getting a bachelor's degree. By and large, these are professional courses that train specialists in a particular field. The possible disadvantage of such an education is that students who have graduated from college do not have an opportunity to be qualified for a master's degree.

Technical institutes are suitable for those who have chosen any narrow specialization, since it is better to study at a specialized university right away. In ordinary universities, for two years, students study general subjects, and in subsequent years, profile. Moreover, British students have an opportunity to attend lectures and seminars of other faculties, then to pass the exam and get a double diploma. The best British universities are Cambridge and Oxford.

Study at British universities traditionally lasts for 4-5 years, at some faculties, for example, medical and architectural – up to 7 years.

Higher educational institutions offer tuition on a fee-paying basis both for foreigners and citizens of the UK. Citizens of the country can get student loans, which they begin to repay only after receiving a diploma and applying for a job with a minimum wage of GBP 21,000 per year. Recently, in parliament, more and more members are inclined to increase the cost of training. Such initiatives are unpopular among students.

The main principle of German higher education is academic freedom. To enter the university, applicants do not need to take exams, but they must have an appropriate certificate of secondary education. To enter the university, foreigners must pass an exam confirming knowledge of the German language. Education in many universities in Germany is free both for German citizens and foreigners.

The principle of academic freedom is understood as the ability of students to independently choose basic and additional educational courses, as well as draw up an individual educational plan. Free attendance of lectures is also allowed, but this does not exempt students from further certification in selected disciplines.

Higher education institutions in Germany can be divided into:

- 1) Humanities Universities;
- 2) Higher schools that train specialists in certain areas (engineering, design, business, etc);

3) Large universities, in which faculties and specialties of various kinds are represented. Here, students are engaged in basic and applied research. A wide variety of subjects makes it possible for students to receive interdisciplinary education.

One of the most attractive features of higher education in Germany is its practical orientation. The possibility of gaining not only academic knowledge in a subject but also practical experience at the same time is a valuable qualification for any job market. The dual study model in Germany is a model to many other countries to follow.

In term of researching, Germany offers a broad spectrum of possibilities, mainly because of the links between academics and enterprises. Many highly specialized companies of small and median size are looking for students whose research proposals serve their market goals. Faculties and professors quite often have joint projects with local companies and this academic/enterprise bond fosters many of the research possibilities.

Italian higher education system is represented by universities, technical universities, university colleges, conservatories and academies. In Italy, people usually enter universities when they are 19 years old.

The first stage of higher education is C. D. U. (Corsi di Diploma Universitario), which is an analogue of a bachelor's degree. The training lasts for 3 years and consists of compulsory, additional subjects and practice. The second stage of higher education is C. L. (Corsi di Laurea). It lasts from 2 to 5 years, depending on the specialty. Medicine and pharmaceuticals have been studied for 6 years.

The third stage of higher education is Corsi di Dottorato di Ricerca, DR and Corsi di Perfezionamento, i.e. doctoral research programs and postgraduate courses, or professional excellence. It can be attended both at universities and in specialized educational institutions, Scuole di Specializzazione. Upon completion, a specialist diploma or a doctor's degree is issued.

France ranks first among non-English-speaking countries in the number of foreign students studying there. Every third doctorate is awarded to a foreigner.

In France, there are three types of higher educational institutions: universities, higher schools and specialized schools. Most universities are state-owned and essentially do not differ much from universities in other countries. But the education system in higher schools deserves separate explanations. These are small educational institutions, in which the annual enrollment may not exceed 50 people. As a rule, they specialize in a narrow circle of disciplines, such as: engineering, business, pedagogy, etc. They have close ties with enterprises or government departments. Higher schools provide two types of education:

- 1) Higher schools (Grandes écoles), which are a «superstructure» over the already begun education;

- 2) Bachelor and master degrees according to the scheme 3 + 2 years.

The first type of program is available only in French. Specialized schools provide education in the following areas: fine and applied arts, cooking, paramedicine, journalism, theater, etc. Some specialties can only be obtained in specialized schools.

The issue of getting quality higher education in Europe is becoming more and more topical. Today, students look to the future with thoughts about the best learning conditions, the quality of the diploma, the status of the university, and, of course, the practical application of all the knowledge that is subsequently translated into employment in a successful company. Education in European higher educational institutions may be compared with the creation of a solid foundation, on the basis of which young specialists will build their professional life, path to success, development and financial well-being.

ART THROUGH THE EYES OF YOUTH

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Today the problem of art among young people is the most urgent, since young people have ceased to be interested in culture. Now it is very rare to meet young people in museums, theaters, galleries. In the modern information world, young people are fixated only on themselves and their problems, they do not break away from their gadgets. This can lead to negative consequences, namely, degradation of the population.

The aim of this work is the analysis of art in the modern world, as well as the identification of the causes characterizing the ignorance and ignorance of young people in matters of art.

The study of the aesthetic culture of the population and its artistic orientations has been and remains a problem that attracts the attention of researchers. In modern dynamic reality, we become witnesses and participants in socio-economic processes, which, in turn, affect changes in society. The results of scientific research, in general, complement the sad picture. A sociological survey conducted in Rostov-on-Don showed that 73.3% of young viewers aged 16 to 18 justify their choice of films with the opportunity to “disconnect” from everyday reality and “leave” in the bright, unfamiliar world of cinema; 46.6% - a desire to have fun and remove negative emotions; 30.0% - the desire to see your favorite actors on the screen. And only 6.6% of the young Rostovites surveyed explained their on-screen preferences by a tendency to think about any life problems [0].

Undoubtedly, in the system of sociocultural preferences of youth, theater art is increasingly shifting to the background. This can be explained by the low availability of theatrical art for a wide audience (concentration of theaters in large cities, high ticket prices for both local and touring theaters). But not only this leads to a low

interest in theatrical art. We can sadly note the underdevelopment of a significant part of the youth in theatrical theater culture, and a low level of general humanitarian training.

The main motives for young audiences to visit the cinema halls, theater performances, their choice of computer disks, DVDs, CDs, Internet sites, as a rule, are non-artistic motives - the desire to have fun, relax, “relax”, change the atmosphere, etc. Artistic and aesthetic motifs for most of the audience are secondary or do not matter at all.

The culture of the Soviet era set as its first task the upbringing and adoption of ideology, while the entertaining component of culture was insignificant. In the absence of an alternative, people consumed what the state supplied them.

Young people today consume the culture that television offers. In the content of contemporary art, adolescents often encounter the humiliation, deformation and destruction of the image of a person. In works of art, episodes and scenes of violence and cruelty often appear, which often contradict morality and have a negative impact on the younger generation - this is a problem of all world cultures [2].

However, the younger generation continues to create art. Passion for dancing and martial arts, a new word in modern art culture - graffiti, body art as a means of artistic expression, literary experiences - all this brings new, bright colors to the art.

In modern society, mass culture can be at a fairly high artistic level, and, entertaining a person, distracting him from everyday problems, educate him, attach him to world culture, science, philosophy.

Thus, in the modern world can not do without art. It is an integral part of our life. We believe that the state should cultivate the population, therefore it is necessary to create a greater number of musical theaters, historical museums. But first of all, parents should explain to children how important it is to be cultural and educated, because nowadays there's nowhere to go. In schools and institutes, measures should be taken to cultivate modern youth. But do not forget about yourself. Try to spend less time at a laptop, read books, take an interest in poetry, classical music, painting, expand your horizons.

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DEVELOPMENT OF SPORTS IN THE DONETSK PEOPLES' REPUBLIC

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The article shows that development of sports tends to be a factor of country competitiveness and main sports development issues in the country. Nowadays, there is a need to find new forms and methods of promotion and popularization of physical culture and sport, to create a single sports information space and to provide sports area with more effective managerial decisions.

Keywords: Development of sports, professional athletes, martial law, sports schools and clubs, psychological education

Active people are healthier people. And the sports and fitness habits they form at an early age are the ones that they will carry through life. Obviously, the great advantages that can be taken going in for sports are:

- fitness (in struggling with weight, a daily dose of exercise goes a long way);
- life skills (you can learn a lot in sports that you will use the rest of your life);
- academic success (studies show that athletes also tend to do better in school and have lower dropout rates than their non-athletic peers);
- less drinking and drug use (research shows that sports can serve).

Speaking about teenagers or young adults' involvement in sports in the Donetsk Peoples' Republic, we can outline several problems that we are going to highlight.

The Donetsk People's Republic was founded in 2014. For the period of more than 5 years area of sports has been permanently changing. At the moment, the problem of the development of sports in the DPR is the main attraction.

It is difficult for the young generation to develop and progress in such a specific environment, professional athletes are especially limited in this regard, but even in spite of this, the conditions for progress of professionals and amateurs are growing every year.

In this article, I would like to consider a few important problems that are related to the main topic of speech.

First, we need to separate the problematic issues into internal and external.

Internal issues involve education of highly qualified specialists in the area of sports and their deficit; financing and low budget of sports schools and clubs; psychological education of young athletes and their attitude to sport.

External issues include the impact of politics on sport and its development.

At the moment, there are several universities in Donetsk where they teach specialists in the field of sports (trainers, medical staff). The first problem is that their education takes place during the war period and, as practice shows, education takes place in a simplified manner. And eventually, we get specialists who find it difficult to find work because of a lack of experience or free vacancies in sports facilities. Also, current sports experts are former athletes who have decent experience in performing, but most of them often do not have special education. The shortage of highly qualified specialists is caused by the fact that most of them have left to work in other countries for more status and profit jobs.

The second difficult issue is financing and the low budget of sports schools and clubs. Currently, in the Republic there are mainly only state-owned sports schools and sections that are funded by public funds. And as practice shows, the state budget is becoming insufficient for the effective development of sports. In the meantime, due to the political status of the state, there is also a lack of sponsors who could help in

resolving this issue. And all these issues add up to the indifferent attitude of young people to sports, which brings us to the next question.

The third issue is the psychological education and attitude of youth athletes to sport. The question is quite difficult since there are many factors that can affect the psychological state of youth. One of such factors is the martial law in the DPR and its influence on the development of sports. It lies in the fact that political status does not allow our sportsmen to fully perform in international tournaments and represent their state. This causes certain problems in the motivation of young athletes, especially those who decided to dedicate themselves to this cause. All of these issues affect the psychological state of athletes. Current specialists cannot motivate and psychologically support young athletes and instill in them a desire to play sports and progress, which is why they later finish doing this permanently. Poor funding affects motivation and results in a lack of goals to achieve. And ultimately, young people have a negative attitude to sports in general.

The external issue is politics, or rather, the political status of the state that prevents athletes from performing at international tournaments and it also scares away sponsors for the development of their own projects.

In my opinion, this issue needs to be primarily dealt with since it is a premise and a basis for resolution of the abovementioned ones.

However, despite all the above-mentioned shortcomings and problems in the area of sports development, the state does everything in its power and, by the strength of its capabilities, solves certain problems in this area.

In conclusion, the state needs to develop in the same direction and, of course, search the ways of solving the above problems in order for the young generation to be physically developed and psychologically strong.

COMPUTER ANIMATION

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Nearly everything we do in the world is helped, or even controlled by computers. Computers are used more and more often in the world today, for the simple reason that they are far more efficient than human beings. They have much better memories and they can store much information. Of course, in the modern world, interest in computer graphics and animation is very high. And today, computer graphics and animation have become part of our lives.

A cartoon is a type of illustration, possibly animated, typically in a non-realistic or semi-realistic style. Someone who creates cartoons in the first sense is called a cartoonist, and in the second sense they are usually called an animator.

The concept originated in the Middle Ages, and first described a preparatory drawing for a piece of art. In the 19th century cartoon came to refer to humorous illustrations in magazines and newspapers. In the early 20th century, it began to refer to animated films which resembled print cartoons. Computer animation is the process used for generating animated images. The more general term (CGI) computer-generated imagery encompasses both static scenes and dynamic images, while computer animation only refers to the moving images. Modern computer animation usually uses 3D computer graphics, although 2D computer graphics are still used for stylistic, low bandwidth, and faster real-time renderings.

Computer animation is essentially a digital successor to the stop motion techniques using 3D models, and traditional animation techniques using frame-by-frame animation of 2D illustrations. Computer-generated animations are more controllable than other more physically based processes, because it allows the creation of images that would not be feasible using any other technology. It can also

allow a single graphic artist to produce such content without the use of actors, expensive set pieces, or props.

For 3D animations, objects (models) are built on the computer monitor (modeled) and 3D figures are rigged with a virtual skeleton. For 2D figure animations, separate objects (illustrations) and separate transparent layers are used with or without that virtual skeleton. Then the limbs, eyes, mouth, clothes, etc. of the figure are moved by the animator on key frames.

CGI that created entire films. Until the late 1990s CGI was used sparingly, but in 1995 *Toy Story* became the first full-length CG feature.

CGI that captured people. As the early 2000's rolled in, audiences were awed once again when a fully-rendered CG character appeared on screen.

In Peter Jackson's 2001 film, *Lord of the Rings*, Gollum was the first motion-captured character to come face to face with other actors. Traditional animation was combined with artificial intelligence software to replace actor Andy Serkis' movements with those of Gollum's.

Today using 2D graphics is considered obsolete. 3D objects with use of color and light really are able to create illusion.

In conclusion I would like to admit that we live in the world of computers. Tasks that were impossible to perform some ten years ago now can be easily accomplished with the help of computer. Today, probably everyone has played some computer games; saw a computer animated cartoon, or a movie with special computer effects.

CGI changed movies, science, art forever...

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ENGLISH CALENDAR

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If we tried to look back to when the first calendars were made we would find that they have been in use for over 2,000 years. This suggests that thousands of years ago people had already discovered patterns of time and seasons. It affected when they planted, harvested, hunted and performed many other of the tasks necessary to their very survival.

However, the calendar we know and use today, the Gregorian calendar, first came into use around 1582. Our use of this calendar is not so very different from the ones used thousands of years ago. We use them to keep track of social events as well as appointments.

This article is devoted to the English calendar, namely to the history of the origin of the names of the months and days of the week.

The relevance of the topic is justified by the fact that the study of any language is impossible without knowledge of the days of the week and months.

The aim of this work is to investigate the etymology and the origin of the names of the months and days of the week in English.

What does the word "calendar" mean? This word comes from the Latin "calendarium". The word "calendar" translates as "debt book". Earlier in such books indicated the first days in each month. These first days were called "Kalends". In Ancient Rome, in the days of the calendar, the debtors paid the interest.

There are several versions of the origin of the names of the days of the week. The most plausible and supported by official science is the version of the formation of the names of the days from the names of the planets.

According to scientists, the tradition of measuring time by seven — day week originated in Ancient Babylon and was associated with the change of phases of the moon. Astrologers noticed "wandering" luminaries in the sky, which they called "planets". They believed that the planets revolve around the Earth in the following order: Moon, Mercury, Venus, Sun, Mars, Jupiter, Saturn. According to the names of the planets and luminaries (in turn, named after the gods) began to call the days of the week. Monday was the day of the Moon, Tuesday — Mars, Wednesday — Mercury, Thursday — Jupiter, Friday — Venus, Saturday — Saturn, Sunday — Sun. These names were adopted by the Romans, and then many people of Western Europe used them.

Another version of the origin of the names of the days of the week is associated with the names of the gods of German — Scandinavian mythology. The gods, worshipped by the Saxon ancestors of the British were quite numerous, but those from whom the days of the week were named were the main objects of their worship.

Sunday was named after the name of the Sun God. As a sign of special reverence for this deity, the ancient Saxons dedicated to him the first day of the week, which they called "San'zdeg". Monday was named after the goddess of the Moon, who was the main deity of the Saxons. God Tuesco worshipped as father. From the Saxons he was devoted to the third day of the week, called "Tusko'zdeg". The

modern name in English is Tuesday. Wednesday was named in honor of the deity Woudena. The God Wouden (also Wotan or Odin), was the supreme deity among the Northern Nations. In honor of him was called the fourth day of the week — “Wooden'zdeg”. Thursday was dedicated to the God Thor. Thor is the eldest son of Odin and Friga. He devoted the fifth day of the week — “Tor'zdeg”. The goddess Friga, or Freya, wife of Odin, was worshipped by Saxon, Danish, and other pagans. She was also called Hertha and was considered the goddess of the Earth. It was dedicated to the sixth day of the week, called by the Saxons "Friga'zdeg". The modern name is Friday. It was named after the God Siter. The name of this day came from the Saxons “Siter'zdeg”.

The names of the months in English are derived from the names of the Greek and Roman Gods. For example, January is named after Janus — the Roman God of gates and protector of people from uninvited guests. March is named after the war God Mars. April got its name from the Greek goddess of love and beauty Aphrodite. May — the name of the month derived from the name of the God Maya — the goddess of fertility. June is named after the Goddess Juna, but in Russian her name sounds like "Hera". She acted as the patroness of all widows and marriages.

Some of the month names in English were borrowed from Latin. For example, the word September came from the Latin word "septem" — seven, October - from the Latin word "octo" — eight, November was formed from the Latin word "novem" — nine, December-from the Latin word "decem" — ten.

The etymology of the origin of certain English months is associated with the names of great people or with the names of ancient holidays. So, let us consider the month July. The month is named after Gaius Julius Caesar. August is named in honor of Augustus Octavian, thanks to his efforts the formation of the Gregorian calendar was completed. The month of February was named after the feast of "Febra", which translates from Latin as "purification".

During this work, we got acquainted with the history of the calendar, namely the origin of the names of the months and days of the week in English.

This work can be useful for developing the correct pronunciation and spelling of English words. The facts presented in this work contribute to the expansion of the cognitive sphere of man.

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ISSUES AND APPROACHES IN BUSINESS ENGLISH

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Business English, a term used in many publishers catalogues for a subset of ESP books, caters for a multitude of users and activities, among whom there can often be very little similarity. Business English courses and materials can serve both the Occupational user of English (for example the manager of a company, an accountant, a secretary) and a student (for example a student of business, banking, economics, for management). The term business English implies the existence of a discrete form of the language.

Business English is often treated as an ergolect (or work language), which suggests that an ergolect operates on the level of lexis and at the level of transaction, hardly at all at the level of grammar. What is distinctive about business English,

compared with other ergolects, is that it is a mediating language between the technicalities of particular business, and the language of the general public. It is not purely for intra-group communication. This is not surprising since business and commerce are by definition an interface between the general public and the specialist producer. Business transactions are likely to be similar whatever the nature of the particular business; the particular business, however, will affect content and lexis.

Business languages has been insufficiently studied, compared for example with the languages of EST. It is generally presented in the form of overviews. Some studies look at particular text types or aspects, for example telexes and oral interaction. An important finding, made by Williams in particular, is that the languages taught in textbooks is different from that used in real life. Williams concludes that more real data is needed about what language is used in different situations before we as teachers and coursebook writers can begin to select what to teach for different situations.

However, as well as attempting to discover the authentic linguistic realisation of discourse functions, we also need to know what strategies speakers use when conducting complete transactions. Micheau and Billmyer make a start on this, concluding that where language content was once the focus of our curriculum, interactional skills have now become a topic of discussion in their own right. Three points must be made here. First, native speakers of English who are new to the work of business may have just as much need of lessons in discourse skills and strategies as non-native users of the language. Hence we might expect, and indeed can find, business English textbooks, which aim to cater for both native and non-native English speakers. Second, as an international language, English is used as the means of communication in business transactions between people none of whom is a native user of the language. Thus, any study of authentic business English languages must include data on the forms and strategies employed by practicing business people who are non-native speakers of English. Third, more consideration needs to be given than at present to cultural aspects of business communication. Currently, too much

attention is focused on the business practices of Western Europe and the USA, any cross-cultural adjustment being made in the direction of the West.

There are a very large number of business English textbooks available on the market; only a few can be considered here. A striking feature is a large number of general books, which seem to differ very little from course books for EGP – working through a standard set of structures, teaching much common core as well as some work-related vocabulary, and dealing equally with all the skills. There are several reasons for this. First, the role of business English as a mediating language (see the discussion above) implies that it must bear much similarity with everyday language. Second, the wide range of people who might identify themselves as students of business English may suggest a market for general course books (and also for some more specialised books. Third, we may note that in the private sector, particularly, language schools offer `open door` business English courses. As the student are not likely to be homogeneous in terms of work experience, a general textbook applicable to a range of business situations may be most appropriate one to use.

These general business English course books thus often have very general aims. Jones and Alexander is a flexible learned-centred course in communication skills for people who need English in their day-to-day work. Many of the course books aim to provide students with the practical language skills needed to communicate effectively in a wide range of business situations. The target audience, too, is very broadly defined, often with both practicing business people and student of business (or commerce or management) being catered for by the same materials. Brieger is aimed at the specialist or non-specialist student or business English. Some are designed for adults who need English for professional as well as social purposes and or adult students of business English.

These books clearly meet a need. They appear to fulfill what are surely common expectations of a language textbook/course book: namely, that it should be

reasonably complete in its coverage of language forms and functions, usable as a reference source, and fairly lively and interesting.

More narrowly targeted business English textbooks may be designed for a specific type of student. Knowles and Bailey, for example, is a carefully designed low-level course in listening comprehension and conversation skills for Japanese business people.

We might expect something different from general English for reading and writing, since many of the written text types in business English are specific to the business world, for example invoices, quotations, company reports, memos. Carrier and Spiro aim to develop reading skills using a variety of business text types. Cotton and Land, however, both use texts from business journalism and seem to activate language knowledge more than reading strategies.

Near all the books so far referred to seem basically designed for classroom and interactive use, although there is a tendency for publishers to claim that they can also be used for self-study. So far more investigation is needed into design of effective material.

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ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF CULTURE IN THE MODERN WORLD

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The state of modern culture is largely determined culture of post-industrial society. As a result of the scientific, technological, computer and technological revolutions, modern culture has undergone fundamental changes. She starts exist as if in three dimensions, breaking up into three main components - humanitarian, scientific, technical and mass.

The aim of the given paper is to highlight the problem of cultural interaction among the people in the world.

Mass culture first appeared in the United States, as not being too burdened by the historical and cultural past, this country turned out to be the most susceptible to the cultural possibilities of scientific and technological progress. A special cultural first appeared here industry producing and replicating mass culture for mass consumption. The characteristic features of mass culture are its accessibility, ease of perception, entertainment, simplicity, orientation to the undeveloped consciousness of people.

In modern industrial and post-industrial societies there is a shift in the center of cultural and spiritual influence on people from schools, universities, classical art and the church to fashion and television, becoming the defining core of culture and people's lives, performing the role that religion, reason, philosophy and science used to play. Almost all significant events of modern social and cultural life take the form of a vibrant television show [1].

If we accept that the basis of life in modern society is science, engineering and technology, then before our eyes there is an accelerated the formation of a common

world civilization. She really is unified and universal, since there is no national mathematics, chemistry, physics and science as a whole as a system of knowledge about the world. They are universal and in this regard, Japan is not much different from Europe, and Russia from USA. In most schools in the world, the same subjects are studied, in them necessarily taught foreign languages to facilitate communication between people. Space satellites and modern communications allow people to receive information from all regions of the world. A large the Internet plays a role in this, ensuring the inclusion of countries and peoples in unified communication system. A person has a sensation the world as a whole.

Emerging for the first time in the history of the cultural unity of mankind changes the mechanisms that determine the fate of individual cultures and civilizations. Nowadays, more than ever, it has become obvious that culture any people or countries not in contact with others cultures and not experiencing their influence, inevitably doomed to lagging behind the pace of world cultural development. Today not a single people and no country can no longer develop their culture in an independent way, outside the unified world culture of mankind. A new era has come, in which the forefront of world history enters multidimensional dialogue of cultures of different countries and peoples [2].

However, modern globalization processes do not occur in the world definitely smooth, no problem. Fact that global economic, political, legal, technological, integration processes simultaneously cause a change in life way of life, traditions and cultures of entire peoples and countries, forcing them to revising and even abandoning some ethnic and national values. This is especially evident in the narrowing of the sphere the functioning of the national language and the spread of English the language that today is used by about 1.5 billion people in the world. English has become the main language of modern science and technology all over the planet. It's no coincidence that 90 percent of the information stored on a worldwide computer network - in English. Meanwhile, the language of any nation is not only a means of communication, without her there is no nationality. Therefore national

consciousness native language is perceived as a living organism, requiring careful relationships and worries. So, in France in 1994 even special “Act on the use of the French language”, prohibiting the excessive use of foreign terms and expressions [3].

This taking into consideration all above mentioned information we may make up the following conclusion. In spite of the fact that the issue is being investigated consistently it's necessary to continue this activity in order to make the people of our planet communicate and cooperate on different problem more effectively.

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SIGHTSEEING ROUTE: DISNEYLAND IN EUROPE

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In one of the suburbs of Paris you can find fairytale kingdom of Sleeping Beauty and famous Mickey-Mouse, where they only law governs - each man, who stands on this land, irrespective of his age, sex or nationality, must be happy. Best of

all it is to come here with your family. Because this magic world was created not for children but for their parents as well - in this . Fairyland a grown-up can relive his childhood with his own children . This world-known palace is named " Euro Disneyland " .

The first Disneyland was founded in 1955 in California State. But the first and the only Disneyland in Europe appeared in the last ten years of the XX century , when the father-founder of "Tale Empire" died. Managers of Disney's company went reconnoitering to Europe. Great Britain was not for them because of its not advantageous geographical position. Spain was preparing for Olympic games. Choice was aimed on France. And in 1987 they decided to build Euro Disneyland in France.

Disneyland is the complex, which consists of two parks of sideshows and entertainments

- Disneyland Park and Walt Disney Studios Park-and Disney Village with restaurants, night clubs, discos, which work all the night, and seven hotels.

Main side-show of the Country of entertainments is - "Pirates of the Caribbean Seas": dark neglected castle, tropical bogs or swamps and savages, which are depicted with actors of Disneyland. In the restaurant "Blue Lagoon" they cook dishes of the ration of Caribbean aborigines. But a guest risks becoming the hero of the performed subject and fall into pirates' hands. You can come to the neglected town from the movie "Indiana Jones" and meet Indian Maya with their mystical idols and pyramids.

Main Street is the main street of Disneyland Park .You can go for a drive by car model of the last century along the streets of the town, where castles, cosmic switch-banks, water side-shows are situated. You can meet Mickey and Minney, Donald duck, Aladdin; you can have photos with them and take their autographs. You can make an excursion round the park on the railway in the ancient train; visit many different souvenir shops, cafes and restaurants. You can see beautiful "Electric parade", which takes place some times a day.

One of the interesting districts of the Park is Fantasyland. It is made for the youngest guests of Disneyland. The main adornment is the Castle of Sleeping Beauty. In contrast to American and Japan, you can see inside and go for a walk in its fairytale halls. In Fantasyland you can meet 27metre dragon, the monster with large sharp-clawed pad who puffys smoke and fire to the visitors. This dragon guards Snow-white and seven dwarfs. At Christmas Santa Clause joins them. In Fantasyland you can meet Pinocchio, Cinderella, Lancelot and Peter Pen. There is “American switchbacks” and new attraction “Peter Pen's Fly”. Those, who like Alice Wonderland, can go to the interesting labyrinth. You can visit the restaurant “Toad's hall”. If you want to find yourself a Cinderella on the ball, you must go to the cafe near the huge pumpkin-coach.

Adventureland. In this part of the town you come to Eastern market, which reminds the city, where famous Aladdin lived. You will see Robinson Crusoe’s house on the top of the tree ,mysterious caverns on the island of adventures .You will go by boat on the river of Underground town, where your boat will fight with Caribbean pirates and you will find yourself in the island, where pirate’ laws rule.

Discoveryland is the center of different modern side-shows, computer games and videofilms. In Discoveryland you can go for Interesting travelling by Time Machine, fly to stars, see submarine world from “Nautilus”. You get great pleasure at circus show and in the cinema “Cine-Magique”. Certainly you'll experience unforgettable sensation on “death loop” of the side-show “Cosmic Mountain”.

Frontierland. In this part of the town you find yourself in the times of America's developing by first settlers. Here Castle with kind ghosts and the fortified fortress where heroes of Wild West live wait for you. On the little cattle-farm real cows graze. You can see real Indian life in the village of Pocahontas, make trip by canoe and ancient steamships “Mark Twain” and “Molly Brown”.

During the first years after opening Euro Disneyland was visited by more than one hundred million people every year. They said, that American culture was completely penetrated in Europe; but instead of triumph unexpected scandal broke

out. All newspapers and magazines told about bankruptcy of Disneyland, staff reduction and its debts. Dead loss of Euro Disney Company in the first quarter of the last year made up 76.8 million euro.

Expenses on opening of new park of Walt Disney Studios provoked deterioration of financial results of Euro Disney .They were opened on February 2002. Here you can find yourself on another side of the screen. It is difficult to know whom of famous actors you can see when you go for a walk along Tinsel Town. This place reminds Sun Set Beach in Los Angeles - the place of rest and shopping with expensive shops and modern restaurants.

In spite of all difficulties Disneyland as for its visiting takes the same place as Eiffel Tower and Louvre. It seems, that the Land of animated tales attracts people's attention not less than famous museums do.

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TO THE PROBLEM OF GLOBAL HEALTH ISSUE

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In accordance with the latest ideas, human health is a synthetic category that includes, in addition to the physiological, moral, intellectual and mental components. Hence, not only the person who has a chronic disease or physical defects, but also one who is distinguished by moral pathology, weakened intellect, and an unstable psyche, is more or less sick. The health problem of mankind is quite “old”.

The reproach for civilization is the preservation of high child mortality on the planet. Specialists from the World Health Organization (WHO) believe that if it does not decrease, then over 100 million children will die from diseases and malnutrition during the last decade of the 20th century in underdeveloped countries. In this case, most often we are talking about ordinary diseases: pneumonia, tetanus, measles, whooping cough, etc. The time has come when the level of civilization of any country should be determined not only by the development of the latest sectors of the economy, but by the life expectancy of the population.

The object of the research is actual health problems.

The subject of the study is public health.

Purpose of work: to study the current problems of public health in modern conditions.

The global problem of health and longevity is largely a derivative of other global problems that cause diseases, contribute to their spread, reduce the person's working and reproductive age and his life expectancy. These include:

- environmental degradation, depletion of resources and deterioration of their quality;
- population explosion and overpopulation in a number of developing countries;
- lack of food and its poor quality, hunger and malnutrition;
- urbanization and rising levels of stress factors.

It is obvious that the concept of a healthy lifestyle is not within the scope of interests of either tobacco companies or corporations that provide their customers with fatty, cheap and junk food (such as McDonald's). But least of all, it is beneficial to firms manufacturing pharmaceutical products. On the contrary, medicine has become one of the most profitable businesses. The pharmaceutical industry offers

“health” to millions of patients, but often does not provide the promised product. Instead, it delivers medications that only alleviate symptoms, while at the same time supporting the cause of the illness as a condition for further business development. This industry spends twice as much money to cover fraud as researching drugs for future therapies. This organized deception is the reason why such an investment business can continue to exist behind the strategically developed smoke screen of the “benefactors” of mankind.

It should also be noted that the person himself often prefers a satisfying life full of various pleasures, not really thinking about the consequences. But it cannot be argued that such an approach to life is a consequence of a low intellectual level. The nature of man is to constantly strive for new, ever greater pleasures.

As you know, a disease is nothing more than a consequence of more general and deeper processes. The following are some of the reasons for the deterioration of public health and possible solutions to this problem.

1. Lack of effective medicine. The solution to this problem, as noted, is hidden primarily by the pharmaceutical companies themselves, because they are not interested in presence of an inexpensive drug on the market that can cure the disease in a relatively short time with minimal consequence.

2. Lack of financial resources from the state. The availability of money makes it possible to develop programs for the prevention of diseases, improve working conditions, create the opportunity for good rest and restoration of health, as well as implement other social projects aimed at preventing diseases among all segments of the population.

Thus, the whole history of mankind clearly shows us that neither the development of science, nor the economic well-being of the state can lead us to the desired result. The world is undergoing an anthropological catastrophe. This catastrophe affects all dimensions of human life, in fact, identifies the rapidly

developing “world pathology”, the disharmony of the interaction of the world economy and the biosphere.

The current trends in assessing the current state of human health indicate continuing adversity in the formation of health, which can lead to a deterioration in the quality of the population, the restriction of its participation in creative activities to improve the socio-economic situation in the country.

Summing up the information we may conclude:

Human health synthesizes physical, spiritual and social health, in which the preservation of a balanced relationship with the environment, harmonized interaction of man with nature, is manifested. The most priority area is to increase the level of the psychophysical state of health, maintain optimal working capacity, professionalism of workers, the quality of life of the population and the achievement by the individual of a genetically determined life expectancy, which ultimately ensures the need for a healthier lifestyle.

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ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES IN MODERN WORLD

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Have you ever wondered about what world we and our children will live in? We would like to believe that it will be better, because all technologies are adapted to the needs of people. But there is a serious problem, which has not been solved yet.

This is an environmental problem. For thousands of years, people had been drinking clean water and had been breathing clean air. But then the scientific and technical revolution came. The ecology began to deteriorate rapidly, and this process does not stop, but becomes more and more intensive. Nowadays in big cities people even wear gauze bandages. And what will happen next?

As far as air pollution is concerned, this is not only the gas pollution in large cities. If it were only for dirty air in large cities, it would be half a problem. But because of the intensive growth of industry, the air is being spoilt everywhere. And there are fewer and fewer places where it is clean. The greenhouse effect is directly related to this problem. The content of carbon dioxide in the Earth's atmosphere increases, thermal radiation does not go into space, as it has always been. This raises the temperature on the planet. And who knows what humanity is threatened by melting glaciers!

Speaking about water pollution one should remember that in many ancient cultures people didn't live in places where the water was dirty. Today, to find clean water, you have to go far out of the town or go to the nearest supermarket to buy drinking water.

Drinking water is vital for human health. Almost all of its sources are exposed to anthropogenic and technological impact of different intensities. The problem of drinking water quality affects many aspects of the life of human society throughout the history of its existence. According to the World Health Organization, over 1 billion people in the world are not able to use clean drinking water and about 2.4 billion – normal household sanitary conditions. According to the World Health

Organization, this is the cause of death of 2.2 million people in the world every year, among them many children.

What is the way out? After all, it is impossible to return people into the middle ages. The only way that we see is to solve this problem not only at the state level in programs to improve the environment and combat the pollution, but also for each of us to start with ourselves. To stop littering, gradually move to biomaterials, become more respectful about nature and only in this way, being united, humanity will keep the earth clean. The biggest problem in the world is ecology. The invention of machines, household appliances, care products, military equipment: all this makes life easier for us, but destroys our environment.

The ecology of the planet is a matter for everyone. There is no person on the Earth who would not suffer from environmental pollution, even if many people do not feel it and do not realize it. Man is an amazing creature, the only one who, without hesitation, pollutes his own home. We can say, he cuts off the branch on which he sits.

From year to year, humanity makes their life more comfortable, surrounding themselves with useful things, creating technologies, mechanisms, new substances, etc. and this is certainly well, because progress and development are important components of our lives. But this medal has a reverse side, and it lies in the systematic destruction of plants, animals, air pollution, water and soil. Factories and cars emit countless gases into the atmosphere, destroying the ozone layer that protects us from solar radiation. They make the air unfit for breathing, and in addition to this, they dump sewage into rivers and seas. In biology, the human species is called "homo sapiens", but if you look at what they do to the environment, you'll have doubts about this name. No other creature on the planet is able to pollute the Earth the way we do it.

The only one thing pleases that there still are people who unite themselves in public organizations and stand in defense of our common home. However, if you

look at the news, it becomes clear that their efforts are obviously not enough. Forests still continue to be cut down, the seas are being polluted, and there is becoming less and less clean air, without talking about species extinction. Is a new model of phone or car worth irretrievably lost forests or thousands of people with cancer due to contaminated water, air and radiation? We are sure, it is not.

The only hope here remains that more and more environmentally friendly materials, fertilizers and substances are being developed now. But in our country, unfortunately, it is still in its infancy.

The degradation of the natural environment depends both on the number and concentration of the population and on the volume of production and consumption. In modern society, all these factors have acted in such a way that the human environment is highly polluted. People over the last century have allowed too much increase in the production and spread of waste, by - products and chemicals. Pollution is very harmful to life on our planet, of humanity itself. We pollute the air and water, live in such a noise and dust that none of the animals on the planet will endure.

The search for the causes of degradation of the natural environment and the solution of environmental problems that have arisen, although not recently, began quite late in the history of human society. However, as life shows, the study of ecological balance reduces the possibility of its restoration while the investment of capital brings great profits. These problems did not emerge as economic ones until they threatened the very mode of organization of the production process, an organization that is based on and cannot be carried out without the increasing exploitation of the two sources of wealth: the land and the worker.

So, ecological problems have no borders and in order to avoid environment disasters people should broaden ecological education, understand that the beauty of nature is extremely fragile. People must obey the unwritten laws of nature, live in harmony and respect with it, protect and take care to provide future on our planet.

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF GLOBALIZATION

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Globalization is understood as economic, political, social and cultural relationship among the entire human community, is the predominant orientation of the present stage of world development. However, contradictions and negative effects of globalization related to its irregularity and potential conflicts, posed by political scientists, creates doubt about whether there is a perspective in involving newly formed sovereign into this .

The importance of the issue boils down to the fact that in modern world two contradictory processes contrast each other: the process of globalization of the modern world and seeking to preserve national identity and cultural originality of every civilized country. Culture has long been a privilege of those who, because of their knowledge, education, property and social statute, could have access to works of progressive thought, literature and art.

The term globalization is used too often and can have various meanings. In our study we will assume that this term refers to globalization of financial markets and the growing dominant influence on the national economy global financial markets and transnational corporations. In this sense, globalization should be distinguished from free trade, which does not have such far-reaching consequences for individual countries.

Globalization has brought enormous benefits.

1. Globalization has opened new opportunities for innovation and entrepreneurship of global economic growth. But globalization has also negative aspects. First, it is prone to crises; second, it enhances the inequality between the rich and poor within countries and between them; third, it causes misallocation of resources between private and public interests.

2. Globalization promotes cooperation between states in solving supranational problems. Whether the states want or not they are involved in their decision. A huge number of problems arising among nations and organizations can be solved only on the global level. These are such problems as climate change, the ozone hole, the occurrence of deserts, carbon emissions, environment, crime, epidemics, poverty, terrorism has also become global in the context of globalization.

3. Globalization plays its role when a growing number of non-state actors in economy and politics take a number of functions previously performed by States.

4. Globalization in itself does not at all streamline the system of international relations. On the contrary, it leads to the spread of principles that, in general, border on anarchy from the realization that national states are losing their ability to govern due to the activation of cross-border processes. Encourages governments to create a trans-state world order.

5. And the last thesis: the efforts of states to create a global governance system are intensifying. There are four possibilities, even theoretical ones, of creating such a world government.

And finally, the optimal, of course, system is the concept of global, corporate governance, which is most popular among theorists of globalization.

In conclusion it is possible to state that the final choice of a global governance model will occur very soon. The gap between the requirements for managing the global economy and politics and the extremely sluggish efforts of states to create a coherent system of global governance is only growing. This means that rumors of the death of nation-states, even in the European Union, where they donate a significant part of their sovereignty to Brussels, are greatly exaggerated.

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THAILAND

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CAPITAL: Bangkok (Krung Thep)

FLAG: The national flag, adopted in 1917, consists of five horizontal stripes. The outermost are red (symbolizing the Thai people); those adjacent are white (symbolizing Buddhism); the blue center stripe (representing the monarchy) is twice as high as each of the other four.

Today travellers often choose Thailand for holidays. What is so special about this country, why does it attract tourists so much? Cultured, historic, warm and cheerful Thailand attracts tourists with its sparkling temples, tropical shores, grand cuisine, and the endless Thai smile.

The abundant cuisine of Thailand

Worshipped around the world, Thai cuisine emphasis on lightly prepared dishes with strong aromatic and spicy components. Thai dishes are prepared from fresh seafood, rice, raw or cooked vegetables, and local spices – lemongrass, chilli peppers. This believe that all four basic tastes: sweet, salty, spicy, and sour must be in the food.

Thailand nature

Thailand has a tropical climate. For much of the country there are three distinct seasons: the hot season, from March through May; the rainy or wet monsoon, June to October; and the cool season, November through February. While continental

Thailand receives most of its precipitation from June through October, rain occurs at all seasons in peninsular Thailand, the largest amount along the west coast from May to October, and along the east coast from October to January

Thailand has a tropical monsoon climate with plenty of suns, high rainfall and high humidity. This climate leads to the fact that Thailand is rich in a huge variety of flora and fauna. There are lots of forests, mountains, rivers, valleys and gorges in Thailand that are great places to visit. Thailand is famous for its beautiful white sand beaches and clear blue seas.

EDUCATION

Schooling is compulsory for nine years, including six years of primary school and three years of lower secondary school. Three-year upper secondary schools offer general or vocational studies. Both teacher training and technical and vocational training (especially in agriculture) have been stressed in recent development plans. The academic year runs from June to March.

Sacred Places of Thailand

Thailand is a country with a great religious aspect, full of Buddhist temples, shrines, traditional healers and other spiritual masters. Visitors can see various statues and icons of Buddha. Stunning temples and golden Buddhas are everywhere. Fortune-bringing shrines decorate homes as well as modern malls. Tourists can join the meditation retreats and religious festivals.

Major sports include football (soccer) and basketball. Thai bull, cock, and fish fighting are also popular (though illegal), along with Thai boxing, golf, badminton, and kite fighting. All visitors must have a passport, visa, and proof of sufficient funds for the stay. Precautions are recommended against typhoid, hepatitis, and malaria.

Thailand. Beach resorts and relaxation

Thailand is an incredibly popular destination for tourists. This paradise offers plenty of hotels, resorts, restaurants, and other useful facilities. You'll never be bored in Thailand. If you get tired of strolling along beaches and markets, there are many attractions. Enjoy expensive bars, live theatre, theme parks with white tigers, elephants, and bright exhibits

In Thailand, there are a huge number of amazing places, a trip to which you will surely remember for a long time, and today we will tell you about the 5 most interesting destinations.

The Island Of Phuket

In Phuket, you can find a suitable area for any category of travelers-whether it's families with children who need good sand and shallow sea, or nature lovers who are interested in beautiful scenery. The nature here is really amazing and incredibly beautiful-mountains, forests and parks, lakes and waterfalls, bays and lagoons, as well as many viewing platforms from which you can see the island in all its glory and take stunning photos.

Phangan

Phangan is good for a unique combination of untouched and well-developed infrastructure. There is everything you need for a holiday-hotels, cafes, beach cafes overlooking the sunset, all kinds of zoos and water parks, shops, including large. But there is no large amount of entertainment

And this is one of the reasons why Phangan is much less popular among tourists from Russia. The second reason is that it is quite difficult and long to get here. There is no airport here so you either have to fly to Koh Samui, or take a bus / train and — in any case-then go on a ferry or a fast catamaran.

If Phuket and Phangan are rich in more "classic" natural beauty, the Krabi region is a unique place in Thailand, with nature unlike other regions. The visiting card of Krabi is karst rocks that look just cosmic, and this applies to both the sea and the coast.

Bangkong

Not only beaches and the sea is famous for Thailand-if your way to the Islands lies through the capital, it makes sense to stay here for a couple of days. It is here that there are many attractions interesting from the point of view of history and culture. There are hundreds of temples alone. However, the greatest interest for tourists are only the most important of them-the Royal Palace, the temple of the Reclining

Buddha, the Temple of the dawn and the Temple of the Golden Mountain with an excellent observation deck.

For a family holiday in the Thai capital, there are also many places-Siam Ocean World aquarium, butterfly garden, Dusit Zoo, Dream World entertainment center, Siam Park and others.

Of course, Bangkok attracts fans of entertainment "for adults" — all kinds of drag shows, go-go dances And Bangkok is a Paradise for shoppers. If you want to buy some things, clothes or electronics, it is hardly necessary to do it at the resort-at dozens of capital markets and shopping centers

Thailand is the place where tourists can relax and enjoy the beautiful nature.

THE WORLD THROUGH THE EYES OF YOUTH

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The role of youth cultures in modern society.

The aim of the article is to show the variety of youth cultures.

The term “culture” can be defined as language, dress, beliefs, manners and tastes in food or music of a particular group.

The concept of youth culture appeared in America in the 1950s and spread to Britain in the 1960s. It was a result of improvement in Western economics, which meant that teenagers had money to spend.

That is to say youth culture is as smaller culture that exists within a large one. For instance, youth subcultures, centering around such musical preferences as rap, heavy-metal or hip-hop, may spot somewhat particular styles of dress, language, and behavior, while accepting other aspects of the dominant culture.

There was the development of music and fashion industries with the orientation to the youth market. New group of young people dressed in Italian-style and leather clothes appeared. They were called Mods. However, there were young people who were against the materialistic wealth and stressed on spiritual values. They tried to show their protest in wearing unusual clothes, hair dress or in other ways. Thus in the 1960s and 1970s Hippies appeared, the brightest example of youth culture.

“Tune In, Turn On and Drop Out” was the motto of the hippie movement that grew partially out of young America’s disillusionment with the Vietnam War. Hippies were mainly white teenagers and young adults who shared distrust towards traditional values and authority. To express their protests and to “turn on” others, the hippies used art, street theatre and particularly music. This culture reached its peak in the summer of 1967, when a concert in San Francisco’s Golden Gate Park introduced the music of the hippies to a wider audience. The concert inspired thousands of young people around the country to head to San Francisco, including film, posters and album covers. In the 60s hippies sought to free themselves from societal restrictions, choose their own way and find new meaning in life. This made hippies instantly recognizable to one another and served as a visual symbol of their willingness to question authority. Also they often chose brightly coloured clothing. Moreover Hippie culture spread worldwide through a fusion of rock music, folk and blues, it also found expression in literature, fashion and the visual arts.

In the mid-1970s punk rock appeared. To the contrary to hippies they were full of hate. There was a great unemployment (especially among young people) at that time. Many young people blamed the society and in punk movement they expressed their negative feelings. Punks often had brightly coloured hair and wore clothes that could shock people.

As a large number of young people watch music videos, these influence greatly their minds. They wear the same clothes, sing violent lyrics and feel very cool.

Moreover rap and hip-hop were born in the ghettos of New York over 40 years ago. Rap fashion is big business today. There is also a rap language or rather slang, used by many teens. Unfortunately rap songs make young people believe that money is the most important thing in the world. Moreover Graffiti style was influenced by the hip-hop culture. And it became a life for some young people. I would say that this type of art is gorgeous and attractive as it can express people's attitude, opinion to the society.

I can't help saying about youth nowadays. Today co-called "bloggers" or YouTubers are very popular with teenagers and young people. They try to imitate their favourites. On one hand it is rather fascinating and funny, but on the other hand young people think that YouTube channel is a great way of earning money. So, they think that high education is needless nowadays as say can make a living as blogger or YouTuber. No wonder values of youth also have changed. All they need just money and fame. Probably not everybody has become materialist but majority of them.

As for modern music I must say it has become more violent and senseless however young people are crazy about it.

Surely social networks influence their minds greatly. They became dependent on them. Young people spend lots of time surfing the Net instead of meeting their friends or reading a book.

All in all different youth cultures which appear and change each other helps to make some conclusions. Here they are.

- Youth cultures are formed in reaction to society's values.
- Youth cultures help young people become independent of their families.
- These cultures give young people the opportunity to be something different before they agree and accept society's values.
- Youth cultures enable young people to express themselves by choosing the style that suits them.

- The values of a youth culture do not matter – just have to be different from those of the older generation.

Are they good or bad? No one can answer. But it's quite clear that youth cultures can bring change to society and help young people in their search for identity.

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CYBER SPORT AS A NEW FLOW OF YOUNG PEOPLE ACTIVITY

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Today we will talk about such a thing as eSports. As we know computer or electronic sport is a team or individual competition based on video games. All eSports disciplines are divided into several main classes, distinguished by the properties of spaces, models, game task and developed gaming skills of eSports players: first-person shooters, real-time strategy, various kinds of simulators, team role-playing games with elements of strategy and much more.

The history of eSports began with the game "Doom 2", which had a network game mode through a local network. Due to the popularity of the game "Quake", in 1997 in the United States there was the first League of eSports players. The history of eSports begins in 1997, when the "C. P. L." was founded, which made the first tournament in the discipline of "Quake". But the first game with the possibility of cooperative combat was "Doom 2".

Prize funds can reach several million US dollars. Tournament "Dota 2" "" the International "" several times broke records for payments: so in 2016 was played 20 million dollars, in 2017-24, in 2018-25.53, and in 2019-34.

Competition for the popularity of the game "Dota 2" can make the game "League of Legends", as it is two games of the same genre, and the number of fans "League of Legends" is not inferior to "Dota 2". After all, its creators invest a lot of effort and money to attract new fans to their project

Although "Dota 2" and "League of Legends" are competing projects, but not everyone can know that these two grandiose projects came from the legendary game "Warcraft 3 The Frozen Throne" from the company "Blizzard". Studios creators compete as well as their projects

Just a lot of attention gathers around a series of games "Counter Strike", perhaps the most popular first-person shooter at the moment.

There are also negative moments in the form of microtransactions, namely game items that sometimes cost a lot of money such as "AWP-Dragon Lore" from "Counter Strike Global Offensive", which costs about 123 thousand rubles or "Unusual Golden Baby Roshan" from "Dota 2" that costs about 120 thousand rubles. And it's sad because such a system is now present in almost every online (and not only) game.

Tournament games are broadcast live on the Internet, gathering a multi-million audience, eSports players are always in the spotlight of young people and girls (girls are not people) interested in this discipline.

Just a lot of people dream to reach the level of the game of their idols, and also to visit their place in the role of the same eSports player. But not everyone knows that this requires a lot of effort. Where can find so much time where does an ordinary person, or a student?

Also, eSports players give a good incentive to their fans who imitate them, and want to be like them, which makes eSports players good guys. lead bad people can't someone on good deeds

ESports in some moments exerts a positive influence on a person, namely :

- First, computer games in General, and eSports in particular, improve spatial thinking. And " better than University courses in chess and geological modeling.

- Secondly, the game develops visual memory.

- Thirdly, the age-related decline of mental abilities slows down.

- Fourth, there is discipline and self-control. Without this at major competitions – in any way.

- Fifth, playing, a person feels effective, self-esteem increases. And this is reflected in other areas of life.

An interesting observation of researchers: video games help to assimilate natural science knowledge and cope with complex mathematical problems. And players outperform their non-playing counterparts in the professional sphere. Is that why computer games in some countries are used for training surgeons, pilots, soldiers

Ask, but what about the known "computer" problems: vision loss, impaired posture, weight gain. They, experts say, are solved by elementary "occupational hygiene" under the guidance of an experienced coach. By the way, those who are engaged in eSports professionally, spend half the time at the computer than just gamers.

Each online tournament brings together not only players, but also those who are generally interested in eSports itself. There are no prerequisites to the fact that this sport will suddenly become uninteresting. However, there is one serious factor that does not allow to evaluate virtual sports by analogy with the real one. The same

football is loved because of its accessibility and simplicity. You just have to take the ball, and you can play anywhere. But eSports will require a computer, and even powerful, will need investment for the right to play. But the participants themselves, although not 100% sure of the future mass character of their sport, are trying to implement it.

There is reason to think... Our children live in cyberepohu. So maybe it will be more rational not to protect them from "harmful" computers, but to teach them how to interact with them? And to achieve success in life thanks to modern technologies. Including-why not? - and in a young but promising sport – eSports.

GLOBALISATION PROCESSES IN THE MODERN WORLD

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There were at least three shifts in international economic and political relations during the last century. After the Versailles-Washington system, a bipolar system of Euro-Atlantic and Soviet regimes appeared and brought new rules in international relations. Nowadays the world system covers about 200 political entities, including 186 states, which are engaged in and but not to be at war. That is why world expects now speak about globalisation processes. Six of every ten people in the world consider these processes to be positive. One-tenth of the world`s population has the opposite point of view. So, there is no common agreement in defining globalisation`s impact on the world economy. Highly developed countries receive many benefits from globalisation, but there is a view that developing countries become poorer and do not receive much from the integration processes. Despite this fact, the most favourable positions on globalization are found in Holland (87% of its population),

and then in Venezuela (82%) and India (79%), which belong to the group of developing countries. Citizens of some highly developed countries consider globalisation to bring much harm for `poor` countries. In contrast, the inhabitants of some developing countries expect many benefits for their economies in the future. From a long-term perspective, those processes may lead to the creation of a common economic zone for the whole world.

The magazine *Foreign Policy* in association with the advisory firm A.T. Kearney developed a list of countries ranged by their globalization level. Among the 62 countries represented there, the highest globalisation level is reached in Ireland, Switzerland and Singapore. Russia takes 39th place. In comparison, Japan holds only 38th place. To create this scale, a set of thirteen indexes was developed. It includes data about the level of economic integration, data about foreign trips and tourism, the level of technical integration, the level of political integration.

About one-fifth of the GNP of highly-developed countries and one-third of the GNP of developing countries are derived from export. Up to the end of 2001, 40-45% of the world population was engaged in material production and about 10-12% of people were employed in producing services. These statistics pertain to people who worked in the sphere of international trade. Thus, international relational relations remain a primary means of world income redistribution. The greatest share in international trade belongs to trans-national corporations. This kind of vigorous activity creates opportunities to do business all over the world, far from the country of origin. The main goal of the activity of these corporations is to achieve the highest profits, but this also means creating jobs, developing new ideas and accelerating scientific and technological progress. As with everything, such actions bring disadvantages as well: most of the commodities produced by these corporations are consumed in highly developed countries, despite the fact that the main part of manufacturing is concentrated in developing countries.

Economic and political globalisation has been accompanied by an increase of gap in the standard of living in many countries. Speaking about the integration level of the labour market, it is necessary to point out that it is far short the level of, for instance, financial globalization. In the estimation of the UN, the number of people who live outside their country of origin ranges from 50 to 80 million people. This is not large number, but during the next 50 years this situation may worsen. Nevertheless, today the shadow economy of the EU needs extra labour and illegal immigrants satisfy this demand. That is why, in the very near future, highly developed countries will have to project their domestic labour markets. A high immigration level will force them into setting quotas and restrictions on granting citizenship, in education etc.

The most complex and developed form of integration is financial globalization. This process has become possible due to the deepening of financial links between countries, liberalisation of prices, and investment flows. Nowadays, the volume of loans on the international financial market is 60% higher than the volume of international trade on goods and services and 130% higher than the world GNP. The global daily turnover on the currency markets is about \$0.9-1.1 trillion. But sometimes financial globalisation is viewed as speculation and diversion of capital from the manufacturing sector for the benefit of speculators. On the international level there have been many attempts to stabilize the world financial sector and to decrease the financial risks for all of its participants. Since the 1970s managers of international banks have been developing a global security network. In the IMF a new system of solving unforeseen situations on the financial markets is being developed too. Nevertheless, the rapidity of the globalisation process in the financial sector remains the main weak spot in the world economy.

Another aspect of globalisation is cooperation in tourism. The tourist sector makes up 10.9% of the world GDP. There our country not great development potential. Resorts on the coast of the Sea of Azov are popular only among the

population of the Donetsk and Lugansk republics due to the difficult situation in the country

Joining the trend to globalisation is useful for Donetsk People's Republic. It means that our republic will become a real member of the world system, enjoying equal rights and responsibilities. But to enter this system much must be improved in our national economy and policy. First of all, it is necessary to stabilise the national law system. This will help to develop all spheres of life in our country. Then it makes sense to raise the competitiveness of goods and services produced in Donetsk People's Republic, and tourist services in particular. This will take our country closer to getting the status of a highly developed country. Developing the tourist sector is very important, because a high level of foreign tourist arrivals creates a positive image of our country as reliable and brings additional revenues for the national budget.

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DONETSK IS THE INDUSTRIAL CENTER OF THE DPR

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Donetsk is a major supplier of various chemical products. These are mineral fertilizers, boric acid, ammonium sulfate, aqueous ammonia for economic purposes, acetic acid, washing pastes, paint and varnish products.

For more than 80 years, the products of Donetsk chemical plant, which produces inorganic chemical reagents and substances of high purity, have been highly quoted in the foreign and domestic market. The main nomenclature of the enterprise - more than 800 names.

The range of their application is very wide: medicine and pharmacy, electrical and radio engineering industry, glassmaking and mechanical engineering, as well as research and analytical practice. Especially pure substances are used in fiber optics, semiconductor technology, aircraft, nuclear power, rocket science, production of single crystals and artificial stones.

Donetsk state plant of chemical products was previously known for the production of industrial explosives, ammunition: artillery, engineering, aviation for various purposes, as well as elements of dynamic protection of armored vehicles. Its products were mostly destructive. But times are changing. From its shops began to enter the market completely "peaceful" products: strollers, toys made of plastics, linoleum on a fabric basis, foam, and even vacuum cleaners superior comfort. Donbass is quite able to feed itself, it can be self-sufficient and attractive for investment, the region has a high potential.

Donetsk today is a dynamically breaking metropolis, where high industrial and scientific potential, workers and highly qualified specialists are concentrated, where there is a developed infrastructure and production base.

The coal industry is located in seven districts of the city and is a production complex, in which 16 coal mining enterprises, 2 concentrators and briquette factories, which employ 38 thousand people, are concentrated.

Coal deposits of the city are characterized by quite complex mining and geological conditions of development: low power of coal seams, large depth of their occurrence, high gas content, the tendency of many layers to sudden emissions of coal dust and gas.

The largest share of fuel production falls on the mine. A. F. Zasyadko. In the city 9 of ferrous metallurgy enterprises specializing in the production of iron, steel,

sections and sheet metal (more than 280 sizes of sections), pipe billets from carbon, structural, alloyed high-grade steels.

Metal products meet the requirements of international standards and are the main export potential of the city, amounting to 50 percent.

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Donbass is quite able to feed itself, it can be self-sufficient and attractive for investment, the region has a high potential.

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ECOLOGY AND REVERSE LOGISTICS

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The environment is everything that surrounds and affects character and growth of living things. When talking about environmental problems, ecological issues cannot be separated from their effect on mankind, nor can human actions be separated from their effect on the ecology. Our daily life, industrial and business development on the one hand, and the state of the global environment on the other hand are interdependent, yet often this interdependence is often overlooked.

Today the planet holds more than 6 billion people. Global population has doubled in the last 40 years and is expected to double again by 2050, with 90% of that increase occurring in developing countries.

One of the most alarming of all human assaults on the environment is the contamination of air, earth, and water from dumping. Evidence of dumping can be found everywhere, done by individuals and large corporations alike. Hong Kong e.g. dumps more than 1,000 tons of plastic a day. Americans throw away 16 billion disposable diapers each year. Open sewage drains and festering landfills are common sites in many parts of the world.

Manufacturing industry, fuel burning, power stations emissions gas damage the environment. Since CO₂ is a greenhouse gas, this has significant influence on global warming. The influence of this factors we can see on graph called the Keeling Curve, that shows a steady increase of the amount of CO₂ in the atmosphere. The concentration of CO₂ rose from 313 parts per million by volume to 406 ppmv since 1958 until 2018 and this amount continues increasing.

On this graph you can see how the growth of the amount of CO₂ gas in the atmosphere leads to the increasing of average temperature from year to year. Global

climate change has already had observable effects on the environment. Effects that scientists had predicted in the past are occurring now. Scientists have high confidence that global temperatures will continue to rise largely due to greenhouse gases produced by human activities.

Let's see the effects of global warming: temperatures will continue to rise, more droughts and heat waves, hurricanes will become stronger and more intense, sea level will rise, arctic is likely to become ice-free.

As for our territory, we should consider environmental impacts of mining that can occur at local, regional, and global scales through direct and indirect mining practices. Impacts can result in erosion, sinkholes, loss of biodiversity, or the contamination of soil, groundwater, and surface water by the chemicals emitted from mining processes. These processes also have an impact on the atmosphere from the emission of carbon which effect on the quality of human health and biodiversity.

Having being studying logistics for more than two years we cannot but mention here a special area of logistics called Reverse logistics which is related to the reuse of products and raw materials and deals with harmful influence of human activity connected with manufacturing. Reverse Logistics it's a process of planning, implementing and controlling the efficient, cost effective flow of raw materials, in-process inventory, finished goods and related information from the point of consumption to the point of origin for the purpose of recapturing value or for proper disposal. It's a pity to say that nowadays in our republic there is no reverse logistics at all. But we can consider methods that companies in other countries use and see what practices we can implement.

We can:

1. Choose raw suppliers with requirement of maximum reduction of waste. In case if it's impossible, consider the elimination of losses from those wastes.
2. Transportation by optimal routs trying to deliver by with minimum time. It'll lead to reducing of mileage of transport and decreasing of emissions in atmosphere.

3. Consolidation of cargo consignment allows to use “ecological” transport like railway and air transport.

4. Returned items can be resold. In case of damage of items it can be refurbished, repackaged, reused for parts or recycled. Other product categories may be more appropriate for liquidation (think food or consumables) but many products can still be reused in a creative way. Companies even make toothbrushes out of recycled yogurt cups. By reducing waste in these ways, companies can make more money and help the environment at the same time.

If the product is defective, the customer should return the product. The manufacturing firm has to organize shipping of the defective product, testing, dismantling, repairing, recycling or disposing the product. The product will travel in reverse through the supply chain network in order to retain any use from the defective product. Reverse logistics has two main responsibilities: product returns and end-of-life product disposal. Of the two, product returns is clearly and legally the responsibility of the manufacturer. There are numerous initiatives, and laws in some states, to make product disposal also the responsibility of the manufacturer.

Thus, we will have to stop using many things if we want to end pollution. We can't do it immediately so scientists and engineers should find the ways to gradually reduce pollution from automobiles and factories. It's a responsibility of the government to make enterprises to take measures for reducing of pollution. Individuals and groups of people like students should cooperate to force enterprises to stop or at least to reduce the polluting activities.

In conclusion, we would like to say that today, reverse logistics and ecology are two interconnected things. The development of reverse logistics will contribute to increasing attention to environmental issues.

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THE ADVANTAGES OF APPLICATION OF ENNEAGRAM IN TOURISM BUSINESS

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Statement of the problem in general. The problem of the inability of travel agents to communicate with customers is quite acute. The fact is that the success of the tourism business and the successful sale of package tours depend a lot on the customer base, their attitude to the travel agency, the success of previous trips, and other factors. If once the client faced rude disrespectful attitude, or simply the travel agency could not satisfy his requirements sufficiently, he is unlikely to return to the agency again. A permanent customer base is also of great importance.

The aim of the study is to consider the enneagram as a new way of interaction between employees and customers in the tourism business and to reveal the possible ways and benefits of introducing the enneagram.

Presentation of the materials of the main study. The enneagram of the personality, or enneagram (from the Greek. Ennea - nine, gramma - figure), is an integral model of a person's deep motivation, aimed at his personal transformation and development. The model studies a personality, its structure, as well as adaptive strategies and defense mechanisms, mental and emotional habits and fixations. According to this model, each person has a well-defined personality structure, their

own automatic reactions and some “programmed” behavior, and therefore he refers to one of the personality types that is clearly dominant in him (enneatype) [1].

The enneagram is more common in the west, but almost no one knows about it in our country. Most people are interested in the enneagram in order to get to know themselves or people around them, however, for example, in the USA, the enneagram is actively used for professional purposes. When the scriptwriter describes the character, he uses the enneagram model to make his image look like a real person, with its own advantages and disadvantages. Therefore, very often we involuntarily identify ourselves with characters from films or series - they really can be like us.

In the tourism business, there is such a thing as consumer segmentation. Segmentation is based on a number of principles: geographical, the principle of tourist preferences, economic, age [2].

The segmentation according to the psychographic principle is also important. Psychography studies the way of life of people, i.e. the settled forms of their being in the world. These forms are expressed in activities, interests and opinions. Psychography draws a portrait of a person in the whole variety of his actions and interactions with other people. A lifestyle is better than occupation, the level of material wealth or belonging to a particular social class, helps to understand the changing values of a person and his purchasing behavior. However, this is not enough. A potential tourist, while choosing a tour, bases his choice on deep motivation, personal preferences, worldview and many other things, which a person who does not know the technique for determining the enneatype cannot understand. Having knowledge of the enneagram, the travel agency manager will be able to determine what kind of person is now in front of him and subsequently better understand how to work with a particular client by the way of conversation, general behavior and appearance.

The enneagram is a psychological tool. But it can be useful in other areas of life, including business. Many companies use it to increase employee productivity, team building, as well as staff recruitment. By inviting a potential employee for an

interview, the boss will no longer ask template questions; he just needs to talk to the person.

Firstly, it will reduce stress during the interview and create a more friendly atmosphere. Secondly, this method will help to more fully recognize a person and evaluate not only his ability to work, but also his communication skills, which are especially important for a manager in tourism, human behavior during stress and unforeseen situations, the best ways to encourage and motivate, and also the strengths and weaknesses of his personality.

Knowledge of the enneagram has a positive effect on relationships in the team. Knowing each other's enneatype, colleagues can be more loyal to some mistakes or weaknesses of others, while distributing the load and tasks in accordance with what each employee is better prone to. This approach will have a beneficial effect on relationships in the team, which will positively affect the quality of work in general.

Conclusions. In the modern world, a huge number of new ways of interacting in a team and in business are used. And the enneagram is currently gaining great popularity in our country. I present several recommendations on the implementation and use of the enneagram in the tourism business:

when applying for a job, make the enneatype test mandatory;

educate tourism workers in the basics of the enneagram;

massively inform tourism workers about the need and benefits of using the enneagram in daily work, as well as in interaction with colleagues;

it is imperative to send tourism workers to enneagram trainings in Russia, where they are held quite often.

Without innovations in tourism, the industry will not develop. Using an enneagram can significantly improve interaction with customers, and this will have a beneficial effect both on the local business and, subsequently, on the entire industry. This type of typing is actively used in other countries, which helps them to remain at

a high level and rise even higher. The key to success is to learn from someone else and improve it. If at least some of those people who somehow relate to the tourism industry try to create something new, which was not there before, this will not leave any chance for tourism in our country to remain at the same level for many years.

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HOW TO TRAVEL WITHOUT PRODUCING GARBAGE

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The issue of ecology is always relevant. Since the development of industrial cities, which create huge amounts of pollutants we have been polluting our surroundings. The problem has become real. Nowadays our planet is in serious danger.

We live in an era of enormous consumer appetites. We constantly buy and acquire unnecessary things. It becomes crystal-clear that “humanity has evolved into the modern disposable society, readily buying and discarding non-recyclable products and packaging that were designed to enhance consumer convenience and regular

purchases” [2]. But progress does not stand still. Many countries have learned how to deal with garbage by creating new recycling systems and using fines.

It is hard to follow zero waste principles when traveling. Numerous publications on the topic testify to “the ecological cost of our travel endeavours. Though, the wave of global tourism has transformed the economy of several nations, it has also led to globetrotters inadvertently contributing to climate change” [1].

Tourists produce 8% of greenhouse gases per year. This includes accommodation, food, souvenirs and transport. Planes make the biggest carbon footprint. Up to 90% of harmful emissions into the atmosphere are accounted for by transport. When traveling, use the aircraft only if necessary. Trains, local trains and buses will take you to the right place not as fast as the plane, but their use will significantly reduce the amount of harmful emissions.

To solve these problems, the paper shows that there are many tips to help us to become more attentive to the environment. Even if you do not plan to give up garbage completely or dramatically change your lifestyle, they will certainly come in handy – to abandon plastic bags in favour of a fabric bag, not to use plastic tubes and to avoid plastic utensils will never be superfluous.

Make a travel plan. If you imagine what you will do in the journey, it will help to reduce the potential amount of waste. The main goal is not to buy anything from the forgotten at the airport or in another store, so that you do not have to get rid of the packaging.

Give up one-time. Use all reusable, cloth bags, glass jars or metal food containers, handkerchiefs, towels, Cutlery for eating on the go or in transport, water bottles.

Stay in “green” hotels. These hotels care about the environment – save water and electricity, properly dispose of garbage, use alternative power sources, etc. as a rule, these hotels have certificates LEED, Green Hotel, Green Leaf and Green Key.

Try replacing liquid soap and shampoo with solid cosmetics. It is usually sold in eco-friendly packaging.

Thanks to the development of digital technologies, many companies have applications that will allow you to save paper while traveling. Try to use e-tickets wherever possible. And if not – you can collect paper tickets.

All these exotic shells, turtle shells, butterfly wings, etc., as a rule, are obtained illegally, and such a souvenir market leads to the disappearance of the rich flora and fauna of our planet. Carry from travel impressions, not a bunch of figures that will gather dust on the shelves. If you want to bring something home – let it be something useful. For example, fruit, delicious cheese or tea.

We all love nature and hope that our grandchildren will be able to travel to places that will be as clean as they were hundreds of years ago. The primary goal of the study is to say that garbage is a real problem in our daily lives and during travelling. We have to do our best to save our planet.

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THE ROLE OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN AESTHETIC EDUCATION

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The formation of the young state of the Donetsk People's Republic led to a redefinition of the ideas, goals, objectives of education and the establishment of ties with many people. The solution of the conflict situation in this territory attracted representatives of different countries of the world. This has increased the interest especially of young people in participating in the resolution of this problem and to learn foreign languages. It is a well-known fact that culture in a broad sense is a prerequisite that determines the characteristics of the individual. In the modern world, which is getting closer, the Donetsk People's Republic makes every effort to enter the world stage. Despite the political situation the cultural barrier remains an important issue in this approach. It should be noted that the main way to remove this barrier through the unification of civilizations and mutual understanding between peoples is cultural proficiency in foreign languages. All of the above helps to strengthen the trend of changing the linguistic approach and ideological orientation to foreign languages of cultural, communicative and individual approach to the use of foreign language scientific material. Lingua-cultural studies, as follows from the name, it is a subject that, on the one hand, includes learning the language, and, on the other hand, gives certain knowledge about the country of the studied language. The main objective of lingua-cultural studies is to provide communicative competence for cross-cultural communication.

The main task of the subject is to study those units of the language and extra-linguistic phenomena which most vividly reflect the national peculiarities of the foreign culture. That is, our main task is to obtain background knowledge necessary for successful cross-cultural communication. So, the lingua-cultural competence is not only studying the language (to form language, communicative, linguistic competence) and linguistic aspects practically, but also examining the language as cultural phenomena. To understand the difference of cultural-historical environment and national character of world language, also to understand the meaning of language units as a cultural component. Here belong:

- Historical and cultural background, which includes not only knowledge of history, but also knowledge of culture of the language community in the process of its historical development;
- Socio-cultural background – peculiarities of communication within the society, social behavior, social values, conversation formulae, non-verbal communication;
- Ethno-cultural background, which includes information about the way of life, traditions, holidays, etc;
- Semiotic background, which contains information on symbols, connotations, realia and other language units bearing specific national coloring.[2]

For example, let's consider aesthetic activity with literature. Studying the language, students learn a lot of new and interesting things about countries, cities and their history, about educational institutions, festivals, famous people, scientists, artists, if books of different levels of complexity are used for reading.

The main method of aesthetic education has always been and remains the text. The development of students' ability to read excellent literature is the task of a foreign language. By selecting texts, it is necessary to pay attention to such basic criteria that correspond to the main categories of aesthetic theory.

The ideas and categories important to youth concern: love, friendship, success in aesthetics educate the aesthetic taste, valuable orientations, ideals and criteria of man. The aesthetic life of a personality is for us a definite ideal. The life and career in the human personality is always changing, that's why the ideal of life can change. But there are certain categories by which our existence is manifold and harmonious. Learning a foreign language helps in education, the purpose of which is to educate the individual.

The study of a foreign language increases the overall language culture of expressing thoughts on mother and foreign language. And that has a good influence on the development of students' thinking and language skills in the study of foreign

languages. The study of a foreign language is connected with the work of the visual, auditory, speech and motor organs. It has a good influence on the development of memory, because the student words, phrases, idiomatic phrases, schemas of sentence formation of the humanities. People cannot get along without contact and without influence. Entertainment is not just an exchange of opinions and emotions, but also a call of the human to himself to his soul, thoughts, dreams and memories. The unrethiness becomes a need for the people. And the most meaningful and most expressive way of entertaining human beings are words and speech. The ability to speak and to hear, to conduct discussions is an important condition of mutual understanding.

At the beginning of the 21st century, cross-cultural communication is becoming more and more important. Man is formed by the culture in which it grows. Engaging in communication with other cultures, students expand their vision of the world, change the way of life, mentality, keeping cultural-specific, native to them features, develop tolerance, respect, desire a positive attitude to everything new.[1]

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IMPACT OF ASIAN CULTURE ON YOUNG PEOPLE THROUGH ANIME

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Anime in Japanese culture already counts about 100 years of history. The first anime was drawn in the beginning of the 20th century by an unknown artist, for what was on the anime itself. A short cartoon called "Katsuda Xiangxin" consisted of fifty frames drawn on a tape of celluloid. The boy depicted here paints hieroglyphs for "moving photographs", which are used at the time to refer to the word "cinema", then turns the viewer around, takes off his hat and bows down. In 1917, the first animated films began to appear in Japan, lasting from one to five minutes. One of the first Japanese cartoons is Dekoboko Shingatho (New Sketch Album) by Dekoten Shimokawa, Saru Kari Kassen (Battle of Crab and Monkey), and Momotaro (1918) by Seitaro Kitoyama. The first Japanese animated cartoons were mainly created by enthusiasts who were inspired by the works of their foreign colleagues, although most often the characters and the plot borrowed from old Japanese fairy tales.

Until the eighties of the twentieth century in Japan was the internal development of animation, in 1980, also known as the "Golden Age of Anime" anime began to spread around the world, as well as began to originate subculture Otaku. For the Japanese Otaku were true fans of Anime, for the whole world - they were fans of anime and manga. In the future, subculture otaku had a great impact on the creation and development of anime. In the nineties of the twentieth year, the style of anime has changed, it became more elegant. Also by the beginning of the nineties, producers began to pay more attention to the final product, for each series, the film began to allocate many times more funding compared to the eighties. In the nineties, the most common style of "kawaii" also began to increase interest in the anime fantasy genre.

By the mid-nineties, anime had gone through a financial crisis. In 1995, it was directed by Hideaki Anno of Gainax and continued to develop the fur genre of anime, with robots combining both mechanical details and biological matter, and with hints of the gospel's divine origins. The series combines ideas and motifs that are interesting for both anime fans and the wider audience. Being initially put in the children's timeslot, "The Gospel" was extremely unpopular, despite its original

affiliation to a very nice fur children. A few episodes later, the timeslot was changed, and in its new quality the Evangelion suddenly won the attention of the public. In a short time the series became incredibly famous in Japan, and soon among fans of anime around the world. The story of the boy running from reality was told in a confused, crumpled way, using a lot of art-house techniques, and it turned out to be so well received that ten years later the sales of accompanying goods - figures of heroes, collection items - are still quite large. The gospel became the second breath and rebirth for Japanese animation. From the date of release of the Gospel to the present day anime is one of the most popular cultural attractions of Japanese culture.

Anime in Russia

It is difficult to determine at what point anime has won the sympathy of the Russians or when the first otaku appeared in the expanses of the state, we can say only one thing relatively definitely - the history of anime in Russia is more than 40 years. And it dates back to the USSR, where the animation and cinema of capitalist countries were strictly selected according to ideological, economic and aesthetic criteria, and only a few films were released. This exception was also made for some Japanese animated films. Such as "Flying Ghost Ship", "Prince of the North", "Cat in Boots" and so on. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, the first anime to appear on the screens was "Sailor Moon: The Moon in a Sailor. What was the reason for the hostility? Perhaps the main reason was the stereotypical perception of animation, expressed in the following: "Animation = Animation = Cartoons - Entertainment for children". Before that, no animated series had been shown in Russia, designed exclusively for teenagers, and not for the public at the age of 0 to infinity. And the mass Russian audience simply did not expect to see on the blue screen the disclosure of gender relations instead of funny adventures of friends.

In addition, unlike most Western countries in Russia, it is practically not censored, which increases the interest of the teenage audience. There was no difference in cultures. It concerned Sailor-stars, young men who after reincarnation

become girls - the trick of the series, however, not devoid of old traditions. According to Japanese mythology, people after become ghosts and are alive in female form. In the mid-90s, the appearance of otaku club's dates back to the mid-90s. The first such club was the R.An.Ma club (Russian Association of Anime and Manga Fans), founded in 1996. Beginning in 2000, the famous children's anime series "Pokemon" was shown on Russian television. Until then, the term "anime" was rarely used, and the works were simply designated as "Japanese cartoons".

In 2002, the magazine Country of Games published the column Banzai, the most competent series of articles on Japanese mass culture in Russia, and the Internet magazine Anime Magazine, and finally the official distributors of anime on video cassettes and DVDs. New anime publishers are emerging: in 2005. "XL Media, Mega-Anime in 2006 and Reanimedia in 2007. In 2005, the active broadcasting of anime on MTV Russia and Muz-TV began.

Anime festivals are regularly organized, including the All-Russian Festival of Japanese Animation in Voronezh, the North-Western Festival of Manga and Anime "M.Ani.Fest" in St. Petersburg, the South Russian Festival of Japanese Animation "Tanibata" in Rostov-on-Don and the Moscow Anime-Festival.

THE WORLD THROUGH THE EYES OF YOUTH

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The view of youth on a changing world.

Youth is not curious about everything
what is associated with her yesterday,
she eagerly looks only to the future.

(Boris Akunin from the book “The Seasons”)

The aim of the article is to show the problems of youth in modern society. Today's world is a departure from reality. Unfortunately, lost of lost in the whirl of real life, find a "refuge" in illusion, fog, in a fictitious virtual world. Drugs and alcohol. Internet addiction. Gambling addiction. Subcultures. A huge black octopus, dragging youth into the abyss. Someone stops in time and breaks free. Most die, not understanding why he lived.

In our world, you can often hear from adults that the modern generation is lost. And not only that. Modern man lives in a completely different way, annually destroying the heritage of the past in himself more and more. Those values that were laid in him by parents replace others. But are they worthy of replacing things that have been around for centuries? Will they benefit?

Youth is not only the future, it is a “living present”, and it is important to understand how already today the young generation determines the content and nature of the future, how much it carries the “spirit of the new time”.

The problems of modern youth in our time are becoming increasingly relevant. Priorities are changing, among young people, throughout the world.

Instead of being kind, honest and obedient, thinking about family, our younger generation increasingly wants to stand out due to addictions, violence and superiority. Therefore, adults have a difficult task - to instill goodness and humanity in adolescents in order to avoid the subsequent problems of youth in modern society and society. The most important among existing youth problems, are: immorality in behavior, alcoholism, drug addiction, smoking, crime or suicide, substitution of life values.

Our modern, rapidly changing world should set the young generation at this pace, moreover, this generation is the engine of the modern world. Everything positive, innovative, revolutionary in all areas of life is formed by young people.

However, to achieve truly significant goals in life, young people need extensive knowledge, experience, persistence in achieving goals, general erudition and a progressive outlook on things.

I understand that many factors influence on the formation of such qualities of young people. This is a personal position in life, and the socio-economic situation and the ability of the state to create favorable conditions for the formation of a healthy, educated and purposeful generation. Indeed, it is today's young generation that forms the adult generation of the future, and we must make every effort to create the best society: the absence of wars and environmental problems, the observance of basic human rights.

Here is one small story, but extremely thoughtful. It seems to me that neither the Japanese emperors nor Omar Khayyam rose to the height of this story. The author of the story is Archpriest Andrei Vladimirov. "The bunny, looking at the sky with eyes full of tears, said: "Those who truly love should not be afraid of suffering, "and hugged the hedgehog standing tightly and tightly! "

In conclusion I have to say that the world is really beautiful. We burst into it from childhood. So I wanted to begin quickly to master it ourselves, without adults. It beckoned with its mystery and unpredictable freedom. And now it is open to us. Dream. Set a cherished goal. Improve yourself, develop, have your point of view and firm position. Know that only a person can cope with problems himself.

PHENOMENON OF DOWNSHIFTING

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At first glance, the word “downshifting” may seem to have a very complex and hidden meaning. But, in fact, everything is very simple. Downshifting is a term that reflects the human position of "giving up a good life and living a quiet life for yourself."

You can start with the fact that people from early childhood begin to make their choice: Which profession to choose? What kind of people to communicate with? What life position should he choose?

Let's talk a little about who is downshifter? From the earliest years we are taught to be certain consumers. By about 30 to 40 years a person reaches his peak in his career when he has his own savings and investments, his or her personal social status. Such people primarily often express a feeling of not only pride in themselves, but also a certain power over other people. Downshifters are those people who are tired of their "rich lives". This may contribute to some reasons:

- 1) this choice is related to health problems;
- 2) problems at work, such as a crisis of crucial situations;
- 3) routine working days: meetings, negotiations, trips, etc;
- 4) various psychological reasons.

You can list many more reasons, but these are the most common.

Many criticize such people, but no one is entitled to criticize them for their choice. Such people do not need “rich social life”, do not need expensive cars, houses, yachts, luxurious garment. They need some peace from all affairs. Many people choose hitchhiking around the world, rest with friends or relatives, they can

also spend their holidays with themselves. This rest can be described as a way to rethink everything and bring everything in its own way. The question arises: how can a person so easily abandon a "beautiful life"? As a matter of fact, it depends on what kind of person he or she is. Maybe, he or she was planning or it happened spontaneously.

What are the consequences of downshifting? How does this affect a person's life? Most teenagers do not realize why downshifting is desirable to some extent, but ask about that for more mature people, they will answer the question without any problems. This is much more familiar topic for them since they have already achieved their goals in order to be successful. The consequences of downshifting are very diverse: some do not want to leave the "comfort zone", some after a certain amount of time returned to their official jobs.

It can be concluded that downshifting is not so bad for people. This phenomenon influences a person favourably, as he can feel like a "free person" at last.

AMAZING LIFE IN MALTA

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Malta is a tiny island nation in the Mediterranean Sea that has neither mountains nor rivers, but boasts a rich history of amazing events. He is a champion in the density of cultural and historical monuments, boasts unique architecture and always hospitable people. Our review contains only the latest and most interesting facts about this amazing island country.

Officially, in the management of Malta there are 7 islands, only 3 of them are inhabited by people and have a developed infrastructure. The state has a unique

location, which is located at the intersection of trade routes. Malta boasts the oldest trade relations with Sicily. On the islands themselves there are no mountains, no rivers, no other sources of drinking water. Therefore, it is not always clear to visitors why local wine is much cheaper than regular water.

Until 1964, Malta was a colony of Great Britain, which could not but affect the local traditions. For example, in Malta it is customary to drive along the left side of the street, and there are many reckless drivers among the drivers. English is the second official language and is included in the compulsory school curriculum.

By the way, the name of the republic comes from the Phoenician word "malat", which translates as "refuge". Since ancient times, the island has been unofficially known as the "land of honey" because there has always been a large production of honey.

Maltese streets are considered one of the narrowest in the world. Such a layout allows you to create a shadow from the houses and, according to the indigenous Maltese, can serve as an excellent tool for creating defensive fortifications in case of invasion. On the houses themselves, in addition to the usual numbers, you can see the names of their owners.

The main source of income for Malta is the profit from the tourism business. Tourists generate a quarter of all government revenue. Annually, up to 1.2 million tourists from all over the world come to the island. This is due not only to unique attractions, a wonderful climate, but also to some interesting myths. For example, one of the most common myths says that Malta is part of Atlantis, which had once disappeared from the face of the earth.

UNUSUAL FACTS

1. If you look closer to the Maltese Church, you will be surprised to find two hours. They say that the clock on the right shows the correct time and is intended for believers. And those on the left are designed to confuse the unclean forces that tempt people.

2. The Maltese are very musical, almost every resident of the island plays a musical instrument. And for children, attending a music school is almost an obligation.

3. In Malta, there is an interesting tradition: when a child turns one year old, various objects are laid out in front of him. Because the kid chose, determined his future profession. For example, if a child picks up a coin, he will be an entrepreneur, a book writer, and so on.

4. There is almost no crime in the country. The Maltese themselves, half-jokingly, half-seriously explain this by the fact that the state is too small. The criminal will have nowhere to hide.

5. Maltese are very fond of various competitions and contests. It is very strange that the Maltese athletes participated in the Olympic Games since 1924, but could not win at least one medal.

6. Tourism is the backbone of Malta's economy. The second largest inflow of money after industry. About a million tourists come to Malta annually.

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К ВОПРОСУ О МЕСТЕ СТРАНОВЕДЕНИЯ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА

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В связи с интеграцией нашего общества в мировое сообщество, вопрос о внедрении современного студента в мировую культуру, повышении его образовательного уровня и свободном владении иностранным языком, а также необходимости изучения культуры народов, язык которых изучается, особенно актуален.

Социально-экономические преобразования общества тесно связаны с повышением культурного уровня личности и общества в целом, поскольку культура служит универсальным механизмом формирования личности. В современном обществе обучение личности, которая стремится к самореализации и имеет чувство ответственности, способна критически мыслить и ценить духовное и материальное богатство, накопленное человечеством, крайне важно.

Усвоение национальных культурных и исторических ценностей включает в себя понимание международной, универсальной и национальной гармонии. Это способствует распространению культурных достижений других народов и их мастерства. Данная работа предполагает психолого-педагогическую культуру преподавателя иностранных языков, хорошее знание психологических особенностей учащихся, связанных с возрастом, а также умение использовать образовательный потенциал содержания учебного материала. В процессе изучения краеведения реализуются познавательные, воспитательные, социально-терапевтические, адаптивные и развивающие образовательные функции.

Страноведение включает в себя не только лексику, национальную культуру и национальные реалии, но и выполняет значительную образовательную функцию, воспитывает уважение и любовь студентов к стране изучаемого языка.

При всех возможных вариантах культурной самобытности отечественная педагогика за последние три столетия развивалась в основном в рамках западных подходов. Например, софисты были первыми в истории, кто попытался подчинить задачи образования и обучения потребностям

конкретного человека, чтобы сделать их полностью зависимыми от их потребностей и интересов.

Интернационализация образования - это объективный и постоянно развивающийся процесс, который происходил в различных формах задолго до завершения формирования наций и национальных систем образования в их нынешнем виде. Это связано не столько с образовательными аспектами, сколько с общими параллельными процессами и общими социально-экономическими и культурными явлениями, которые происходят в мире.

Страноведение является частью содержания обучения иностранному языку, что представляется одним из наиболее актуальных вопросов педагогики. Это очевидно, поскольку социальный порядок общества в области обучения иностранному языку в настоящее время имеет задачу развития духовной сферы обучающихся, повышения гуманистического содержания образования, образовательного и развивающего потенциала субъекта по отношению к образованию. Основной целью обучения иностранному языку является развитие личности обучающегося, которая участвует в межкультурном общении и совершенствуется независимо от освоенной деятельности [1].

В настоящее время общепризнан тезис о неразрывности изучения иностранных языков с одновременным ознакомлением учащихся с культурой страны изучаемого языка, его истории и современной жизни. Национальные исследования помогают изучающим иностранный язык понять национальные исторические особенности, присущие другой социокультуре.

Известно, что язык, являясь одним из главных признаков нации, выражает культуру говорящих на нем людей, то есть национальную культуру. Поэтому можно и нужно преподавать иностранный язык не только как новый код, как новый способ выражения мыслей, но и как источник информации о национальной культуре коренных народов изучаемого языка [2].

Страноведение является обязательным условием развития межкультурной коммуникации, поскольку человек не рождается русским, немцем, японцем и т.д, а становится таковым благодаря принадлежности к

определенному национальному сообществу. Формирование определенных рас и национальностей происходит в одних и тех же культурных условиях. Каждый язык - это прежде всего, средство общения между людьми. Поэтому для студентов, изучающих иностранный язык, важно иметь возможность использовать его в качестве инструмента общения. В сегодняшней реструктуризации государственного образования этот принцип должен стать основополагающим, которым реализуются достижения культуры и научно-культурного прогресса на национальном и международном уровнях.

Любое изучение языка существенно влияет на личность, меняя ее. И хотя речь идет о необходимости воспитания гражданина Европы, гражданина мира, но это никоим образом не уменьшает проблемы патриотического воспитания, отсюда столь необходим и важен диалог культур.

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DONETSK PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC - MY FIRST IMPRESSIONS

Dean O'Brein

Coming to Donetsk was fate. There's no other way to explain it. After travelling to and from Ukraine for almost 10 years, working on a number of photography projects, I knew that Donbass was waiting.

I'd watched how the decommunisation process attempted to destroy Ukraine's Soviet past. The Lenin monuments being toppled by fascists. The street names being

changed. Soviet symbols being banned and the loss of what you could describe as Ukraine's national language 'Russian'.

I'd witnessed the torchlight parades in the centre of Kiev by the nationalists, the Germanic symbols on open show, and the beatings of anyone showing any empathy towards anything even slightly Russian. Copies of Hitler's book 'Mein Kampf' were available to buy openly from stall sellers on Maidan. And best of all, I didn't read about this in any newspapers, or see this on television, I came and witnessed this for myself. With my own eyes.

My final year in Ukraine was 2018. I was at Odessa on May 2nd and went to the Trade Unions House for the anniversary of the fire. I think this was a turning point for me. I saw how fascists had turned up to disrupt the memorial service. They were pushing mothers and grandmothers who were bringing flowers. They tried to disrupt the whole event. An old lady there told me 'These people do not even have respect for the dead'. The Police in Odessa just looked on, smoking and later were laughing and talking with the fascists.

A few days later I travelled by train to Mariupol for Victory Day on May 9th, only to be hassled by the Police, constantly stopped and questioned. I visited the Police station in Mariupol where many people died. People had started to gather and lay flowers but they too were being harassed by the Police. They were no longer allowed to wear the St. George's ribbon. When the Police saw me they held and questioned me for no good reason.

Slavyansk, Kramatorsk and Mariupol are all close to the contact line on the government controlled side of this conflict. I'd visited there a few times, spoke to locals about the current situation and gave talks in schools. I spoke at a school in Kramatorsk and talked to people on the streets of Slavyansk. It helped me to get a proper handle on what's happening there. Many had relatives on the other side and crossed over regularly. They told me 'you must go to the other side, we have family

there'. 'You need to see what the Ukrainians are doing to their own people'. This weighed heavily on my mind and I realised that I needed to do something.

I needed to know what life was like there for the people. Living day to day in a city under threat of constant attack. Yet still having to go about their daily duties of taking children to school and going to work etc.. So I set about gaining the correct accreditation to enter Donbass and applied for a Russian visa. It took a lot of planning.

Finally on Tuesday 7th May 2019 I arrived in Donetsk. It was nothing like I had been told. It was a very beautiful, clean city. The people were welcoming and I was able to go around the city with my camera. I wandered into parks, shopped at the flea market and of course visited 'Don Mak's' for a burger. The police were friendly, polite and did not request 'a present' (bribe) unlike the police in Kiev when they stop a foreigner.

Of course people were curious when they saw me, but they just wanted to talk and asked why I had come. I told them that people on 'the other side' had said that I should come and see the devastation that the Ukrainian government had inflicted on it's own people. They thanked me and said 'when you get home, just tell truth, that's all we ask'.

I decided to stay close to the centre in Kievsky district. Occasionally I could hear shelling in the distance at night. It might sound strange but this is where I wanted to be. Close to the people. I wanted to feel what they have felt. To hear what they have heard, and to see what they have seen. It's important for me as a photographer to experience what I am photographing.

I loved my morning walk from the top of Artema Street into Lenin Square. I'd pass a coffee shop each morning and stop for a drink. The young girl there spoke great English so I would chat with her most days. She was happy to tell me about life in the new republic. About her hopes and dreams for the future. Like many young

people, she dreamed of travelling. She told me that gaining a Russian passport could make these dreams a reality.

I'm interested in the normal, everyday things. People riding the trolley bus. Kids holding hands with their parents walking to school. Pensioners sitting on benches watching the world go by. These simple acts fascinate me. Especially when all this is happening in a city which is at war.

Whilst sitting near Lenin Square I met and spoke to fighters who had travelled to Donbass to fight against Ukrainian forces. They told me how they too now need Russian passports as they can no longer return to their native countries. If they do, they'll be arrested and placed in prison for a long time.

I was there for Victory Day and Republic Day. I wandered freely amongst the crowds of people. Everyone I spoke to explained how they wanted the war to end. How they wanted peace. They also made it very clear though, that they did not want to return to government controlled Ukraine. This was not an option. They told me about the children who have been killed, the pensioners who have lost their homes. 'Too much blood has been split' one person told me. I see many similarities with this conflict and that in Northern Ireland.

I travelled to the outskirts of Donetsk Airport. Travelling along Stratonavtiv Street I met a pensioner who still lived in one of the houses close by. Her name was Antonina Prokofievna. She now survives by collecting scrap metal. I saw the shelled and abandoned houses. The appalling conditions that people such as her are forced to live in. I was shocked to see the terrible damage that western backed forces have done to this region.

I then travelled to a frontline position at Yasinovata. Here I spent time with volunteers from Vostok Battalion. I didn't see any Russian soldiers. Just local volunteers protecting what they feel is theirs. Protecting their homes, family and

culture. Many have left their families and jobs to come and fight. They told me how they want the freedom to speak Russian.

I love Soviet history and am a big collector of Soviet items. Donetsk still has its Lenin monuments which was great to see. History as it should be seen. I even saw a monument of Taras Savchenko and I asked a man why this is still standing here. He said 'We are not like them on the other side destroying history. We have respect for our past, we're not animals'. I soon realised that the people here do not hate Ukrainians on the other side, they just want to be left alone.

I see my future work here in Donetsk People's Republic. I can't return to government controlled Ukraine. But I don't want to either. I've made my choice and I know it's the right one.

So I suppose the final question must be 'Do I have any regrets about coming to Donetsk?' Yes, I do. I regret that I never came sooner. I never got the chance to meet Givi, Motorola or Alexander Zakharchenko. That's my only regret. They all came from very humble beginnings and fought from the heart. I would have loved to have spent time with each of them and the opportunity to have told their stories.

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СЕКЦИЯ 2. ПРОБЛЕМЫ СОВРЕМЕННОГО ОБЩЕСТВА (АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ЯЗЫК)

PROBLEMS OF EDUCATION IN CURRENT TIME

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1) XXI century as a century that erases ethnic boundaries
Twenty first century is a time of ubiquitous spread of technology and media. Technology became such a common part of an everyday life, that now living is unimaginable without a computer or a phone, it became a bare minimum. Such progress influenced all the fields of daily activity of a human being but communication between people was influenced the most, because now distance of hundreds kilometers is not a problem anymore and thus international communication started to form between people of different social statuses which lead to extinction of language barrier. If literally 50-60 years ago communicating with people from different continents was hard and expensive, now it's the most accessible by anyone that it ever been, it makes knowledge of two, three or even four languages a common fact. For instance if you will take current time and current generation, you will struggle to find a person who doesn't know any foreign language at least on a base level, because of development of computer technologies, television and internet in particular, after all these are the places where interracial "Information transfer" occurs quite often, and this is exactly why people learn different languages to feel comfortable in these socially important aspects of a modern life.

2) The growth of the average human education standard
To start on this thesis, we should firstly refer to psychology. People tend to have standard thinking and thus is a scientifically proven fact thus each of us is afraid to

leave the society on a subconscious level which means everyone should adapt to a current tone of time. As Heidegger said [1]“On a basic level – human being is a temporary creature”, which is applicable to entire humanity. Society change the concept of norms, expand moral boundaries and generally the form of society is being changed by the influence of time. An important indicator of “spirit of time” is the average education of humanity. That is to say in III-II century BC was normal to be illiterate or don't know how to write or count, but in XIX century person couldn't let this, simply, he wouldn't survive without the ability to count the money, and this indicator of average education is constantly rising why people always absorb a colossal amount of knowledge to please the society. Thus now everyone has knowledge of cultural features or at least abstract or stereotypical idea about cultures, regardless of their social class.

3)Pseudoretardation of cultural development of current generation
So, firstly we should tell what is Pseudoretardation[2]. Informational pseudoretardation — is a medical term that means mental disability, in which person shows signs of mental retardation caused by excessive consumption of information, which leads to a big development lag, memory impairment, low level of self-control. And someone already asked himself how it's bound with our topic. It's time to explain. This diagnose is applicable in varying degrees to the most users of information systems, such as social media, media, and internet as a whole, which in turn affects not on just cultural aspect knowledge of a person, but on his intelligence as a whole. But it's worth to note that cultural oversaturation itself leads to such disability. In order not to be unfounded, let's make an example. Which one of those who present in this room could name at least 3 Ayvazovsky's paintings? Who knows when “War and Peace” was written? Or, at least, which Tolstoy wrote it? That's right. Only a few can answer, but why? It's simple, if science started it's rapid grow 100-150 years ago, culture was developing pretty much since humanity appeared. And now because of informational accessibility what accumulated for centuries we try to learn it all in 11 years, while not specific aspect of culture, that is interesting for a specific individual, but the whole culture of humanity. And as a result from

overload with information our brain tends to drop such knowledge, after all education system has a dynamic tone of knowledge, which means it emphasizes specific moment and specific information. And this information is perceived by short-term memory and stays not so long, slowly fading away, but due human beliefs what is important to him only small amount of knowledge stays. As a conclusion from all that has been said . We know a lot about culture and countries, but not so much specific information.

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ADVERTISING AS THE FIRST STEP TO SUCCESS IN MODERN SOCIETY

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Creating and implementing an advertising campaign is no easy task. Having said that, when funds are very tight, and you are just starting out, it can be daunting to hire an agency - even a small shop, or one freelancer. But if you are truly invested in your product or service, and are passionate about getting the word out, there are steps you can follow to do it yourself. [1, с.1].

1. People come in contact with ads from all types of businesses all the time.

So, what will make your potential customers buy your company's product or service versus going with one of your competitors? Show your potential customers

why your business is their number one choice and why they shouldn't even consider your competitors. What makes you different? What do you have that no one else does? This is the kind of thing you're looking for! [2, c. 1-3].

2. Use A Powerful Headline: Grab Their Attention!

People scan things quickly. They come into contact with so many advertisements each day that they can't possibly read each one. This is why you have to make sure that your advertisement actually grabs and keeps their attention. The question you need to ask is "Who are you trying to attract? What would get their attention?"

3. Make Them An Offer They Can't Refuse!

Consumers love a bargain. So offer them a good one so that they'll come back to you time and time again. Whether you're offering an unbeatable price, a free trial, free shipping or a bundled package, going out of your way to provide your customers with a good deal will help you be successful.

4. Talk About The Benefits – What's In It For Them!

Explaining the features of your products or services is important, but explaining the benefits for the customer is really what it's all about. After all, people are more interested in what they get from your services than what you do. Make sense? List out all your services or products. For each one, list out everything that service does. Then, next list out what the result of each feature is – the benefit for the client.

5. Tell Your News: Create an Advertorial!

People are seven times more likely to read a news article than an advertisement. People come in contact with regular ads all day long. There is really no incentive for them to read your ad if you don't offer them more than what everyone else is offering. Readers want to read more once they realize the article isn't just advertising your business but helping them. For example, the ad can provide them with lots of advice, tips and information and how your company and products can help them.

6. Take Away Their Fear: Make Your Offer As Risk-Free As Possible!

If people fear that they're going to lose their money and regret their purchase, they are unlikely to purchase your product. So it's a great idea to offer a risk-free guarantee. Knowing there is no risk and that they don't have anything to lose by purchasing your product or service, is a powerful purchasing inducement. This "reverses" the risk and places some of it on the seller. This is called "risk reversal".

7. Don't just tell your potential customers about what your company has to offer. Tell them directly to click on your ad, order your product, pay for your service, etc. For example, your "call to action" can encourage people to email you for more information, to fill out a form to find out more about your services, to join your weekly or monthly email newsletter or to purchase your product or service. It could even direct users to click on your ad to take them to your website rather than just looking at the advertisement.

8. Make It Seem Urgent, Give Them a Reason To Buy NOW!

If people see that they only have a set amount of time, such as a few hours or days, to snag an unforgettable deal that they're already pretty excited about, they will be more likely to make a move now than later. Many people assume that they'll be able to get the same deal later on. But if they know that they can't, they'll be more likely to take the deal now.

9. Use Exciting Graphics

People are visual. Plain text on a plain background can be boring. People don't always want to read everything that has been written in an ad or an article. You can appeal to the visual interest that your clients have by adding exciting graphics to your advertisements.

10. Complete Contact Information

You've told the interested customers what you're selling, now tell them where to buy it. Anything else is a waste of money. You should use your ads to link people to your website for more information as part of the contact information.

So, these 10 tips for creating an effective ad can help your advertising stand head and shoulders over those of your competition. Advertising is important and good advertising is what will help your company succeed.

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INTERNET AND ITS ROLE IN THE LIFE OF YOUTH

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We live in an information age. We've already learned how fast the knowledge base is growing and understood that it is impossible to know everything. The public, scientists, business people all receive most of the information from the media.

The Internet is a common thing today. Everybody knows that the Internet is a global computer network which embraces hundreds of millions of users all over the world and helps us to communicate with each other. The main use of the Internet is to find information about current events, new jobs, inventions or businesses. You can also use the Internet to read newspapers and magazines, plan your holiday or make online purchases. E-mail makes it possible to send electronic messages in a second

anywhere in the world. You can chat and make new friends on the Internet. Young people are fond of playing games and simply wasting their time in the virtual world.

The history of Internet began in the United States in the 1960s. It was a military experiment, designed to help to survive during a nuclear war, when everything around might be polluted by radiation and it would be dangerous to get out for any living being to get some information or to somewhere.

Ten years later in 1985 the English computer scientist Timothy Berners-Lee introduced the World Wide Web. During the early 1990s increasingly large numbers of users began to use the Internet, due to the ability of the WWW to easily handle multimedia documents. Nowadays, the Internet is used on a mass scale by about 250 million people all over the world. [1, c.370].

Nowadays the Internet has a big impact on companies and organizations. Business people use the Internet for work, for arranging meetings, resolving problems, filing documentation and storing information.

At the same time, the Internet creates a lot of disadvantages for its users.

It gives thieves access to personal information and a cloak of invisibility: they don't have to be there in person to make a fraudulent purchase or to apply for credit in your name.

Using the Internet also makes it more difficult for law enforcement agencies to trace them when they do this. Online identity theft is difficult to track.

Another thing is that it reduces social activity and contacts, leads to isolation and brings psychological problems. People have ceased to enjoy real communication and mostly exist in virtual world, where they can't learn how to build relationships and find common interests, show respect and understanding.

Probably, using the Internet deprives the youth of the main thing – ability to think independently, develop their cultural. Many started using youth slang instead of the words of politeness, lost the culture of behavior and language. [1, c.375].

Moreover, due to the lack of experience and knowledge, many teenagers and young people are exposed to various risks and dangers, nothing to say about the negative effect on the process of study.

Anyway, we must not underestimate beneficial value of the Internet. Multi-media data, emailing, online chatting, file transfer and file sharing, e-commerce, online gaming makes the Internet an enormous carrier of various information resources and services.

We cannot imagine our life without this network of millions of computers around the globe which is fast and captivating with more and more users logging on everyday and staying on longer and longer.

Let us hope, the Internet will not only help develop our outlook and educational level, support project and business development, but create opportunities for growing democracy and freedom and guide us to the society with no borders but peace and respect.

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THE ROLE OF YOUTH IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF STATE POLICY

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Young people of any state need space for the manifestation of their individual abilities in society. The government of the state must make every effort so that young people become independent citizens. The involvement of young people in politics is

aimed to help with their physical, moral and social development. Only together young and adult generations can ensure the prosperity of the state. The goal of youth policy is to preserve the strength of present and future life foundations and values.

State policy in foreign countries regarding youth begins to develop in the middle of the twentieth century. The active development of youth policy was served by a series of protests: " youthquake ", "student revolutions." They went through a number of countries in Europe and the United States and declared youth as an effective force in social reconstruction [0, p.14].

Today we will consider the forms of youth participation in politics around the world. One of the countries with the most developed legal framework for state youth policy is Germany. The Government of Germany supports an intellectual, creative and physical development of youth.

In Germany, there is a special executive body that is responsible for the formation and implementation of youth policy: the Federal Ministry for Family Affairs, Senior Citizens, Women and Youth [2, p.23].

The state helps in realizing the scientific, technical and creative potential of young people, and supports the activities of youth public associations. Therefore, young people are forming an active life position for participation in the political life of the country. Thus, the government is seeking the implementation of programs for the formation and development of a youth policy system.

The United States Department of Youth Policy and the United States Agency for International Development are involved in youth policy in the United States. Direct participation in youth programs is taken by the departments of health and social protection; education and labor [3, p.110].

Youth development programs are developed by such major organizations as the federal youth development agencies, Youth Initiatives and the Institute for Youth Policy. They are engaged in assessing the current situation of youth and determine the prospects for its development.

In the United States many youth humanitarian and scout organizations are based. Their activities are aimed at interacting with youth organizations of other countries.

Some of the youth organizations in the United States were founded with state support. For example, the National Committee of Youth and Childhood, Youth Development Forum. They perform primarily analytical and research tasks.

There are currently over 400 youth support and protection programs in the United States. The most popular are the Youth Defense League programs: the League of Unlimited Campus Opportunities, Students for the Elimination of Hunger, Face to the Street, Help program for single mothers under 20, Introduction to Urban Issues, and the Salvation Army program », Which currently cover all the professional educational institutions of the country [4, p.71].

In modern Russian society, youth policy is a complex system of programs and projects. Consider the following forms of youth participation in political life:

1. Youth branches of political parties: "The Time of the Young", "Lenin Communist Youth Union of the Russian Federation."

2. Youth branches of political organizations: "Eurasian Youth Union", "Revolutionary Communist Youth Union".

3. Public youth movements and organizations: "Defense", "New Time", "Youth Left Front".

4. Government youth movements and organizations: "Young Guard", "Young Russia", "Ascent" [5, p.15].

We, the youth of the Donetsk People's Republic, believe that our state needs to focus on the experience of countries near and far abroad. At this stage, the Republic is actively working with the young population. Such large social movements and organizations as the "Young Republic" and the "Youth Parliament" have already been operating. Their goal is to support and promote to the masses the initiatives of the young people of the DPR.

The unifying factor in the youth policy of the countries is the orientation to the adopted international documents. The United Nations, the International Labor Organization, the World Health Organization, UNESCO, the Council of Europe determine the trends, principles, approaches and directions for the implementation of youth policy. At the same time, each country has its own youth legislation, which is based on the social, historical and cultural characteristics of people.

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THE PROBLEM OF POVERTY IN THE WORLD

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The problem of poverty existed almost the entire period of human development, which was due to a complex of both objective and subjective factors.

These include the problem of production, the shadow economy, living in adverse climatic conditions, disability, stratification of society, the presence in the family of a large number of disabled members, etc.

The aim of the article is to study poverty as the main factor that determines the socio-economic level of the country and affects the deterioration of the quality of human life.

Modern society has significant economic differences between the social strata of the population. As noted, we are talking about the absolute enrichment and absolute impoverishment of large masses of the population. This problem manifests itself not only in violation of the objective laws of economic development, but also in the socio-political and spiritual spheres, which negatively affects the foundations of the life of the nation as a human community. Unfortunately, as practice shows, poverty around the world has become sustainable as a result of the economic depression [1].

By poverty we mean a state in which there is a mismatch between the achieved average level of satisfaction of needs and the ability to meet them in certain social groups, segments of the population. It is characterized by the desire to satisfy material needs.

The problem of poverty caused by the violation of proportions, condition (differentiation of population by level of material, spiritual and social benefits and proportions of the relationship man – society – nature, person – social group – class – society. They are based on the key proportion between the productive and consuming power of society, the expression of which is the ratio of working and free time [2].

In our opinion, first of all, the problem of poverty is related to social forms. The relevance of this issue lies in the stratification of our society into poor and rich.

The economic level of development has a great influence on the unemployment rate. For clarity, here are some statistics.

Table 1 – The twinning of poor and rich countries

Poor countries		Rich countries	
A country	GDP per capita	A country	GDP per capita
Somalia	315\$	Qatar	124 940\$
Central African Republic	449 \$	Luxembourg	109 200\$
Democratic Republic of the Congo	2618\$	Singapore	90 600\$

These statistics indicate that there is a huge gap between the countries in the economy. There is no economic stability in the world, which leads to the fact that some countries have everything, while others have nothing.

Most often, poverty is assessed using the subsistence level, which allows you to determine the poverty line. Cost of living — cost value sufficient to ensure the normal functioning of the human body, health food basket, as well as a minimum set of nonfood products and a minimum set of services required to meet basic social and cultural needs of the individual.

The problem is not limited to the scale of poverty, although it is certainly very important. It is also a matter of how poor these people are, what they can buy with their income, to what extent their children are protected.

The most acute problems are the poverty of families with children. The low level of remuneration does not always allow even both working parents to provide an acceptable (by low national standards) standard of living for their minor children. The number of children is a particularly significant risk factor for poverty in families with children under three years of age (on average, their poverty rate reaches 40.3%). Thus, families with children initially have a high risk of poverty, and its value is directly proportional to the number of children [1].

The solution of the problem of poverty needs improvement of scientifically grounded actions which have to consider specificity, features of formation and

distribution of poverty, the reasons of its occurrence. Strategically, the socio-economic development of society is impossible without reducing poverty, increasing material wealth, and thus creating sufficient conditions for the development of human capital. Consequently, the level of welfare is decisive for the reproduction and development of the level of human life, the development of any country as a whole.

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ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF DISTANCE EDUCATION

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Problem statement. Nowadays, education is available to everyone and everyone who has the desire, try to get it. Education is not only an important component of human development, but also the ability to apply their knowledge in practice. To do this, someone enters universities or colleges, enrolls in courses. Recently, distance education, or online learning, has been gaining popularity. If earlier it was the prerogative of people who didn't have the opportunity to attend educational institutions for any reason, now it is a normal practice.

The aim of the study is to consider the advantages and disadvantages of distance education.

Research objectives: to analyze distance learning, to identify the positive and negative sides.

We have carefully researched the distance learning process and highlighted the advantages and disadvantages.

About the merits:

1. The ability to choose the time for training.

You have the right to determine exactly when and how long your "school day" will last. You can also take a break, if necessary, at any time and for the period of time that you determine. [2]

2. Time saving and relative cheapness of training.

You need not to get up very early to catch the bus. Now you can save an extra hour or two without spending it on the way to the university. In addition, you can make a schedule and choose a lesson plan. And online coaches will be cheaper than college tuition, for example.

3. The ability to choose the teaching staff.
4. Possibility to choose the training program independently.

You choose what subjects and languages you are interested in, which eliminates the unnecessary and boring study of disciplines that you are not interested in. [0]

5. An appropriately organized workplace.

There are people who are helped to tune in the right way cozy atmosphere. Thus, you can organize the workplace so that it inspires and motivates you.

6. The lack of dress code.

Not everyone likes the formal-business style in clothes, and someone even constrains in terms of self-expression. Learning remotely, you can wear comfortable clothes for you.

7. Reduced stress levels.

Features of the assessment system, exams, tests and other written work, strained relationships with someone, public speaking – all this can cause severe stress, which is sure to hit your health.

About the shortcomings:

1. Violation of socialization and interaction with a typical team.

Being in a team, a person learns to work together, interact with people, overcome conflict situations, as well as business etiquette. How to dress, how to behave, what to say and to whom—all these opportunities are missed.

2. Lack of "adult life" experience.

Studying at the university is the same work that you need to go to every day, that you need to perform, and for which you can get money. Studying full-time, the student gets used to it and in the future it is easier to adapt during working activities.

3. Narrow focus and incompleteness of knowledge. [3]

The University provides an opportunity to study general and special disciplines, which contributes to the comprehensive development of the student.

4. Lack of practice.

Often, while studying in higher educational institutions, students are sent to practice, where they learn to apply their knowledge. Lack of practice can cause great difficulties when applying for a job, as well as when performing it at first.

Conclusions: Analyzing all of the above, we believe that despite all the advantages of distance learning, it is necessary to give preference to education in an educational institution, if there are no special indications for learning at home.

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YOUTH'S SUICIDE AS A GLOBAL PROBLEM

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In the whole world, over 800,000 people die from suicide each year. What drives so many people to take their own lives? To those who are not in the grips of suicidal depression and despair, it's difficult to understand what drives so many individuals to take their own lives. But a suicidal person is in so much pain that he or she can see no other option.

Suicide is the 10th leading cause of death worldwide. Suicide occurs throughout the world, affecting individuals of all nations, cultures, religions, genders and classes. For example in 2019, among the top five suicide rate countries are South Korea, Lithuania, Russia, Guyana and Belarus.

Korea's suicide rate, attributable to its high-stress society, is among the highest in the world. South Korea is known for its high-stress professional and educational environments, in which it is customary to work or study long hours into the night.

South Korea has the highest suicide rate in the world for children aged 10-19. For children, most suicides are caused by stress relating to education. Korean children have a school year of 11 months and often spend over 16 hours a day at school and at afterschool programs.

Other countries, including Singapore and Japan, have high-stress work environments but don't face the same high suicide rates that South Korea does. The special combination of factors that has led to this situation includes traditional cultural beliefs and the social stigma around receiving treatment for mental illnesses.

Most South Koreans with mental illnesses never see a medical professional because it is considered a thing of shame, as if one is too weak to handle the pressures of life that everyone experiences.

The South Korean government has taken some measures to combat the high suicide rates, but none has been very effective.

One of the myths about suicidal talk, and actual suicide attempts, in young people is that they are just a bid for attention or "a cry for help." Kids who talk or write about killing themselves are dismissed as overly dramatic – obviously, they don't mean it! But a threat of suicide should never be dismissed.

If a child is talking about dying, you should always pay attention. "I wish I was dead." "I just want to disappear." "Maybe I should shoot myself." When you hear this kind of talk, it's important to take it seriously – even if you can't imagine your child meaning it seriously.

The most cited risk factors for suicide include psychiatric disorders, genetics, family and social situations.

Suicide is a desperate attempt to escape suffering that has become unbearable. Blinded by feelings of hopelessness, and isolation, a suicidal person can't see any way of finding relief except through death. But despite their desire for the pain to stop, most suicidal people are deeply conflicted about ending their own lives. They wish there was an alternative to suicide, but they just can't see one.

Common misconceptions about suicide are as follows:

Myth: People who talk about suicide won't really do it.

Fact: Almost everyone who attempts suicide has given some clue or warning. Don't ignore even indirect references to death or suicide. Statements like "You'll be sorry when I'm gone," "I can't see any way out," may indicate serious suicidal feelings.

Myth: Anyone who tries to kill him/herself must be crazy.

Fact: Most suicidal people are not psychotic or insane. They are upset, grief-stricken, depressed or despairing, but extreme distress and emotional pain are not necessarily signs of mental illness.

Myth: If a person is determined to kill him/herself, nothing is going to stop them.

Fact: Even the most severely depressed person has mixed feelings about death, wavering until the very last moment between wanting to live and wanting to die. Most suicidal people do not want death; they want the pain to stop.

If a loved one expresses thoughts or plans of suicide, it's essential to initiate a conversation.

When talking to a suicidal person you should:

Be yourself. Let the person know you care, that he/she is not alone;

Listen. Let the suicidal person unload despair, vent anger. No matter how negative the conversation seems, the fact that it is taking place is a positive sign;

Offer hope. Let the person know that his or her life is important to you;

Take the person seriously. If the person says things like, “I’m so depressed, I can’t go on,” ask the question: “Are you having thoughts of suicide?” You are not putting ideas in their head; you are showing that you are concerned, that you take them seriously, and that it’s OK for them to share their pain with you.

But you shouldn’t:

Argue with the suicidal person. Avoid saying things like: “Your suicide will hurt your family,” or “Look on the bright side.”;

Act shocked, lecture on the value of life, or say that suicide is wrong;

Offer ways to fix their problems, or give advice, or make them feel like they have to justify their suicidal feelings. It is not about how bad the problem is, but how badly it’s hurting your friend or loved one.

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TOLERANCE IN MODERN SOCIETY

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Analyzing the problem of tolerance in modern society, first of all two important observations should be made. First, the concept of "alien", "other" does not

mean ideas, behaviour, actions, rituals, which inevitably lead to degradation, to the destruction of the social and spiritual values. The unconditional problem in this case boils down to the fact, that in practice their catastrophic and negative value is not always immediately and unambiguously revealed. This explains the difficulties in assessing these ideas, and accordingly, personal social difficulties in forming a certain attitude to them. On the other hand, it should not be underestimated that it is a tolerant attitude, devoid of the desire to immediately prohibit, brand and reveal the true essence of the "other". One more idea is brought up by the mentioned above. Tolerance does not imply a mandatory rejection of criticism, discussion, and even more so from their own beliefs.

Currently, the problem of forming tolerance is a particularly great issue. This is due to a number of reasons: the sharp stratification of world civilization on economic, social and other grounds and the associated increase of intolerance; development of religious extremism; aggravation of interethnic relations caused by local wars; the problems of refugees, etc.

The main principles of tolerance *de jure* are as follows:

1) the rejection of violence as an unacceptable means of introducing a person to an idea;

2) voluntary choice, emphasis on the sincerity of his or her belief, "freedom of conscience". Just as in Christianity "preaching and example" are ways of proselytizing, the idea of tolerance can become a kind of landmark, a kind of flag of the movement, uniting like-minded people. It is not necessary to condemn or blame those who are not yet "enlightened»;

3) ability to force yourself without forcing others. Fear and coercion from the outside does not contribute to restriction and tolerance, although as an educational factor at a certain moment disciplines people, while forming certain morals;

4) obedience to laws, traditions and customs without violating them and meeting with public needs. Obedience to the laws, not to the will of the ruler or the

majority, is an important factor in the development and movement in the right direction;

5) acceptance of the other, which may differ in various ways-national, racial, cultural, religious, etc. Tolerance of each one contributes to the balance of integrity of society, the disclosure of completeness of its parts and the achievement of the "Golden means" on the basis of the Golden rule of morality.

The same principles but de facto are as follows:

1) in the UK schools in 2018 teachers were banned from calling pupils "boys" or "girls" . The purpose was not to offend those who have not decided on their future calling;

2) in the USA kindergartens the fairy tale "Three pigs" is renamed "Three puppies" not to offend the feelings of Muslims. At the same time, Muslims themselves are treated there with prejudice;

3) in the US a number of States recently tried to ban the book "The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn". It turned out that Mark Twain too often used the word "Negro" in this work;

4) Great Britain is "a champion" of tolerance. Children on costumed a cocktail party in kindergarten are banned to wear a pirate blindfold on eyes and cling hook on hands. It could hurt the feelings of people with similar injuries if they occasionally pass by.

To summarize the above mentioned, it is necessary to point out the most important thing: tolerance is good in its only manifestation when it is really necessary. It also should not be in favour of those who benefit from it and for whom it is convenient. It should be born in mind that the democratic society is built on the principle of equality.

THE ROLE OF THE UNITED NATIONS IN THE SETTLEMENT OF ARMED CONFLICTS

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The past century – and the past 50 years in particular – has been of extraordinary importance for the development of international law. At the beginning of the century, the principle was accepted that the waging of war was not without restraint. There were accepted notions of “protected” persons and of “combatants” and “non combatants”. The permanent Court of Arbitration was set up; then the Permanent International Court of Justice, both in the Hague. Later came the League of Nations, the first generalized international organization dedicated to peace and stability. This, with the Permanent court, was the guarantor of the post World War 1 minorities treaties – a point of departure for contemporary human rights. In turn, the United Nations became a truly universal international organization and its Charter and Statue have allowed great flexibility in what it does and how it does it [3, p.187]

The United Nations, or UN, is an international organization established in 1945 and now made up of 192 states. The Purposes of the United Nations are: first of all, to maintain international peace and security, and to that end: to take effective collective measures for the prevention and removal of threats to the peace, and for the suppression of acts of aggression or other breaches of the peace, and to bring about by peaceful means, and in conformity with the principles of justice and international law, adjustment or settlement of international disputes or situations which might lead to a breach of the peace and also to achieve international co-operation in solving international problems of an economic, social, cultural, or humanitarian character, and in promoting and encouraging respect for human rights and for fundamental freedoms for all without distinction as to race, sex, language, or religion [1, Ch. 1].

It also should be pointed out that the Charter of the United Nations is based on The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which declares that everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person. Moreover, all are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to equal protection of the law. All are entitled to equal protection against any discrimination in violation of this Declaration and against any incitement to such discrimination [2, Art. 3, 7].

The United Nations Peacekeeping Forces are employed by the World Organization to maintain or re-establish peace in an area of armed conflict. The UN acts as an impartial third party in order to prepare the ground for a settlement of the issues that have provoked armed conflict. If it proves impossible to achieve a peaceful settlement, the presence of UN forces may contribute to reducing the level of conflict. The Peacekeeping Forces are subordinate to the leadership of the United Nations. We distinguish between two kinds of peacekeeping operations – unarmed observer groups and lightly-armed military forces. The latter are only allowed to employ their weapons for self-defence. Altogether, 14 UN operations have been carried out. They are evenly divided between observer groups and military forces. The observer groups are concerned with gathering information for the UN about actual conditions prevailing in an area, e.g., as to whether both parties adhere to an armistice agreement. The military forces are entrusted with more extended tasks, such as keeping the parties to a conflict apart and maintaining order in an area. UN interventions have been in particular demand in the Middle East, both as regards observer groups and military forces. The UN first took on the task of sending observers to monitor the armistice between Israel and the Arab states in 1948. The most extensive UN operation in the Middle East is represented by the formation of UNIFIL, subsequent upon the Israeli invasion of Lebanon in 1978. Its tasks included watching over the Israeli withdrawal, maintaining conditions of peace and security, and helping the Lebanese government re-establish its authority. Such tasks have taxed the capabilities of UNIFIL to the utmost, but the UN forces have made an

important contribution by reducing the level of conflict in the area. However, this achievement has not come without significant cost.

The most acute military conflict in the modern world is the war in Syria. All countries of the world render active military and humanitarian assistance to the Syrian people. Moreover, in Geneva, under the auspices of the UN, there are inter-Syrian negotiations on a political settlement, and as Staffan de Mistura, who served as Special Envoy for the past four years and four months, said, successes in the Syrian direction were achieved largely thanks to UN mediation. Thanks to international efforts led by the United Nations, the potential of ISIS in the area of planning attacks, attracting foreign fighters and financing was noticeably weakened.

In modern society people shouldn't fight for the peace with the arm in their hands. But people of our country continue war, because we have no choice, we must protect ourselves. Better die standing than live kneeling. I think that to solve our conflict and stop the war the heads must appeal to each other directly and start productive negotiations, but even the United Nations doesn't have enough influence on our opponents and stop war. However, much attention should be paid that United Nations in conjunction with other organizations, such as the Red Cross, provides food, drinking water, shelter and other humanitarian services to inhabitants suffering from famine and displaced by our civil conflict.

To sum up, speaking about the topic under consideration it should be pointed out that there is nothing worse and more terrible than war. First of all, war means death, blood, starvation, cold, diseases, destruction and children's tears. The most serious consequences of wars are human victims. Moreover, there are no winners in the war, only losers and all countries in the world should come to the conclusion that we must not use war as an instrument of policy. The United Nations with the help of modern diplomacy not should but must solve such problems or conflicts by means of negotiations and common sense.

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MODERN PROBLEMS OF YOUTH SELF-REALIZATION

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“Let your dreams be bigger than your fears, your actions louder than your words, and your faith stronger than your feelings.”

- Janina Pulido

Fear is the desire of what is feared, it is sympathetic antipathy; fear makes a person powerless, weak ... and, as you know, the first sin is always committed in weakness.

Fear is the thing which does not allow a young man to fully reveal his potential. Inexperience and vague perception of all problems gradually push young people off the right path and make them act vile and weak, thereby worsening their own position regarding the solution of the problem. This leads to a decrease in self-esteem, to self-flagellation and constant meditations before bedtime: “What if?”

The indicated problem is not the only one in the self-realization of youth. Lack of motivation completely cuts off the desire to achieve any goals. In my opinion, the whole point is in the wrong perception of values.

The Russian mentality in many respects forms our system of values and viewpoints on life. It is the peculiarity of our mentality that often prevents us from

fully revealing ourselves and 100% realizing all our goals. The Russians, as you know, are not amenable to domination under them and are reluctant to obey both of them.

S.L. Frank writes that "the Russian spirit is thoroughly saturated with religiousness." A similar opinion is shared by the philosopher, historian L.P. Karsavin, noting that religiousness is an essential aspect of the Russian spirit, however, Russian orthodoxy has a serious drawback - passivity, inaction.

A.P. Chekhov said that "nature has invested in the Russian man an extraordinary ability to believe, a testing mind and the gift of thinking, but all this are shattered in the dust of carelessness, laziness and dreamy frivolity."

Passivity and the "gift" to blindly believe in a brighter future that is the serious flaw in our mentality. It inhibits the development and self-realization of youth. Exactly Russian mentality does not allow a person to stand out in society, to feel in special way. But there is another point of view: our worldview is too narrow, so everything that does not meet our standards is subjected to harsh criticism and insults from society. As A.I. Solzhenitsyn has noted, "uniform methodicality, perseverance, internal discipline — the Russian character is most painfully lacking properties, this may be our main vice." Therefore, you should overcome the narrow horizons of ideas about life and move on, go until the environment begins to admire you.

You should stop waiting, hoping that everything you need will be presented on a silver plate. You need to believe in yourself, in your own strength. It is extremely difficult to re-educate yourself; not everyone can do it, since it requires solving numerous problems. Similarly, a conservative society is dragging the future outlook, which is difficult to change because it is mostly often closed to something new, which creates a problem.

Our goals should become more pragmatic, so as not to give in to temptations and, without slowing down, rush to our ideas and desires. What does religion respond to? - "There is God's will for everything!" Or "Your Creator himself determined the way for you." Nonsense! Religion lost own strength in the twentieth century, and today the financier when faced with a professional problem, does not go to the Holy

Father for advice because he solves everything by scientific methods. This is by no means a surge of atheism: I'm just trying to say that only a rational beginning and a pragmatic approach can give the desired result. This is undoubtedly a problem. One of the options for its solution is presented in the book of the American futurologist Jacques Fresco "Designing the Future." The author fully describes all the basic aspects of building the futurity, focuses on the proper prioritization, analyzes the mistakes of the past and gives detailed instructions on how to prevent them in the future. As Dave Shepell said, "Modern problems require modern solutions".

Do not forget that everything in this world is relative, what is savagery for one is the norm for another. So it is in our case. You should not be sceptical with reference to my thought, but you should pay attention to what is happening in our world: the terroristic attack in New Zealand, the civil war in Ukraine, the new "cold war" between the United States and Russia, the personnel crisis among specialists in public administration. The problem has remained unsolved so far.

PACKAGING MARKET: FROM RESEARCH TO SUCCESS.

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Introduction. Packaging is an unmistakable symbol of today's market. From point of view impact on the buyer, it is beyond competition among other way of promoting the goods. It allows you to sell goods much more expensive, without changing anything in it. Beautiful bright packaging is associated with receiving positive emotions, waiting better product quality.

Analysis of the packaging market: Based on the results of 2018, about 225 million tons of tare products were consumed in the world, while in 2000 the size of

consumption was 150 million tons. The largest consumer is China, whose packaging market in 2015 amounted to 68 million tons; The Russian market size in the same year was estimated at 4.6 million tons. By 2030, predicted an increase in market sizes for 30%

1. Packaging functions: Nowadays, packaging is presented mainly with requirements that make it easier to using the goods, ensure maximum economy of the packaging process, during transportation, storage, as well as moving in stores.

In order to help the sales of products, packaging must do next functions:

Localization function. The main goal: moving goods from one place to another, make it possible for pass the product to through the distribution system. As a result, the product gains the ability to be effectively delivered to the place of the trade transaction, allowing customers to purchase it where it is most comfortable for them.

Protective function. Protecting the product from the environment is the broadest packaging function. The product must not have physical damage or even look damaged. In other words, the packaging is actually between the product and the environment.

Ensuring product usability. This role of packaging is particularly multifaceted and need to meet the demand of consumer needs, i.e. packaging should maximize and most specifically provide useful services to the person using this product. The package should be designed for an unprepared consumer and should be understandable even without detailed instructions on how it works.

Informative function. Packaging should have all the necessary information. Packaging - should inform the buyer about the features of the product what the product is and how to use it. It should contain a list of ingredients, instructions for use, instructions on how to store the product.

Reuse packaging. Its return after use to industrial enterprises, clearing from contaminants and filling with the same product makes it possible to effective savings

packaging materials. The most typical example - is bottles that are reassembled and refilled.

Recycling used packaging. In order to restore natural resources through the collection and use of recycled materials. For example, the re-melting of aluminum cans to produce aluminum for the production of new cans, the recycling of waste paper to produce “recycled” packaging paper.

Disposal of unnecessary packaging residues. Most packaging materials - paper, cardboard and plastics are good combustible materials and are suitable for burning. If burning is not available, disposing of these packaging residues can be a big problem. Therefore, one of the most important areas for improving packaging - will be to reduce the use of packaging materials.

Marketing function. It shows the technical and economic indicators of packaging, as well as the requirements for saving usable space during transportation, storage and sales, the marketing function dictates the requirements for providing an advertising space, space for the necessary information, as well as requirements for the identification elements and also for individual packaging features.

2. Analysis of the impact of packaging: Often people spend on the value of the goods in just a few seconds. In such conditions, cute packaging is the key to a high level of sales.

And now a question for the audience: “What do you think, how long does the first impression of product take?”

According to Business Insider, creating a first impression of a product takes about 7 seconds. Right packaging helps the buyer find the product he needs. Helps build long-term customer relationships. Often, a person just needs to see the logo of his favorite brand to make a choice. The original packaging can attract human attention. Research show: consumers who make choices based on packaging, at least in a third of cases, make decisions based on their own taste.

Effective packaging can profit the company even after the sale of goods. About 90% of consumers reuse boxes and packages. Representatives of the business, in turn, argue: by giving due attention to packaging, a company can increase interest in its products by 30%.

Packaging trends. Design is a reflection of the development of society, packaging is what “catches” the buyer when he first sees a product on a supermarket shelf. It is very important at this moment to guess the thoughts and moods of the buyer.

Today, there are 5 main visual directions in packaging: Nature. Natural motives in packaging design are relevant now. Complex shapes, textures, watercolor illustrations in combination with a “clean” background - this is how we perceive nature today.

Vintage. Vintage is nostalgia for the times when everything was simpler, the world was larger, and the ingredients from which the product was made were written in clear words.

Less. This direction is a continuation of minimalism, but not pure minimalism tending to zero. This is a modified and improved version, premium quality, gloss, glamor.

Innocence - Childhood - Naivety. Each of us wants to return to childhood. Characteristic differences are the use of handwritten "children's" fonts, simple color ornaments and simplified illustrations. This style returns us the warmth and delight of children's perception.

Individuality. This style is born of minimalism, but as in the case of the LESS style, it is brought to the absolute. This style is beyond trends and times, when you do not need to be the best, you can just be yourself.

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF EDUCATION IN THE UIS COUNTRIES AND ABROAD

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Statement of the problem in general. The problem of illiteracy of the population is affected in many countries of the world. In our time, about a billion people are still unable to read and write. Such condition of education hinders the development of the cities, countries and the world as a whole in such spheres as: economic, scientific, informational, medical and so on.

Many specialists who have acquired their knowledge in highly developed countries do not seek to return home, exacerbating the problem of the educational gap in society.

The aim of the study is to consider the main problems of education in the UIS countries, the advantages and difficulties of education abroad.

Presentation of the materials of the main study. Today, every conscious student can identify the main shortcomings in the education system of his country.

The main problems of education in the CIS countries are:

- non-compliance of the provided material with modern requirements;
- low funding;
- weak practical orientation;
- corruption;
- gap in educational levels.

The organization of academic activities in modern Russia is largely inherited from the Soviet educational system. However, the world is developing and the introduction of innovative technologies into the educational process, equipping educational institutions with computers and modern technology, is an integral part of modern education. Theoretical training of students should not be based on simple memorization of information, but on its understanding, ability to put into practice.

Secondly, educational institutions of the UIS countries at all levels face such constant problem as the lack of funding. This negatively affects the level of salaries of workers in this area and every year this problem becomes only more acute.

Corruption is also an important issue in education. It includes such things, as: the theft of budgetary funds, bribes, the sales of diplomas, and the production of fake educational documents. Many laws are being taken against corruption, but whether they work is a difficult issue because the corruption begins with the constant collection of money from the parents of schoolchildren for the things that the state should provide.

The main levels of education in the UIS are pre-school, school and higher education. Preschool education is a poorly organized system that does not provide the necessary amount of knowledge, which should lay a certain foundation for further education in school. Often, training for preschoolers is done by people who have not received a pedagogical education. Also, at the moment, the school leaver does not receive the amount of knowledge that is required to pass the state exam and enter the university. High school students have to turn to paid tutors.

At the same time, education abroad is also complicated for the citizens of the UIS countries [1].

One of the most important problems of studying abroad is the high cost of studying. The provided benefits, grants, scholarships help students a lot, but this does not mean that serious expenses will not be required.

Also, several other important problems are the language barrier, the documentation procedure, and the choice of institution itself.

The main advantages that remain determining factors in choosing a study abroad are as follows:

- high level of training;
- flexible selection of choice and a variety of specialties;
- affordable internships and career prospects;
- practical focus on obtaining knowledge.

In high school, students can create their own curriculum and prepare for admission in advance. You can study programming, statistics, doing business, painting and much more: the child has everything to try his hand at a variety of activities. For example, students at the British Lincoln Academy conduct marine research, work on digital media, and create engineering projects. Even after entering a university, you can change your specialty at any year of study - or just listen to the most interesting courses at neighboring faculties.

The best schools and universities in the world work are in the USA, Europe and some Asian countries. Diplomas from most Ukrainian universities have little to say to a foreign employer - unlike the Sorbonne, Cambridge or MIT diplomas. There are also lesser-known educational institutions with an excellent reputation: Louisiana State University has the best financial audit and oil industry courses in the world, and University of Massachusetts Boston is one of the top business schools. Private schools attract the best teachers: in St. Johnsbury Academy, about 70% of teachers have degrees at Brown, Harvard, Dartmouth, and Johns Hopkins.

Foreign universities cooperate with leading world companies: from Washington State University you can go on an internship at Boeing, Microsoft and Amazon.com, and from Goldsmiths University of London - at Yahoo! and the BBC. Students at Les Roches receive an average of 3 internship invitations per semester,

and after graduation they easily find work in the best companies in the industry. Graduates of the Italian Polimoda Institute in 88% of cases find work within six months after graduation, including Dior, Cavalli and Giorgio Armani.

Conclusion. In the Donetsk People's Republic (hereinafter referred to as the “DPR”), various measures are being taken to develop the sphere of education. The whole system is in the process development. In order to improve the quality of education in the Republic, it is proposed: to pay more attention to legislation in the field of education (conducting educational reforms), to allocate more funds to solve the problem of underfunding of this area, to eradicate corruption, to move from outdated forms of presenting material to modern ones, and to increase the practical application of the theory, create a harmonious and interconnected system of education from preschool to higher education. Only if the abovementioned tasks are fulfilled, a holistic development of the sphere of education in the DPR is possible.

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THE IMPACT OF STRESS ON THE STUDENTS PRODUCTIVITY

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Problem. The students` educational process is one of the most intellectually and emotionally tense types of activity which can be the reason of stress emergence.

Stress often is the cause of the behavioral, emotional, cognitive, motivational spheres violation. In this case it becomes necessary producing the ways of overcoming stress that in its turn ensure student's educational productivity and stable emotional state.

Goal of research is to consider the concept of stress, giving its characteristics and finding the ways of problem salvation.

Research results According to G. Selie the stress essence lies on a state of mental tense which arises inside person due to difficult and unusual events [1]. So stress is the body's reaction to any change that requires physical, mental and emotional responses. Stress can have a harmful and beneficial effect, which helps to divide stress into two groups: distress and eustress. However, the article touches the negative side of the stress and considers its influence on students.

According to the World Health Organization, about 45% of all diseases arise due to stressful situations, which confirms the urgency of this problem. That is why it's extremely important to identify the symptoms, which are divided into 3 types: physiological, psychological and behavioral. These types are depicted in the Picture 1.

Picture 1. Types of negative stress influence

As a result of stress physiological symptoms, such as headache, nausea, loss of appetite or sleep, can most often be signals of an imbalance in the body. A sharp change in behavior, for example, avoiding communication with others, a significant increase in cigarettes smoked or alcohol taken, can also point on stress existence. Cognitive (psychological) symptoms such as decreased attention and memory, the inability to think creatively and make decisions, can be a potential threat to the safety of activities.

The stages of stress are classified into 3 types: stage of anxiety, stage of resistance and stage of exhaustion.

The first is the stage of anxiety. On this stage a person isn't able to control his own actions and thoughts. The behavior changes and becomes the opposite of that which is usually characteristic of the person. The stage of resistance includes body response which increases in such a way that a person can make a decision and cope with the situation that has happened. And the last stage is the stage of exhaustion which leads to internal organ damaging.

According to the recent K. V. Sudakova's survey some causes of stress have been identified [3, C.130]:

lack of sleep which appears during an examination period due to Poor academic performance in some university subjects, incomplete laboratory work and homework, missing classes and lack of full knowledge of any subject;

unsatisfactory living and studying conditions which are complemented with conflicts with other students, teachers or relative;

too much training load. Most often students who want to study well face this problem, but find it difficult given the memorization or analysis of any information. That is way they spend too much on doing homework sacrificing sleep or a good rest;

lack of interest in academic disciplines and chosen profession.

So negative stress consequences are damaging personalities and social lives, make students more sedentary, reserved and nervous. That is why it is necessary to give some particular recommendations to cope with educational stress:

students should learn how to manage their time and accustom themselves to self-discipline. The ability to plan and competently dispense strength will help to keep up with studies and find time for a good rest;

take daily walks in the fresh air, go in for sports that derives stress hormones from a body; sleep at least 8 hours a day. Leading healthy lifestyle reduce stress in a half;

communicate with friends or relatives in free time;

look for positive points in any situation, because positive attitude people easier cope with stressful situations and live much more longer and healthier then negative-minded people.

Conclusions. In conclusion the research demonstrates that the quality of the life is largely dependent from the person, so stress can still be avoided. However, everyone needs to make efforts for this in order to ensure the life full of joy and pleasant memories.

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PLASTIC POLLUTION: A GLOBAL PROBLEM WITH LOCAL SOLUTIONS

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Plastic pollution has become one of the most pressing environmental issues, as rapidly increasing production of disposable plastic products overwhelms the world's ability to deal with them. Plastic pollution is most visible in developing countries, where garbage collection systems are often inefficient or non-existent. But the developed world, especially in countries with low recycling rates, also has trouble properly collecting discarded plastics. Plastic trash has become so ubiquitous it has prompted efforts to write a global treaty negotiated by the United Nations.

Plastic pollution affects land, waterways and oceans. Scientists estimate that 8 million tons of plastic garbage gets into the oceans every year. In general, plastic debris exacerbates the environmental problems of the water shell of our planet.

Plastics in the oceans usually decompose within a year, but not completely. Toxic chemicals can get into the water from some plastics, intoxicating it. In 2014, it was estimated that there are about 270 million tons of plastic waste in the oceans. Plastic products make up 85 % of all debris in the oceans. About half of these plastic products are disposable.

Oceanologists predict that this year the amount of plastic waste entering the world's oceans may increase from 8 to 9 million tons. Experts urge countries and international organizations to devote more efforts to combating environmental pollution.

Garbage dumps located near the oceans contribute to the formation of garbage in the ocean because it can be easily swept away and transported to the sea.

In the Pacific Ocean there are two mass clusters: the western garbage site and the eastern garbage site. The first one is off the coast of Japan, the second is between Hawaii and California. These sites contain 100 million tons of garbage.

As a result of pollution, living organisms, especially marine animals, can be damaged either by mechanical effects such as obfuscating or ingestion of plastic objects, or by exposure to chemicals in plastics that poison them. It is estimated that about 267 different species of animals have suffered from obfuscation and swallowing of plastic debris and more than 400,000 marine mammals are killed each year due to plastic pollution in the oceans.

You may be shocked to learn that less than 50% of the 480 billion plastic bottles sold in 2018 were collected for recycling. This means that in excess of 240 billion plastic bottles became plastic waste and began polluting our already fragile ecosystem. This is a global problem on an enormous scale and is causing irreversible damage to our planet [1].

In November 2018, Greenpeace experts and volunteers studied how much the coasts of the Black and Azov Seas are polluted with plastic waste. On eight hundred-meter sections of beaches, they found 13 thousand plastic fragments with a total weight of almost half a ton. The main pollutant of the Black Sea coast turned out to be styrofoam, and the Azov Sea - drink bottles and their parts [2].

Efforts are being made to reduce the use of plastics and to promote its recycling. Some supermarkets charge customers for plastic bags, and in some places more efficient reusable or biodegradable materials are used instead of plastics. Some communities and businesses have banned certain commonly used plastic items, such as bottled water and plastic bags.

Since 2021, the EU countries will prohibit the production and sale of disposable plastic products on their territories. Plastic cutlery, ear sticks, cocktail tubes will be banned.

The new law also contains requirements for EU countries to limit the use of plastic products that do not yet have an alternative. The relevant measures of the state should be developed independently.

The Russian authorities so far only promise to consider the possibility of adopting such a law. At the end of March 2019, Russian Prime Minister Dmitry Medvedev allowed the consideration of the issue of the refusal of disposable plastic utensils at the legislative level, "otherwise it cannot be regulated." He emphasized that the production of plastic items can be a profitable business, but this is "harmful to nature." In May 2019, the head of the Ministry of Natural Resources Dmitry Kobytkin announced that a ban on the sale of disposable plastic utensils was being prepared in Russia. But the authorities have not yet taken any concrete actions in this direction [3].

Thus, the solution of the plastic pollution problem is to prevent plastic waste from entering rivers and seas in the first place. This could be accomplished with improved waste management systems and recycling, better product design that takes into account the short life of disposable packaging, and reduction in manufacturing of unnecessary single-use plastics.

What then each of us can do to contribute to the solution of this global problem?

Try not to use things with a short life cycle. Moreover, today almost all of the disposable plastic items have reusable alternatives. Buy fewer things which after usage immediately are thrown in the dustbin: single-use dishes, towels and napkins. Choose products in packaging from environmentally friendly materials: paper, glass, and textile.

The life of one plastic bag is about 12 minutes. At the same time, such packages do not decompose, and their effect on the ecosystem is growing every day. If you want to help the planet, get some reusable cotton bags for shopping.

Do not buy water in plastic bottles and use reusable stainless steel bottles or other reusable materials instead.

If you can't imagine your morning without coffee to go, come to coffee houses with your own thermo mug. If you are in a hurry, but you have forgotten to take a thermo mug when buying coffee to go, refuse at least a plastic lid and a spoon.

Thus, being aware of the importance of personal contribution to solving this problem, taking concrete steps to prevent plastic pollution, we can help the planet become cleaner and healthier.

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THE APPROACH OF YOUNG PEOPLE TO POLITICS

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In the modern world there are so many treats, geopolitical conflicts, that can't be solved without establishing an international dialogue. Young people play a special role in this matter. Young people are the future of any country. Their

innovative, fresh views on existing problems, the vision of how to solve them plays an important role in the formation and implementation of global politics.

Over the past 10 years, a new wave of rallies and opposition protests has flared up in Russia, where the main crowd consists of young people. Since 2011, observers have noted that exactly young people are characterized by higher civic engagement and more active participation in political protests. But is it good and what are the true drives of young people?

As a recent study by a group of Russian scientists showed, a large mass of young people remains non-political. A slightly smaller part attends rallies only because being in protest is status and fashionable.

It is no secret that modern youth is very different from the previous generation. This difference is reflected in political views. Why, in our time, do young people have such liberal views?

I think one of the reasons is the way we get information. According to surveys, exactly the Internet (and not TV) is the main source of information for 70% of young people and only for 10% of respondents in the older age group. Where else, if not on the Internet, can we stumble upon active propaganda of pro-liberal subcultures and movements? More than 70% identify with a certain group: feminists, anarchists, etc.

Another reason is age. teens, going to rallies, do not fully understand all aspects of politics. but youthful high spirits and the effect of the crowd sometimes makes them take very risky, unjustified and rash acts.

The best example here is radicalism. Radicalism is an extreme, uncompromising adherence to any views. Most often it leads to cruelty and violence, especially at political rallies. for me, justifying radical actions is just as stupid as religious wars. Violence never has excuses and good causes.

But there are also other social youth movements that are aimed not at making a loud statement about oneself through a protest, but at really useful social work. For

example, the all-Russian social movement “Victory Volunteers” holds national and international events, takes care of veterans, helps in the improvement of memorial sites and popularizes modern achievements of Russia with the help of interesting formats. In my opinion, the number of such movements should be increased. They contribute to the development of the correct political position and views of young people.

Another example of the social activity of youth can be given from the events in Ukraine in 2014. Thousands of young people organized protests. They wanted the country to join the European Union, not understanding completely the consequences and negative aspects. During this period, extremist activity was the cruelest. Hundreds of people were injured or even killed, buildings were destroyed, the political situation was aggravated. A crowd of young people who were not aware of their actions and consequences was capable of terrible things. Can such youth be the future of the state? I don't think so.

So, to sum up, after analyzing the attitude of young people to modern politics, I can highlight several points that can help change negative trends for the better.

Firstly, the government should pay more attention to the education of children both in the global economy and in the internal political affairs. I think that now insufficient attention has been paid to this question, that's why children without sufficient knowledge go to rash meetings.

Secondly, nowadays we need new, innovative methods of attracting youth to socially conscious organizations. It will help to create a sense of national purpose and patriotism in any country.

THE MODERN WORLD THROUGH THE EYES OF YOUTH

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Youth is not only the future, it is a “living present”, and it is important to understand how much today the young generation determines the content and nature of the future, how much it carries the “spirit of the new time”.

The problems of modern youth in our time are becoming increasingly relevant. Throughout the world, and in Russia, in particular, among young people, priorities are changing. Instead of being kind, honest and obedient, thinking about the family, our younger generation increasingly wants to stand out due to addictions, violence and superiority. Therefore, adults have a difficult task - to instill goodness and humanity in adolescents in order to avoid subsequent problems of youth in modern society and society.

Today in Russia about 27% of the youth of the total population. It includes young people 14-35 years old. At the moment, Russian youth is increasingly seeking higher education, because this increases the likelihood of good employment. But, oddly enough, there are downsides to this. Young people with higher education emigrate to Western countries, believing that the standard of living there is higher than in Russia. Despite these criteria and the youth unemployment rate is also high - about 6%.

In our adult-run world, youth aren't often asked for their opinions and ideas on how to address society's greatest challenges. Yet a collective effort to reverse this trend is one of the most powerful steps we can take towards a tangibly better world. Here's why:

- 1) Youth want to make a difference

Young people have an acute sense of justice when it comes to society's issues. Looking at the world with fresh eyes, they see its problems as moral wrongs that can and should be righted. There is no reason in their minds why change isn't possible now, so they are eager to get involved – both by contributing to grassroots efforts and joining the search for long-term solutions.

2) Youth are creative

The fresh perspective young people bring to the world gives them a unique ability to think up creative solutions. Unconstrained by deep-rooted societal norms, youth can come up with ideas that would not have crossed the minds of more world-weary adults. These solutions may not always be practical, but they can uncover hidden assumptions and opportunities that illuminate new pathways forward.

3) Youth have an important perspective

Many of today's greatest social issues have a particular impact on young people. Given their typical roles as students and care-receivers, youth often experience issues like gender inequality and violence much differently than adults. This perspective is critical to incorporate in the solution to any social problem, because it reveals new dimensions of each issue and suggests opportunities for innovation.

4) Changemaking develops effective, optimistic future leaders

When young people contribute their ideas and energy to addressing social issues, they begin to see themselves as capable leaders who can make important contributions to the lives of others. Youth who might otherwise feel academically or socially inferior to their peers realize that their unique strengths are needed to build a better world. The empowering effects of changemaking spill over into adulthood, as youth retain their motivation to help others and pursue their goals with confidence. Young people are a limitless source of innovative energy, and engaging them now will inspire a generation of lifelong changemakers. So why don't we invite them to join the team today? Let's encourage youth to start their own social ventures and give

them the support they need to be successful. And perhaps more importantly, let's invite them to the decision-making table where their voices will truly be heard. Young people deserve the chance to explore and address the problems they see around them – and their contribution is an opportunity the world can't afford to miss.

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THE PROBLEM OF ORPHANS

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Family is the main value in the life of any person. The problem of abandoned children, or orphans, is an acute problem for modern society.

UNICEF and global partners define an orphan as a child under 18 years of age who has lost one or both parents to any cause or death. By this definition, there were nearly 140 million orphans globally in 2015, including 61 million in Asia, 52 million in Africa, 10 million in Latin America and the Caribbean, and 7.3 million in Eastern Europe and Central Asia. This large figure represents not only children who have lost both parents, but also those who have lost a father but have a surviving mother or have lost their mother but have a surviving father.

It is an undeniable fact that the presence of a mother and a father in the family plays an important role in children's mental, emotional, behavioral, physical, social and psychological development process. Every child needs their parents' love, care

and attention to ensure their healthy development. It is a tragic situation when a child loses both parents, because the challenges that he or she will face will be much greater compared to other children. The risks are even more for social orphans because they understand that they are being abandoned, and this will pose serious risks if not taken care of seriously.

Children and adolescents have always been an important focus of study for mental health researchers. Studies have highlighted emotional problems such as depression, anxiety, and difficulties in social interaction as well as behavioral problems such as hyperactivity and conduct problems in them.

Studies have shown that the prevalence of emotional and behavioral problems among children and adolescents brought up in institutional homes is higher as compared to similarly aged youngsters brought up by their own families.

Emotional and behavioral problems are more frequent among orphans and other vulnerable children because they are exposed to abuse, exploitation, negligence, lack of love and care of parents. They are also more likely to be emotionally needy, insecure, and poor. In addition to these factors, most of them are brought up in institutional homes where individual care is inadequate.

To solve this problem it is necessary to take the following measures:

The government and the society should help potential social orphan hood families and prevent them from giving their children up. But for existing orphans, the steps that should be taken include:

Let orphans know that they are not alone;

Let orphans realize their value and importance;

Orphans' self-esteem should be maintained to prevent inferiority complex and negative feelings;

Listen to orphans to understand their problems;

The government and legal institutions should protect orphans and their rights;

Orphans should be provided with good role models;

The right of education and career of orphans must be protected;

Doctors and psychologists must be made available to address orphans' psychical and psychological problems;

The government should provide orphans with economic support and scholarships to prevent them from becoming child laborers;

The laws to protect and supervise orphans' right should be made and implemented.

Every child is a beacon of hope whether they are orphans or not. And every child, orphan or not, needs exactly the same love, care and attention to safeguard their healthy development. The future is in their hands, whether they are orphans or not. So it is up to this generation to decide what kind of people will inherit this world when we are gone: those who are loved enough, or those who were deprived of it.

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YOUTH ISSUES

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The article is headlined Youth Issues. It talks about what are the problems of modern youth.

Youth is a wonderful time. We begin to live in this period of life. After all, we break out from under the cosy wing of parents and go on a free voyage at this moment. We're not as safe as we used to be. Now we face the first problems, we make many mistakes in this wonderful period of life.

All human life is formed at this time. Beliefs and morality, health and bad habits, hobbies and education - all this happen in youth. Youth is a period of life when youth is trying to find their place, a cell in society.

This time is always associated with the problems of young people when they struggle to adapt to society. Young people are faced with difficult decisions that they can make in modern society. The younger generation faces a number of challenges. These are the eternal problems of money and independence from parents, the problem of choosing a profession and getting an education for this profession, the problem of youth unemployment and the constant gap between generations. Often young people suffer from personal problems of an emotional nature, which may seem unimportant and even stupid in the eyes of adults, but they are extremely important for the young people themselves. This is the problem of making friends, the problem of first love, that is, the problem of developing relations between people.

An important issue for young people is a career choice, which is really difficult. The problem of choosing a profession of modern youth at the moment is known to many, everyone at a certain age met her face to face. Many, faced with the need to choose a profession, are very worried, because it is terrible to take

responsibility for your actions. Of course, young people try to rely on their interests, but they change, and the profession will remain with them forever. Unfortunately, there are parents who believe that they themselves have an idea about your future career and in most cases try to force or solve everything without the consent of their own child. And most often the child does not want to do as his parents decided. The choice of profession is an important and serious step in the life of every person, and that it was correct, it is necessary to analyze many aspects: demand in the labour market, the financial costs of education, their abilities, but, in any case, this choice should be independent and deliberate.

Another youth problem is unemployment. The transition from study to work is an important stage of human development. The transition of young people to economic independence is becoming more difficult and protracted. Unemployment among young people during this period is not a trifle at all; it has consequences for the health and well-being in the future for young people. To solve this problem, young people need to strive for higher education. Then they will be well trained for the skilled workforce that industrialized societies need.

There is another problem that almost all young people face today - this is the tension that arises between parents and children. Parents condemn their children for following a modern, sometimes challenging fashion, living according to the "new" rules. Children refuse to accept the "old" values, do not understand the care, concern on the part of parents. You can't blame anyone. That's the price of progress. Undoubtedly, the older and younger generation cannot have the same views on life and interests. Because of their age and life experience, adults have a different view of the world than the younger generation. But this should not become a barrier between generations. After all, children and parents are the closest people in the world. That's why we have to protect our parents.

Quite often, young people are forced or forced to take part in these antisocial activities of their age category. They go towards drugs, crime, alcoholism, vandalism, etc. Thus, they fill their feelings, rebelling against society and adults.

The next problem is the problem of friendship. Friendship is an integral part of life and is valued quite highly for most young people. Young people are ready to help their friends, protect them, enjoy their success. The next problem is the problem of love and dating. Many parents give their children freedom of communication, but there are those who want to protect their children too much, which prevents them from dating the opposite sex and sometimes even communicating with them. It is in this way that this leads to many psychological problems since they prevent their children from gaining experience in communicating with members of the opposite sex.

Parents, on the contrary, need to help their children to solve these problems together. We must understand that it is young people who are the ones who conquer this world.

Now we see that in the lives of young people there are still quite a few problems. Nevertheless, in life there are wonderful moments that can happen in youth. So we recommend you enjoy this wonderful time!

ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS FROM THE POINT OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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The Earth is the only planet in the solar system where life is. If you look down at the Earth from a plane you will see how wonderful our planet is. You will see blue seas and oceans, rivers and lakes, high snow-capped mountains, green forests and fields. For centuries man lived in harmony with nature until industrialization brought human society into conflict with the natural environment.

Today, the contradictions between man and nature have acquired a dramatic character. Every year the world's industry pollutes the atmosphere with millions of tons of dust and other harmful substances. The seas and rivers are poisoned with industrial waste, chemical and sewage discharge. People who live in big cities are badly affected by harmful discharge from plants and city transport and by the increasing noise level which is as bad for human health as lack of fresh air and clean water.

Among the most urgent problems are the ozone layer, acid rains, global warming, toxic pollution of atmosphere, disappearance of forests, contamination of underground waters by chemical elements, destruction of soil in some areas, threat to some flora and fauna representatives, etc.

One of the most important problems is the pollution oceans. Many ships sail in the ocean water- fishing ships, some ships carrying people, some are carrying oil. If a ship loses some of the oil in the water, or waste from the ships it puts into the ocean, the water becomes dirty. Many sea birds die because of the polluted water. Many fish are dying in the sea, others are getting contaminated. Fishermen catch contaminated fish which may be sold in markets, and people may get sick from eating them. Lakes and rivers are becoming polluted, too. Some beaches are dangerous for swimming.

Another important problem is air pollution. Cars and factories pollute the air we use. Their fume also destroys the ozone layer which protects the Earth from the dangerous light of the Sun. Aerosols create large "holes" in the ozone layer round the Earth. Burning coal and oil leads to global warming which may bring about a change in the world's climate.

The other problem is that our forests are dying from acid rains. Deforestation, especially destruction of tropical forests, affects the balance of nature in many ways. It kills animals, changes the climate and ecosystem in the world.

A person can do some damage to the environment but the greater part of pollution certainly comes from industry. Modern industry production is the main threat to nature.

There are a lot of places on our planet that need immediate help. Our country is not exception. The nuclear accident at Chernobyl, which took place on April 26, 1986., has seriously aggravated the ecological situation in our region too. That catastrophe can be considered as the largest disaster of the 20th century. The level of thyroid gland cancer has increased, the immunity of children and women is weakened, many diseases appear out only a few years later. Everyone understands that this catastrophe is a threat to health of our nation, and though years have already passed, the results will be shown on the future generations.

I'd like to say a few words about animals in danger of extinction. The blue whale is the largest animal which has ever lived. Once there were over 200000 of these creatures living in the Atlantic and Pacific oceans. Since the seventeenth century they have been hunted for their oil and meat. In fact, so many of them were killed that by 1963 their population had been reduced to just 1000. Today it is even less than that. The African elephant is the world's largest land animal. Today there are fewer than one million of these animals left. Even though they are now protected, they are still being hunted because of their tusks, which are used to make ornaments and jewellery. There is only one way to save wild animals and wild habitats – conservation. That means protecting animals in danger by law, opening more national parks, building fewer new roads, planting more new forests, cutting pollution. If we don't do that, many wild animals will soon have just one habitat- the Zoo.

The activity of many public organizations is directed to protect environment. One of the most known organizations is "Greenpeace". Due to "Greenpeace" the commercial whaling is banned.

When I look around I realize that not all people understand the importance of nature protection. On fine summer days a lot of people go out of town. They have picnics on the shores of lakes and the banks of rivers or on beautiful forest glades and

they often leave behind a lot of rubbish- plastic bags and bottles, tins and paper. It makes me feel sad when I see people returning to town with huge bunches of forest or meadow flowers. Many of these plants are included into the Red Book which contains the names of rare plants and animals. Some of them have become extinct and others are on the verge of disappearing. If we don't realize that we are all responsible for what's happening around us we will never feel secure about the future of the world we live in.

What can be done to protect nature? I offer 3-Rs rule for all young people: reduce, recycle, reuse.

1. Choose to reuse

It's not waste until you waste it! Think carefully about how you can reuse something before you throw it away. Also, if things break, try to repair them before you replace them. Have your jeans got holes in the knees? Make new shorts out of them or give them to someone who needs them. Don't throw away empty jars and bottles, rinse them out and use them to store other things.

2. Turn it down or switch it off

Always switch off the lights when you leave an empty room, and use light bulbs that save energy.

3. Be a lean, green shopping machine

Only buy what you really need and use all of it. Think about buying something new? Try the 30-day rule- only buy it if you really want it 30 days after you first saw it. At the supermarket, while buying things you do not need by writing a shopping list before you go and making sure you keep to it.

4. Put packaging on a diet

Firstly, buy things with simple packaging that can easily be recycled. Secondly, if you are preparing a packed lunch to eat at university, take a sandwich in a reusable lunchbox, juice in a reusable bottle and a banana, rather than a sandwich in

a plastic bag, or a carton of juice and biscuits which are each wrapped in silver paper and even more plastic.

5. Save on paper

Try to cut down on the amount of paper you use. Use both sides of the paper and then recycle it, don't create paper waste.

6. Get others involved

Lust but not least, encourage you friends to cut down on waste too! Swap magazines, books and clothes, send them a copy of this newsletter.

In conclusion, I believe that environment disasters can be avoided if people broaden ecological education and every person understands that the beauty of nature is extremely fragile and people must obey the unwritten laws of nature.

THE INFLUENCE OF MASS MEDIA ON STUDENTS

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The aim of this topic is to explain the young people's perception, in general, but mainly of the ones that still study in universities, namely if, and to what extent they consider the influence of the mass-media nowadays to be beneficial and helping them to better understand the environment they are acting in or, on contrary, as manipulating them.

The manipulation is a historical concept, that have been used for thousands years by the political and military leaders to use the masses for achieving their targets. At first, used in a direct way for later, closer to our present days, to be used in a more subtle way through mass-media, the manipulation stays as a

controversial topic, as it is not equally perceived by each individual. The written or the broadcasted press has a considerable input in the public opinion formation, thus becoming a pillar for transmitting the image intended by the communicator to the predilect users of the media channels. This way, mass-media becomes a favorable environment for an instant dissemination of the information towards the news consumers. The news lacking any objectiveness or the shows with a confusing way, the implicit or not strictly argued information are just a few tools used to manipulate people, both by press or TV. Another particular important factor that influences people's opinion is the Internet. The technological ascension in the past few years, has transformed the Internet into an alternative for information and interaction that is currently indispensable for all the population segments but mostly for the youth. This qualitative research measures the perception of the influence the mass-media has upon the youth, by the received answers to the grid-type closed questions that were addressed to over 100 students.

Through its conclusions, the research suggests a synthesis both of the positive and negative aspects in terms of the influence the mass-media has upon the young generation that is hungry for knowledge, leaving the right to judge and action being fully informed, right into their hands. The manipulation and control techniques that are presented in the Annex to the present paper represent a think over suggestion for its readers. The main conclusions of the current paper confirm the initial research hypothesis, namely that the mass-media is a two-blade sword for Generation Z, born on internet. On one hand, it forms, on the other hand, it diforms. It is up to us to learn how to use this tool and this study can be useful for such learning. This topic is especially actual for students nowadays because they have to find new information almost every day. All along the years, the mass-media influence increased and became more and more powerful due to the technological evolution, from telegraph, radio, newspapers and internet. Mass-media has an important role upon the education of the young people, being a more and more accessed modality of getting information, that are more or less useful to the people.

Over 50% of the youth that use social networks, do this for being in contact with their friends and just 1% use the social media for finding more about the risks they are facing if they consume alcohol and drugs. For the youth, the information found on social networks have a low reliability degree, the data resulted from the survey indicating a very low level of trust in such networks.

So we can make a conclusion: because of the technological evolution, there are more and more mass-media resources, but students usually have lower level of trust to some internet or TV resources, so people who want to know something new about the world, have to be very careful about the resource they are reading for.

YOUTH AND MASS MEDIA

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Today, we cannot imagine our lives without the media. We constantly follow the news on TV, read interesting articles in the press, communicate with friends on the Internet. Since the majority of the population are young people and they are ardent consumers of the media, and the media at the same time have an impact on the youth audience. We have also found that there is a positive and negative media impact on young people, and we increasingly now talk about the negative impact of the media, which is expressed in their inappropriate behavior in society. And in order to reduce the negative influence, we believe that it is necessary to introduce censorship, regardless of those who will not benefit from it and despite of the society in which we live.

The mass media not only reflect the processes taking place in the country, but also influence the formation of the worldview of young people, take on the

dissemination and creation of appropriate norms of behavior, social values and goals. The need for information communication with the outside world and, accordingly, in the constant flow of information, the need for entertainment and, to some extent similar to it, but not completely coinciding with it, the need for distraction (withdrawal from the daily routine and the ordinariness of the surrounding life) make young people turn to the media.

Satisfaction of the need for entertainment sometimes helps to discharge emotionally, overcome psycho-emotional tension. When realizing the need for distraction, a young person can watch TV programs, listen to radio programs or read newspapers, which are of no interest for them, but help to remain psychologically isolated from the environment.

Information transmitted through the channels of mass media, in modern conditions, becomes a "product" of the industry of consciousness, but, at the same time, is not always comprehensive and reliable. It is necessary to understand that the information, being transmitted, for example, on television, which has a great power of propaganda suggestion, undoubtedly may be one-sided or distorted. The emergence of a global and interactive communication system, the widespread penetration of mass communication and information into the lives of many strata of society give rise to new philosophical and anthropological problems.

Despite the apparent simplicity and availability of information, which a person, at first glance, quite easily manages, he sometimes, without noticing, becomes a passive object of the information world. At the same time, the normal functioning of individual communities and social organizations, from a small group to the population of the country, the state and society as a whole, depends on individuals, their interrelations and relations." The works of modern media culture reflect the social, moral and cultural processes taking place in society. This reflection projects not only the events taking place, but also the feelings and thoughts experienced by modern man. It has already become a recognized fact that with the advent of computers, the spread of satellite television, mobile telephony, etc.,

students and young people began to read less, experiencing significant difficulties in a coherent presentation of events. In addition, mass media actively form certain values and ideals of modern youth.

Speaking about influence, it is necessary to note, first of all, their information and educational role thanks to which not only "walls of apartments to borders of the planet are moved apart", but the tendency of transformation of mass media into the sphere of self-realization of the person gains force. To the long-existing correspondence of viewers with newspapers and magazines, radio and television broadcasts with direct participation of listeners and viewers were added. The development of electronic systems has given rise to a completely new kind of communication and self-realization which means the participation of a person in interaction with certain partners who are interested in him for one reason or another, which allows him to find like-minded people and express himself in communication with them.

It is possible to trace a significant contradiction in the value system of young people: on the one hand, at the level of consciousness it affirms the commitment to personal autonomy, good and stable interpersonal relations, for family creation and decent work; on the other hand, the results of factor analysis clear orientation towards western standards of living. Television in this context plays a significant role in the formation of values of young people. Since young people are culturally quite separate from the older generation, television, which uses western programs and films in its broadcasts, successfully promotes the western way of life and perception of the world.

Thus, in the process of renewal of our society, changes in the political system fundamentally change the place and role of the media. From being unconditionally subordinated to the partly bureaucratic apparatus, they have become an active and influential component of our political system, a public judge, a people's guardian of public order and justice, and an integral element of the emerging legal state.

Summing up, we can say that the influence of the media on the behavior of young people exists and it is quite significant. Young people are a social group that is very much influenced by the media. Addressing the problem of media influence on young people, it is necessary to study ways to reduce the impact of negative information. Otherwise, our new generation will form wrong values and it will be sad to look at their way of life. It is necessary, surely, to impose censorship on films with elements of violence and eroticism, on porn materials in magazines, newspapers, on TV, etc.

This problem should be solved, despite the fact that it will not be profitable for someone, and despite the fact that we live in a democratic society. A healthy lifestyle, highly realized intellectual potential, depth of good morals should characterize our young generation first of all.

GEOGRAPHY OF BRANDS

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Each of us makes purchases literally every day. When purchasing a service or product, we come across such a strange concept of a brand, a word that can describe any product. Some brands are well known and upon hearing the name we immediately understand what quality is in front of us. Some brands take money for their name, some for originality and quality, all brands are different and act on different customers. But are the same brands everywhere equally successful? All countries of the world are divided into categories - they can be divided by religion, finances and climate. Each of these factors creates a special environment due to which the leadership of the brands must either change or leave completely.

First, let's talk about the changes. We see thematic logos and interesting advertisements every day, but brands have a hard time, because what is funny and interesting to one, completely incomprehensible to others. For example:

The first Burger King restaurant appeared in the United States in 1954, after which establishments under this name began to spread around the world. However, before entering the Australian market, company leaders found that a brand with that name already exists in this country. Therefore, in Australia, a new name was invented for Burger King restaurants - Hungry Jack's.

Unilever founded the Ax brand in France in 1983, but in some countries the name has already been taken by other brands. In addition, in English-speaking countries, the direct meaning of the word "ax" ("ax") was difficult to associate with perfumery. To distribute products in the UK, Ireland, Australia, New Zealand and China, the company took the name Lynx (from the Latin. "Lynx").

The DANONE brand was founded by Spanish pharmacist Isaac Carasso. He named the brand after his son Daniel (Danone is his family nickname). Upon entering the US market, company leaders decided to make the brand name more "American" - Dannon. The Americans did not pronounce the former name correctly, dividing it into two words - "dan" and "one".

Next, we look at the statistics of large brands and the markets where they are popular [1].

According to Fortune, Google took first place in the market, ahead of Apple. Last year, the tech giant became 24% more expensive, valued at \$ 109.5 billion. But it's worth noting that Google won mainly due to the "fall" of Apple. The brand reduced its value by 26% to \$ 107.1 billion. The value of Amazon, which became the 3rd in a row in the ranking, is estimated at \$ 106.4 billion. The next largest national brand is Samsung, a South Korean conglomerate that is valued at \$ 66.2 billion, which is less than 2/3 of the value of Google. I would also like to note that in this list is the Chinese ICBC bank, whose value is \$ 47.8 billion, despite the fact that banks

are the least visible companies on the map and are represented in no more than 8 countries. Truly global, only one bank can be considered - the Spanish Santander. But there are other large banks: Royal Bank (Canada), Sberbank (Russia), Banco Itaú (Brazil); DBS Bank, QNB and KBC (Singapore). In the field of financial services, I would also like to mention the insurance giant AIA from Hong Kong.

The next block of popular brands consists of oil refineries. There are at least 7 of them in the world. The largest of these is Shell, located in the Netherlands. The brand is valued at \$ 36.8 billion. Shell is more than 3 times the size of Eni (Italy) and Petronas (Malaysia). The remaining giants in the oil and gas market are valued at no more than \$ 1 billion: PEMEX (Mexico), Statoil (Norway), PTT (Thailand) and Ecopetrol (Colombia). Moreover, each of these companies is quite large in scale to compete with any other company in the world.

The US is ahead of other countries in terms of corporate dominance in online services. But in a number of other influential countries, the most popular brands work in the field of telecommunications. Among them are Vodafone (UK), STC (Saudi Arabia) and Telstra (Australia).

According to statistics, the most recognizable brands are those that specialize in consumer products. Among them, companies operating in the automotive industry: Toyota (\$ 46.2 billion) - the most popular brand in Japan, BMW (\$ 37.1 billion) - a well-known brand in Germany, IKEA (\$ 24.1 billion) - Switzerland, Lego (\$ 7, 6 billion) - Denmark, Red Bull - (Austria). Among the equally popular Nestlé, which produces food products with an annual turnover of \$ 19.4 billion.

Emirates is the largest brand in the UAE, which is one of the most respected airlines in the world. It is worth noting the companies that are less known to the general public: Falabella, the Chilean retail giant in the clothing and home goods market, and Medtronic, the Irish health care provider.

Thus, we can make an important conclusion, as future entrepreneurs, we should all be able to analyze the market, focus on customers and changes among

popular products. But from this article it becomes clear to us that the geography of brands is an alternative way. Even the craziest or vice versa banal business ideas will find recognition in their place on the map. Create, implement your ideas and remember, your place is not where you are, but where you are ready to come.

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LAW PITFALLS IN DEATH PENALTY IMPLEMENTATION IN THE DPR

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According to the criminal legislation of different countries, every year around the world several thousand people are killed. However, at present there are a small number of states that haven't refused to use the death penalty. Since the supreme measure of punishment causes a lot of controversy in modern society, we would like to examine the historical, legal and social aspects of this issue, the peculiarities of the legislative approach and practical implementation with reference to the DPR, and also analyze the foreign experience of applying this penal institution.

We examined the issues of humanity and justice of the death penalty, gave a legal assessment of the conditions for the imposition of the death sentence in the DPR, and also analyzed the views of some scholars on the issue under consideration.

Based on the analysis, we came to the conclusion that in spite of inhumanity, the prohibition of the death penalty is inadmissible, in view of the need to have an exceptional means of protecting the population. Death penalty, or capital punishment

may be just such a form of punishment. On consideration all the aspects of the issue, the authors note that following the principle of humanism, this penalty should be applied extremely rarely, only in exceptional cases.

Death sentence is one of the ancient punishments, known to humanity, used as early as XVIII century B.C. In Juridical Sciences. The issue of capital punishment was always relevant with many researchers coming to their own conclusions. They've asked questions like: does the capital punishment actually scare potential criminals? Does it lower the amount of crimes, and can it completely abolish some of the crimes? After analyzing the origins of set type of punishment, opinions of philosophers and other scientists they came to the conclusion, that compared to primitive society modern world requires humanitarian punishment. Critics say that, capital punishment is useless because:

1. It doesn't scare criminals;
2. Demoralizes citizens;
3. Cannot be retracted;
4. Makes it impossible to rehabilitate the criminal;
5. Is incompatible with norms of modern society.

At the same time many scientists in the field of sociology claim that the mentality of "an eye for an eye" is a rising perspective among the citizens, pressuring law systems to follow the will of people.

Historically, there were many methods of applying capital punishment in Russia and the USSR. Among the most common were quartering, hanging, beheading or a shooting squad.

In 1947 due to colossal losses during the World War II the General Secretary Joseph Stalin and the communist party of the USSR implemented a moratorium on all forms of death penalty. Set moratorium existed for only three years and was abolished in January 12, 1950. The reinstated capital punishment lasted through the

rest of Soviet Union and was typically applied to spies, “enemies of the nation” rapists, mass murderers, etc.

For a short while the death penalty was renewed in Russian Federation, up until September 2nd, 1996, after which the President Boris Yeltsin implemented a new moratorium which is in act till this day.

In DPR capital punishment is in effect but hasn’t been used yet and is still considered a matter of great debate.

So what exactly is Capital punishment: a viable form of punishment or a glorified murder?

Goals of any punishment should be reformation of the criminal, restoration of justice and discouraging other people from committing a crime. While capital punishment makes the reformation impossible, it perfectly suits the other two goals. However, many people would say that the same and more can be achieved through life sentence. The problem with this approach is that criminals sentenced for life have to be fed and kept alive on taxpayers’ money and there’s no guarantee that while being kept alive they will feel any remorse. As much as we like to pretend that a life sentence is just as bad as the death penalty prisoners that got the later felt like they were “winning”. An example of this is terrorist Zacarias Moussaoui who was part of 9/11 attack and felt like a life sentence was the best possible option for him.

Of course, if we are to implement the death penalty again we may change the list of crimes it assigned for as well as set the lowest age limit for it. After all, no one is saying that we have to directly lift passages from old laws.

In conclusion, it should be noted that no matter how inhumane the death penalty is, it is inappropriate to prohibit it. The government, acting as the defender of its people, should have such an extreme means of protecting the population in its pool of punishments. Of course, the country, which is following the principle of humanism, can and should use it rarely, replacing it with life imprisonment, but in exceptional cases it is still not possible to do without the death penalty.

THE TOPICAL ISSUES OF THE YOUTHS ACTIVE LIFE DEVELOPMENT

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We live in the world of problems. Life is impossible without them. There are a lot of problems that people have to face and try to cope with. But I would like to tell about youth problems. There are a lot of them that a young person has to face when he or she stops being a child. Adults think that it is very easy to be a teenager, but this is not true. Nowadays there are a lot of different things that young people want to try. They are cigarettes, alcohol, drugs and it is not so easy to manage them, especially for teenagers. Most teenagers try such things because their friends do and if they do not, they are not considered to be cool. Some young people take drugs or drink alcohol because they are bored and they have nothing to do. Some of them do because their life is terrible and they can't manage it. To my mind, the most dangerous of youth problems are drug and alcohol addiction, AIDS and a frightening increase of the suicides among young people. Teenagers are often involved in different crimes: robbery, vandalism, drug sale. Besides, there are many other problems: poor relationship with parents, problems of friendship and love, getting education and choosing a career, youth unemployment and the problem of earning money and so on. We can name youth problems endlessly. But let's see some of their reasons and try to give advice how to solve them [1].

Smoking

You'd have to be living on Mars not to know that smoking is dangerous. Yet statistics show that young people today smoke more, not less. Why? One answer is that many teens think it cool. Another is the great sums of money invested in advertising cigarettes. Tobacco companies spend millions to encourage the young to start, or to continue, smoking.

The statistics is such:

Over 90% of all smokers start before they are 18.

The average age for a new smoker is 13.

Smoking kills about 3 million people every year.

A smoker is 22 times more likely to die of lung cancer than a non-smoker.

Smoking causes heart attacks, bronchitis, asthma and other diseases.

Nicotine is as addictive as heroin or cocaine. Seven out of 10 smokers want to quit, but can't. Nicotine isn't the only bad thing in cigarettes, there are over 400 chemicals in one cigarette that are known to be very destructive [2].

Drug Addiction

Drug addiction is the plague of our time. So many young people are addicted to drugs. The danger of drugs is a vital problem in our society. Drug addicts ruin their health and degrade morally. With every day they need more and more drugs. To get the stuff and the money for it they don't stop at any crime. They begin to steal, to rob and to burgle. In a state of ecstasy they may ever kill people. And sometimes even for a hundred rubles. It's awful, but explainable. Drugs ruin human organs and affect the brain very badly, even dramatically. Drugmen degrade mentally and don't live long. Usually they die of an overdose. So drug taking is a sure way to an early grave. Why is there such a terrible disease in our society at present? There are different causes of it: the distortion of the eternal conceptions of right and wrong, low cultural standards, social injustice. But I'm sure the root cause is some young people's inability to cope with life difficulties. That's why drug-users and alcoholics want to go away from reality and to get a state of euphoria. They don't realize that intoxicants ruin their lives and they turn into desperate good-for-nothing creatures. Sometimes teens may be involved in a bad company and they become drug addicts. So young people must have strong will-power and common sense not to give in to pals' negative influence [3].

Teenagers' Extreme is Committing Suicides

As far as I know, in recent decades the number of suicidal teens has increased. Young people can't bear the difficulties and pressures of modern life and choose the fatal end. Here are some circumstances of committing suicides: broken families, indifference of parents, the availability of drugs and alcohol and sometimes psychical disorders. Drug and alcohol abuse is tragically destructive. They ruin youngsters' health, produce insensibility, apathy, frustration. All human values lose their significance. Naturally, it may lead to crime and suicide.

To prevent the trouble parents and teachers must be more attentive and well-wishing to children, to their souls and hearts, as total negligence and excessive severity throw the young in the abyss [4].

AIDS Cases among the Young

AIDS is Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome. It is caused by a virus that weakens people so much that they become sick. The name of the virus is HIV – Human Immunodeficiency Virus. AIDS is a global epidemic. It spreads disastrously. No cure has been found as yet. Drug-users belong to the so-called high risk-group for catching AIDS. They help to spread AIDS through dirty syringes. Moreover, AIDS spreads through sexual contact, from an infected mother to her child. So AIDS is a world problem. That's why associations for combating AIDS have been founded in many countries. But I consider defence against the plague of the twentieth century depends on all of us. We must take responsibility for our actions, for our health, for our life, because after all, AIDS doesn't care about our dreams for the future [5].

The Problems of Friendship and the First Love

Young people have many problems of emotional and personal character which may look silly and unimportant in the eyes of grown-ups but appear to be extremely important to the young. They are the problems of friendship and loneliness, as well as the problem of the first love. Youth is the time when a person is vulnerable to opinions of different people, especially to the opinions of his peer

group. So for many youngsters it is very difficult to choose true friends. The proverb says: “A friend in need is a friend indeed”. I agree with it, that’s why I try to make friends with persons whom I can trust and rely on. To my mind, faithful friends are always ready to help you in difficult situations and never betray you. Another problem is the problem of love and dating. Some parents are democratic in this respect, and allow their children considerable freedom in their relations with the opposite sex. Others are overprotective and forbid their teenage children to go out with people they like. In my opinion, it can result in many psychological problems as overanxious parents prevent their children from getting an experience of communicating with representatives of the opposite sex, and this can lead to serious family problems later [6].

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STUDENT SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

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Student social responsibility mainly focuses on taking responsibility for one's own actions. It is a promise everyone should make for the society while working for the social, cultural and, ecological causes. These responsibilities are ethically binding and suggest that each person acts in such a way that minimizes the adverse effect to those around them.

For instance, most of the times you must have seen if two vehicles collide, the drivers blame each other for the mishap. By this act, they not only fail to take responsibility, but are demonstrating a character trait which is very common in people who fail to succeed in anything.

Therefore, in accepting your faults, you are accepting a willingness to develop your character. It's a little effort that brings a big difference around. The essence of the notion «responsibility». So, there are different ways by which a student can fulfill their social responsibilities while they study. Is that some of the basic steps to get you started for the revolution without disturbing your study schedule.

Students can start from preserving the environment If the rotten things bother you and you hate the resources being wasted, then surely you are on the right way. There is a quote “Charity begins at home.” This quote has been long told, but hardly practiced.

So, students can show their social responsibility by doing these basic steps :

Keeping the school or college building and surrounding neighborhood clean, picking up the litter and putting it in the trash , can be your one step as a socially responsible citizen.

Students can also keep a check on reducing energy and water consumption. Every time you leave the classroom, ensure the lights and fans are switched off.

Also, avoid leaving the tap water running.

These minor practices can help in fulfilling the social responsibilities that you owe as a student.

How to be a volunteering? Students can also consider different kinds of volunteer. And before doing this they should use themselves. Have I ever thought of helping others in need? Is there a cause that is close to my heart? Would I like to help an organization that supports that cause? If yes, then you just unlock the next social responsibility you could fulfill.

There are many projects launched by government and Non-governmental organizations to support different social causes like creating awareness for the importance of education, finding shelter for the homeless, looking after the sick people, spending time with old age people.

Students can be a part of any of them. It won't consume much of your time, and you will feel contented after giving time to something that is selfless. As it is rightly said, "The best feeling of happiness is knowing you're the reason of others' smile."

Those students who want to make a difference can always donate things that are no longer of use to them. Rewind a little, and you will find a number of things that are just sitting in your room adding onto nothing. For example books, notes, assignments, gadgets, study table, etc. Also, student can turn to the local people to collect the books and other items.

So, my mind the other way to fulfill your social responsibility is condone any form of bullying. "Pulling someone down will never help you reach the top."

“Bullying leads people to commit suicide.” The majority of young adults who committed suicide could have been saved if help had been offered to them. Rescuing a young adult or teenager is possible with the right type of awareness and education. If you see anything unethical happening around, raise your voice against it instead of ignoring it and moving on as if you saw nothing.

To sum up the most important things how to be a socially responsible person is to follow ethics.

Ethical code helps in understanding the difference between ‘right’ and ‘wrong’ and in applying that understanding to your decisions. For example, if you are given a chance to take up an opportunity that could be really beneficial to you, but it may result in a loss to your fellow people, would it be fair to grab it?

Being just to your morals is the prime social responsibility. After all, you are the one you are answerable to.

It takes a strong thinking to make the right tradeoffs. “Every individual has a place to fill in the world and is important in some respect whether he/she chooses to be so or not.” Nathaniel Hawthorne.

It’s time to take a look in the mirror to see if you are ready to be a socially responsible human being or not. The opportunities are endless. Are you ready to choose?

ANIMALS ARE NOT OUR TOYS

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One of the most important problems of the modern world is animal extermination and abuse. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species includes 13,267

rare and endangered species of animals, of which 6,102 are vulnerable and 4,314 are endangered. 2,851 species are on the verge of extinction. Another 34 species of animals are listed as disappeared in the wild and 748 species are already completely extinct.

By creating zoos, oceanariums, and animal circuses, humans only accelerate the process of animal extinction. In captivity, their life expectancy is reduced, new diseases appear and the process of reproduction is slowed down.

In zoos, animals are restricted to all freedom and brutally bullied. Little elephants are chained to the floor and prevented from even playing in nature. Then the same elephants are brutally trained with a hook.

To make the horse stand on her hind legs for a long time, she is electrocuted.

Training predators is not without cruelty either. Whoever says anything, there is no humane training. Or do you think the animals are politely asked to do a complicated trick? Or did they come to the circus themselves? No! They are beaten and starved.

In zoos, animals don't feel good either. Regular visitors lead to nervous disorders in animals. Heavy noise, crowds and lack of freedom have a negative impact on their health. They live less than in the wild and give less offspring. Zoos are not designed to protect rare species of animals, but only to entertain people.

In oceanariums dolphins and killer whails are not cute and friendly at all. Very often they die not only from cruel trainings, but also from fights between themselves. Killer whails often injure their fellow prisoners and they die in torment. Such smart dolphins often experience discomfort while surrounded by people. This leads to nervous disruption and health problems.

Any restriction of the freedom of wild animals, ill-treatment of them only for the sake of fun, must be punished by law. It's time to ban zoos and animal circuses.

The most famous in the world Circus du Soleil in 35 years of existence has never used animals in performances, but emphasizes only colorful performances of acrobat.

The oldest circus in the world is the Chinese state circus, about 2,000 years old. All this time, artists did not attract animals to performances.

The German circus also refused to perform animals. In 2018, hologram animals appeared in his arena, which struck the audience.

These circuses should be examples to the world which show that animals are not clowns. They need to be protected, they can be admired. Instead of circuses, it is possible to create more reserves where animals will be in a natural habitat.

Pets deserve attention, too. For example, in France, all pets must have documents and social insurance. The authorities ensure that the number of animals on the street does not increase, the person who threw out a dog or the person found to have abused it must pay a fine.

In the Netherlands, animal cruelty is considered the most real offence for violating animal rights by issuing a fine or imprisonment.

Turkey has animal feeding devices. If you throw a plastic bottle into this machine, it will give food to a homeless animal. They are, by the way, sterilized to reduce their aggression and reproduction.

In Germany, the article on animal protection is included in the constitution. For ill-treatment of an animal owner will be fined or sentenced to prison for up to three years. Schools have introduced animal welfare lessons. Dogs can be transferred from the shelter to nursing homes or a blind society. Propaganda is carried out so that animals are taken from the shelter, but the animal simply will not be given away, first the living conditions of the potential host will be checked and only then the decision to transfer, the pet is made.

Pets should not be on the street. But if this happened, people and power should not be indifferent. Creating shelters can save many lives. And by taking the pet out of the shelter, you can make two happy at once.

If the authorities of countries allot money and seriously deal with this issue, one of the humanity's global problems - homeless dogs and cats – will be solved forever.

And we must remember that we are responsible for those who have been tamed.

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SOCIALIZATION OF YOUTH IN MODERN SOCIETY

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Youth plays a key role in the formation and development of our young state. Since the processes of transformation of public life and modernization of the educational system in accordance with the needs of integration are now actively taking place, new social institutions have been formed, the role of students in society is changing, the problem of socialization of students in modern society is becoming

particularly relevant. In the scientific system of concepts the term "socialization" was introduced by the American sociologist F. Gidingstonom, who in 1887 in his paper "Theory of socialization" consumed it in the significance of the close to modern,- "social development of individual's nature and character, preparation of human material to social life" [2, p. 21].

At present, the process of socialization is considered by science in the broad and narrow senses of this concept. Socialization in the broad sense is the definition of the origin and formation of the generic human nature (we are talking about the historical process of human development), in the narrow – the process of entering the individual into society, the active assimilation of social experience, social roles, norms, values necessary for successful life in a certain society.

Youth today is seen as a socio-demographic community, separated on the basis of a set and age characteristics and features of social status. Youth as a certain phase, stage of the life cycle is biologically universal, but its specific age frames associated with it, social status and socio-psychological characteristics have a socio-historical nature and depend on the social system, culture and socialization patterns peculiar to this society.

The specificity of youth is that it is in the process of transition from childhood to adult and going through the stage of family and non-family socialization, interpretation of norms and values, the creation of social roles and statuses, professional expectations. Therefore, this process manifests itself in specific youth behaviors and consciousnesses, concepts of youth subculture, fashion, music, language and so on [1, p. 3].

Now the period of youth is lengthening, the criteria for determining social maturity are becoming more complicated. Young people today – one of the most numerous socio-demographic groups, which constantly replenishes the economically active population of the Donetsk People's Republic, occupies a leading place in the new socio – economic groups-entrepreneurs, managers, bank employees. The number of young people who lead social movements, organizations and political parties is

constantly increasing. At the same time, young people are one of the most vulnerable social groups in the country, as their financial situation deteriorates significantly, uncertainty in the future is formed, and there is a lack of social and industrial experience. Student youth plays a special role in the life of our society. It has certain General features: the unity of goals and objectives in mastering the profession, the relative identity of life models, the similarity of needs and interests due to age characteristics [3, p. 140].

Grad days is a period of active formation of social maturity, new relationships, personal attitude to future professional activity and its values. This time of personal self-identification, searching for their place and role in various social communities. Accelerating the pace of social life contributes to the role and importance of young people in social, political and cultural life. The studying period in higher educational institutions is an important stage of inclusion of students in the system of public relations, their assimilation of social values of society. Taking into account the peculiarities of socialization of students, it is higher educational institutions that should improve the mechanisms of socialization of students, intensify their interaction with various social entities, and contribute to the formation of their active life position.

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THE YOUTH AND OUR TIME

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Youth is a period of life which is of utmost importance in people's life. Firstly, the morals and beliefs, range of interests, education, health and habits are all laid in childhood and youth, and so the personality is shaped. Secondly, youth is a time when a person is trying to find his place in the world. This period is usually associated with problems: young people 'struggle' to fit themselves into society. Among them are eternal problems of choosing a career and getting education, a problem of independence and money, a problem of unemployment of young people and the generation gap. Young people have many problems of emotional and personal character which may look silly and unimportant in the eyes of grown-ups but appear to be extremely important to the young. They are the problems of friendship and loneliness, as well as the problem of the first love.

Probably the most vital problem is choosing a career, which is really difficult. One thing that makes it so difficult is the responsibility you have to take on — it is widely known that your future life depends on the choice made early in life when your personal experience is not so great. Sometimes you may even be not quite certain about the field of knowledge you are interested in. Another thing is that there are parents who usually have their own idea of your future career and, in many cases, try to make their child choose the career path they prefer.

Perhaps one of the most fundamental problems faced by young people today is unemployment which means financial worries, frustration and discouragement. To solve the problem of unemployment, young people should strive for higher education. Then they will be qualified for skilled labour required by industrialized society.

Another inevitable problem facing young people today is the tension which exists between parents and children, or the 'generation gap'. Firstly, young people always reject or at least question the values of their parents because they want to learn from their own experience, not from their parents' standards. Secondly, every younger generation tends to be more educated and better-informed than the previous one. Thirdly, parents tend to aggravate the situation: they try to impose their ideas upon their children. It results in young people's revolt against adult authority.

The youth is the future, therefore at all times to it was given particular attention. But if now to look at our young generation it seems not such cloudless. Now I look at young men with a heavy heart. On many of those who don't have reference points, definite purposes in the life, have no present concept of culture and value. It would be desirable to note a word many as among youth there are people whom with pride it is possible to name the country future. But, nevertheless, the picture appears as the sad.

Looking back in the past, we can compare generations of a century of the past and a century of the present. That seemed inadmissible earlier, unfortunately, in present time is norm. This is the predilection of young to alcohol, to drugs, to loose life. To senior generation it is difficult to adapt in present conditions (sensations of hopelessness, uncertainty in tomorrow) and to keep former system of values. I think that to young generation it is much more difficult in this plan so they still don't have system of values.

Recently the percent of criminal reports with participation of absolutely young people grows. Among offenses attract attention profit-motivated crimes – larceny, extortion of money, swindle. It is connected with that parents can't satisfy all inquiries of the child as at the young such concept «all and at once» is developed. And teenagers can't earn on the wished: many simply don't have desire studies, to reach something by own strength. Even having got education it is difficult for the young to find work, to find the place in a society. The share of young men as a part of the unemployed remains high. The modern youth possesses such line which shows

that the most part from it wishes to have a good income, thus, having no trades and no desires to work. It occurs because the youth doesn't have stimulus to work. The majority has appeared without reliable social reference points. The choice of a course of life began to be defined not by abilities and interests of a young man, and concrete circumstances. From a hopelessness of realization of the possibilities young men, as a rule, follow a wrong way.

It would be desirable to note and some negative influence of technologies. Now it is quite often to meet that children prefer to spend time in the virtual world, for a place of a real dialogue with contemporaries, productive leisure or sports employment. Display of immoral, cruel cartoon films and serials also make negative impact. Sometimes characters of films, instead of parents, grandmothers and grandfathers tell about good and harm representation, that such is good and that such is bad. Perhaps, therefore all of us should face cruelty of children, their disrespect to each other, to the senior generation is more often. I had to meet cruel treatment of children to animals.

In my opinion, the problem of employment of children, teenagers can be solved by their attraction in public works, in sports, to help them to develop their interests, to open talents. It is necessary no to build the big shopping centers, but sports complexes, the centers of employment of children. It is necessary to give more attention to children from unsuccessful families. Support of the state to students, young families, young men which search for work is important also. Formation of viable growing up young generation becomes one of the main strategic problems of development of the country.

Youth is the finest time in life of each person. It is the time, when the person especially feels surplus of physical strengths and flexibility of a body, fast rate enriches mind, the horizon of its knowledge extends. If mind, force and will of young men to direct to the necessary way, to help them to develop their interests and the initiative our country will go on the way to prosperity, force and to the light future.

To conclude, it can be mentioned that grown-ups should work together with young people to help them solve these problems. We must remember that the young people are the leaders of our society and our tomorrow.

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STRESS AND STRESS MANAGEMENT

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Stress is a feeling of emotional or physical tension. It can come from any event or thought that makes you feel frustrated, angry, or nervous. Stress is your body's reaction to a challenge or demand. In short bursts, stress can be positive, such as when it helps you avoid danger or meet a deadline. But when stress lasts for a long time, it may harm your health.

Stress can be acute. This is short-term stress that goes away quickly. You feel it when you slam on the brakes, have a fight with your partner, or ski down a steep slope. It helps you manage dangerous situations. It also occurs when you do something new or exciting. All people have acute stress at one time or another. These incidents of acute stress don't normally do you any harm. They might even be good for you. Stressful situations give your body and brain practice in developing the best response to future stressful situations.

It can be chronic. This is stress that lasts for a longer period of time. You may have chronic stress if you have money problems, an unhappy marriage, or trouble at work. Any type of stress that goes on for weeks or months is chronic stress. You can become so used to chronic stress that you don't realize it is a problem. If you don't find ways to manage stress, it may lead to health problems such as headaches, an upset stomach, and sleep difficulties [1].

If you're living with high levels of stress, you're putting your entire well-being at risk. Stress wreaks havoc on your emotional equilibrium, as well as your physical health. It narrows your ability to think clearly, function effectively, and enjoy life. That is why stress management is very important.

Stress management starts with identifying the sources of stress in your life. This isn't as straightforward as it sounds. While it's easy to identify major stressors such as changing jobs, moving, or a going through a divorce, pinpointing the sources of chronic stress can be more complicated. It's all too easy to overlook how your own thoughts, feelings, and behaviours contribute to your everyday stress levels. Sure, you may know that you're constantly worried about work deadlines, but maybe it's your procrastination, rather than the actual job demands, that is causing the stress [2].

When your stress level exceeds your ability to cope, you need to restore the balance by reducing the stressors or increasing your ability to cope or both. Try using one of the four A's: avoid, alter, accept or adapt [3].

There is nothing more calming than spending quality time with another human being who makes you feel safe and understood. In fact, face-to-face interaction triggers a cascade of hormones that counteracts the body's defensive "fight-or-flight" response. Its nature's natural stress reliever (as an added bonus, it also helps stave off depression and anxiety). So make it a point to connect regularly and in person with family and friends. Keep in mind that the people you talk to don't have to be able to fix your stress. They simply need to be good listeners. And try not to let worries about looking weak or being a burden keeps you from opening up. The

people who care about you will be flattered by your trust. It will only strengthen your bond.

Poor time management can cause a lot of stress. When you're stretched too thin and running behind, it's hard to stay calm and focused. Plus, you'll be tempted to avoid or cut back on all the healthy things you should be doing to keep stress in check, like socializing and getting enough sleep. Don't over-commit yourself, break projects into small steps, delegate responsibility

When you're stressed, the last thing you probably feel like doing is getting up and exercising. But physical activity is a huge stress reliever—and you don't have to be an athlete or spend hours in a gym to experience the benefits. Exercise releases endorphins that make you feel good, and it can also serve as a valuable distraction from your daily worries. While you'll get the most benefit from regularly exercising for 30 minutes or more, it's okay to build up your fitness level gradually. Even very small activities can add up over the course of a day. The first step is to get yourself up and moving. In addition to regular exercise, there are other healthy lifestyle choices that can increase your resistance to stress. You should eat a healthy diet, reduce caffeine and sugar and avoid alcohol, cigarettes, and drugs [2].

Stress isn't necessarily a bad thing. It's what helped our hunter-gatherer ancestors survive, and it's just as important in today's world. We all feel stressed at times, but what one person finds stressful may be very different from what another finds stressful [4]. By practicing a regular stress management technique or two, you can eliminate some of the stress you feel right now and make yourself more resilient in the face of stress in the future. The key to quick stress relief is to experiment and discover the unique sensory experiences that work best for you.

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PROBLEM OF DEGRADATION

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Facing many people every day, I hear more and more such an enduring expression as “youth degrading day by day”. And it is striking that this is heard from the lips of the older generation. And from here it seems to me that nobody believes in us, a large-scale social group called "youth". That we are the worst thing that happened and, in general, could happen to humanity and the planet Earth. And on this note, I want to proudly say: “You are completely wrong! Your ideas about the future of today's youth are wrong! ”

We live

We live in a time when information is available in any form and access. And every day more and more new forums open, which we, the “youth,” are embracing. We are not degrading!

We read a lot

We read a lot! We love to read! We are interested in both fiction and contemporary literature, and science fiction. What interests us is in what period of the time chain what events took place ?! And how did these events affect the people of that time ?! And what did these people feel and what were they experiencing ?! And in what way they solved conflicts ... And now books, of various genres and directions, are published the most than ever in the entire history of the existence of

mankind. Because there is a demand for them. And a certain percentage of this demand is “youth”.

We go to the theater

We also go to theaters! In theaters where performances are staged, based on works of art. And where are contemporary performances staged that raise topical issues of the whole society and the world as a whole. After what we saw, we share our impressions with parents, friends and acquaintances. We think about what the performance wanted to convey to us, people. We are looking for answers to questions posed before our eyes! We analyze and draw conclusions as representatives of “homo sapiens”!

We visit museums

We visit museums. This suggests that we are interested in the past humanity. His story! The way it was! The way we ourselves looked in the past! What did you eat?! How were you hunting?! What devices did you use for this?! And the way we evolved. And a certain percentage of the result of this evolution pleases us. And we also understand that we ourselves are not the end result of this evolutionary process. We are perhaps even only its middle ... Since humanity is developing (!) Every day. And just beginning to show its true limitless potential. And "youth" is part of this humanity [1,320p].

We attend exhibitions

We attend diverse exhibitions! We adore this whole palette of colors, mixed with genius on the canvas and something created by him. Through these colors we are trying to understand what the artist wanted to convey to us?! What was going on in his head and soul when he created it?! And did he think that his creation would be a movement forward, towards the opening of a new direction in the visual arts?!

We are developing ourselves

We are developing ourselves! Since school times, we participate in various competitions, contests. We take prizes in them. We sign up for different circles.

Theatre studio! Vocals! Violin! Art! Basketball! Tennis! Volleyball! Swimming! Chess! Learning foreign languages (which is a huge plus in our time and we understand it)! Communication with representatives of foreign "youth" for universal socialization. This list goes on and on.

It is interesting to us

And we are interested in what is happening in our country. We also discuss situations of a political, economic, cultural, educational, social nature. We express our opinion about them. I bet! But we respect each other! This does not turn into a debate between two crazy people whose goal is to get others to accept his point of view and think as well. We come to a consensus.

We are worried

We worry when some kind of upheaval occurs: terrorist attacks, air crashes, taking away people's lives. We are not insensitive! We are not selfish! We are not indifferent to the rest of the "youth". If something happens, we experience the same as adults. I can say with confidence that we feel a million times sharper than adults. And not because we have not yet formed a "children's psyche", but because we really feel pain. And we do not like the injustice that is happening in many parts of the world. In many of us, there is a heightened sense of injustice, which wants to break out [2,108p.].

And before you call us stupid young people who pose a threat to humanity, think carefully: is this really so. We see the world not like the older generation, but we are ready to do certain things for our future, for all of us.

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YOUNG LEADERS

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Leaders are important not only in companies but in all spheres of human life. Their role is to "guide others in their task". One of the key tasks of leaders is to focus on the object, producing and selling goods and services. They maintain stability and create a culture of efficiency. On the other hand, leaders create vision and strategy. Such workers help others grow, focus on people, inspire and motivate. They create change, help employees move forward, even if the change is abrupt and radical, leaders maintain a corporate culture and a culture of integrity.

Leadership is currently discussed in numerous management programs, radio talk shows, and written media. The concern about the concept of leadership is probably the lack of leadership in all walks of life. According to political commentators, management analysts and other observers, there is either little or no leadership in social society, organizations and, more importantly, in the political environment of many countries to address the challenges of our time.

Leadership as a social phenomenon which accompanies humanity throughout its existence. Wherever a group of more than two people gathers, there may be a situation of leading one and following the other. The leader has a significant impact on the processes of self-organization of the group, the formation of group norms and values, on the behavior of followers. In this regard, leaders and the phenomenon of leadership attract traditionally the attention of researchers. Therefore, in different historical eras, attempts were made to study leadership qualities based on the description of the personalities of great people.

Speaking about leadership in modern conditions, it should be emphasized that at the moment the promotion of young leaders is gaining popularity. This is due to

the awareness of young people in new trends and innovations, their ability to adapt and lead the team with the times. The flexibility of thinking also plays an important role. The flexibility of thinking is the ability of a person to find new strategies for solving problems quickly and easily, sometimes non-standard.

The policy of many countries is aimed at the development of the younger generation, its promotion, and identification of leadership qualities. One of the most global projects is the forum "Young leaders of Eurasia", where gifted and advanced leaders of the young generation from different countries can gather together of the world through selection in several stages.

There is even a statutory youth policy program, as well as an international school of leaders "New generation" in Europe. The Russian Federation also provides a large-scale project "Leaders of Russia 2020", which conducts 8 stages of testing and selection, according to which 300 of the most promising leaders will be able to prove them in various fields.

However, while the new generation of leaders is developing and starting its activities, we should not forget about the most outstanding young leaders of our time.

One of them is the internationally recognized youngest political leader - Sebastian Kurz. If you do not even follow world politics, you probably know that on October 15, the parliamentary elections were held in Austria, following the results of which 31-year-old Foreign Minister Sebastian Kurz became the new Federal Chancellor. And now, Kurz is the youngest Federal Chancellor in Austrian history and one of the youngest leaders in modern Europe.

Another example is Jacinda Ardern. She was elected to the Parliament at 28. At 37, she became a supporter of left-wing social democratic views and led the left-wing government of New Zealand. She is in favor of refugees. She and Kurz hold opposing worldviews but they are united only by their age.

Sebastian Kurtz and Jacinda Ardern joined this week's list of the world's youngest state leaders, who are not yet forty. No matter how much the retirement age

is raised in developed countries, there is no escaping the simple truth: the world belongs to the young people in the true sense of the word.

Here are her few other examples of young leaders around the world:

- Yuri Ratas, 27 years old (Estonia)

In November 2016, the 38-year-old Juri Ratas became the Prime Minister of Estonia. At 27, he was already the Mayor of Tallinn.

- Alexandria Ocasio-Cortez, 29 years old (USA)

She is the youngest woman ever elected to the U.S. Congress. Alexandria belongs to the left-wing of the Democratic party and is an active member of the Democratic socialists of America.

- Marie Black, 24 years old (United Kingdom)

In 2015 (when she was 20 years old), Marie became the youngest member of the House of Commons since 1832. She joined the Scottish National Party in 2014 and took part in the preparation of the Referendum on Scottish independence.

- Tiffany Degua, 24 years old (France)

Tiffany is a member of the Social-Liberal political party «Forward Republic!», which was created by the current President of France Emmanuel Macron. In June 2017, Degua became a member of the National Assembly of France from the Department of Savoy.

- Jordon Steele-John, 22 (Australia)

He is the youngest member of the Australian Parliament elected in 2017. He defends the rights of disabled people and was even awarded for it in March this year.

So, we can conclude, that young leaders play an important role in the life of their countries and in the world culture. Their number has increased dramatically for the last decade. The creation of Youth Parliament in DPR is one step in leadership potential formation in our country.

SOCIAL MEDIA ADDICTION AMONG TEENAGERS

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The concept of Internet addiction is an integral part of "social dependency", which was considered by M. Weber, E. Durkheim, G. Simmel, R. Merton, P. Bourdieu, E. Giddens, Z. Bauman, P. Stompka and other sociologists. In modern life, the Internet has become a virtual social space through which people satisfy their specific needs. People should be well oriented in this space, as well as associate their ideas with intense activity [1, p. 14].

A huge scientific field is the research of Internet addiction as a demonstration of deviant behavior (N. Korytnikova, A. Berezkin, S. Varlamova, E. Goncharova, I. Sokolova, etc.).

This view is based on such a method of adaptation according to R. Merton, as the avoidance of responsibility, according to which a person wants to distract oneself from all difficulties, forget about responsibilities and relax. This is expressed in a long pastime in the network and immersion in virtual reality, in which the whole system of rules and laws of real society is built as a need for compensation for professional and social self-realization in everyday activities, as well as in competition. Thus, Internet addiction is the obsessive desire to use the Internet every day, as well as unnecessary and excessive use of the Internet and the need to spend a lot of time on the Internet.

There are numerous modern typologies of Internet addiction, which is mainly based on the distinction between users and their preferences. For instance, there are six types of computer addiction [2]:

- 1) intrusive web surfing (information overload) - information search;

- 2) necessity of virtual communication;
- 3) gaming addiction (obsessive passion for computer games);
- 4) obsessive financial need (gambling, unnecessary purchases);
- 5) feeling of euphoria and dependence on watching movies, etc. on the internet;
- 6) cyber sexual addiction.

The degree of dependence on the Internet increases with the growth of material wealth. This is especially noticeable among the rural population with different financial circumstances and those who do not use the Internet for work.

The influence of lifestyle on the manifestations of Internet addiction was partially explained, and respondents with a closed lifestyle are more dependent on the Internet than those who lead an active lifestyle.

The developed typology pointed out that with a reduction in the time spent by young people on the Internet, their dependence on it decreases.

Young people are affected by the Internet. Multiple difficulties in everyday life associated with the difficulties of interaction in modern society are increasingly pushing young people to "deepen" the network. Some people feel more confident and open on the Internet. And it helps to expand the number of contacts, which positively affects the satisfaction of social needs. All these points of using the Internet are fascinating for modern youth [3].

The addiction of modern youth on the Internet is a complicated process, the reasons for which are not simple and superficial. Constant technical changes and the development of the Internet have a huge impact on the consumption of Internet services. Young people often not only cannot control the time spent on the Internet but also do not aspire to it.

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NEW WAYS OF WEB-BASED ECONOMY DEVELOPMENT

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In the Digital Era, the increasing use of the Internet and digital devices is completely transforming the way of interacting in the economic and social framework. Myriad individuals, companies and public organizations use the Internet for their daily activities, generating a stream of fresh data ("Big Data") [1]. The term “big data” refers to data that is so large, fast or complex that it’s difficult or impossible to process using traditional methods. The act of accessing and storing large amounts of information for analytics has been around a long time. But the concept of big data gained momentum in the early 2000s when industry analyst Doug Laney articulated the now-mainstream definition of big data as the three V’s:

Volume: Organizations collect data from a variety of sources, including business transactions, smart devices, industrial equipment, videos, social media and

more. In the past, storing it would have been a problem – but cheaper storage on platforms like data lakes and Hadoop have eased the burden.

Velocity: With the growth in the Internet of Things, data streams in to businesses at an unprecedented speed and must be handled in a timely manner. RFID tags, sensors and smart meters are driving the need to deal with these torrents of data in near-real time.

Variety: Data comes in all types of formats – from structured, numeric data in traditional databases to unstructured text documents, emails, videos, audios, stock ticker data and financial transactions.

All of this is principally accessible through the World Wide Web (WWW), which has become the largest repository of information in the world. These digital footprints can be tracked and, if properly processed and analyzed, could help to monitor in real time a wide range of economic variables. In this context, the main goal of this thesis is to generate economic indicators, based on web data, which are able to provide regular, short-term predictions ("nowcasting") about some business activities that are basic for the growth and development of an economy [2]. The following conventions and assumptions were used for compiling the research data:

Companies studied were U.S.-based and generated all or part of their revenues from Internet or IP products and/or services.

The scope of the research was limited to companies who had revenues associated directly with the Internet. The study did not include second or higher order impacts of the Internet Economy.

Revenues and jobs were based on worldwide estimates of U.S.-based companies.

Revenues were calculated based upon companies' estimates of the percentage of their revenues that were Internet-related. For the largest 300 companies analyzed products and services and categorized them into layers and estimated revenues for each layer using phone interviews, annual reports, and other secondary research data.

Since most companies were unable to estimate the percent of their total employees dedicated to Internet-related revenues, jobs' estimates were attributed using the ratio of Internet revenues to total revenues.

Concretely, three web-based economic indicators have been designed and evaluated [3]: first, an indicator of firms' export orientation, which is based on a model that predicts if a firm is an exporter; second, an indicator of firms' engagement in e-commerce, which is based on a model that predicts if a firm offers e-commerce facilities in its website; and third, an indicator of firms' survival, which is based on two models that indicate the probability of survival of a firm and its hazard rate. To build these indicators, a variety of data from corporate websites have been retrieved manually and automatically, and subsequently have been processed and analyzed with Big Data analysis techniques. Results show that the selected web data are highly related to the economic variables under study, and the web-based indicators are capturing a great extent of their real values, thus being valid for their use by the academia, firms and policy-makers. Additionally, the digital and online nature of web-based indicators makes it possible to provide timely, inexpensive predictions about the economy. This way, they are advantageous with respect to traditional indicators. This method has contributed to generating knowledge about the viability of producing economic indicators with data coming from corporate websites. The indicators that have been designed are expected to contribute to the modernization of official statistics and to help in making earlier, more informed decisions to policy-makers and business managers.

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BASIC PROBLEMS OF MODERN YOUTH

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Youth is not only the future, it is a “living present”, and it is important to understand how already today the young generation determines the content and nature of the future, how much it carries the “spirit of the new time”. The problems of modern youth in our time are becoming increasingly relevant. Throughout the world, among young people, priorities are changing. Instead of being kind, honest and obedient, thinking about family, our younger generation increasingly wants to stand out due to addictions, violence and superiority [1, p.124]. Therefore, adults have a difficult task - to instill goodness and humanity in adolescents in order to avoid the subsequent problems of youth in modern society. Of the existing youth problems, the most important are: immorality in behavior, alcoholism, drug addiction, smoking, crime or suicide, substitution of life values.

The first of the main problems among youth is immorality in behavior. Everything that affects adolescents is very important. Regarding immorality, it should be absorbed from the diaper. This problem of youth is laid subconsciously, using the example of a family. If a teenager sees one parent's disrespect for another, then in 90% of cases, he will also relate to others. He will not have the limits of decency through which he cannot cross. And his surroundings will begin to adapt to him, and this is a secondarily acquired problem of modern youth. Often parents wonder why their child is doing this? But it turns out that the whole problem is friends. It is necessary to initially growing of a child correctly, and subsequently, to be interested in his company. This is the only way to protect a teenager from immoral behavior.

We can consider alcoholism as a second problem. Alcoholism can be called a social problem of youth, since no one is safe from it. Here, both hereditary predisposition and acquired one are affected by the retraction method. A teenager who started drinking alcohol early loses its meaning in life. Subsequently, his stimulus is drinking. Today, alcoholism is the most pressing problem of youth, regardless of gender. A teenager in the stage of alcoholic intoxication becomes unbalanced, obsessive, rude, and reckless. From here another problem of youth comes out, that is crime. Indeed, such people are knee-deep in the sea and they can go to great difficulty [2, p.89].

Most of all crimes committed by adolescents in the stage of intoxication. In order to avoid teenage alcoholism and raise a full-fledged member of society, it is necessary to monitor the children and protect them in time from bad companies where alcohol is practiced. It is better for the child to acquire the meaning of life in sports, music or other areas. Addiction is one of the worst and the main dependencies of the youth. This is a problem of youth of the 21st century and need to fight it much harder than alcoholism. It takes roots as well, from the adverse companies. Teen caught in such a company, by a twist of fate becomes a hostage situation, and not to be outdone by his peers, decides to try a drug. Often this is fatal and after six months he becomes addicted to drugs. Such problems of youth in the modern world lurk at every step, and get rid of them by yourself is almost impossible. Therefore, you should not rely on the case, that issue doesn't hook you, the parents - control and monitor your child [1, p.42-44]. If it's already happened, you should find a rehabilitation center, where the former addicts, the teenager will recover from a terrible disease. Only correct and long-term rehabilitation will help to solve a social problem of modern youth, as drug addiction.

Substitution of values in life is a major moral error in the education of the modern teenager. This problem of modern youth is quite relevant. In the pursuit of modernity, many teenage girls instead of striving for a happy family life, trying to become attractive and sexy, come to the depravity of nature. This also applies to boys

who in spite of their idols, over time you realize that they don't get to become such as that. This leads to loss of all values and disappointment in life. But we must remember that by itself is not resolved.

Finally, the constant and the main problem is the generation gap. One of the main problems of youth is their lack of understanding of adults. Through this there are a lot of conflicts with parents. Often teenagers leave home, and sometimes even decide to take their own life. I think parents should work on themselves: to remember themselves in childhood, sign up in social networks, read information about this issue.

Thus, summarizing, we can say that the state should pay more attention to issues of youth: to support the organization's institutions working exclusively on youth issues who provide effective psychological and social assistance to young people; to pay more attention to the development of sport, and to attract the younger generation to professional sports. Conduct more advocacy about healthy lifestyle of youth, to attract not only state organizations and institutions but also private companies and the media.

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SOCIAL LIFE OF GENERATIONS

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“Every generation revolts against its fathers and makes friends with its grandfathers.” — Lewis Mumford

«There is no progress without information» - this is how our time of development of information technologies was called. Mass media become one of the most leading spheres of our social life, which have a lot of functions: on the one side mass media objectively looks at things and represents only the truth but on the other side it is promoting a certain ideology, imposing traditional foundations of people.

Youth is a leading mechanism of our life and each new generation has a lot of differences to a previous. And there are several reasons, which, first of all, are in the difference in the foundations and traditions of the «Fathers and Children»:

- Attitude to life. Why is the character of our predecessors so strong and unshakable? First of all, this is because of patriotism and love for the motherland, which were imposed on them from the cradle. Now, almost every second teenager has a dream, as soon as possible to leave the country, in the western lands, where it is supposedly easier to live.

- The pursuit of fashion. For some reason, circumstances have developed so that nobody previously needed T-shirts with a company logo on their chests have turned into one of the distinguishing and most important features of a person. Paying for a few even ugly letters, people buy themselves a status that previously had to be earned by hard work. [1, p.145].

- New culture. Music, cinema and even art began to regain the interest of teenagers.

· Religion and faith. Religion as such lost strength in the 20th century. Now, most people have forgotten about it, and they consider it nothing more than a simple tradition.

As a result of these circumstances, there is a fairly accurate analogy with the theory of generations presented in the 90s by American scientists William Strauss and Neil Howe. They argued that generations that appear over time are cyclical and repeat approximately every 80 years. So, 6 generations were allocated: G.I. Generation, Silent Generation, Baby Boom Generation, Generation X («13th Generation»), Generation Y («Millennial Generation»), Generation Z («Homeland Generation»). Their biography was created not only by the conditions of upbringing in the family but also by the historical, political and economic events taking place at that time.

It is quite simple to implement this theory in reality, applying it to your own family. For example, my parents, as representatives of the «X's», although have rather conservative outlooks on life, but they are astonished by their ability to independence, which they got in early childhood. What is noteworthy, they still follow their relatives' bits of advice and compare their thoughts with one's interests. First of all, this is characterized by the fact that they were growing up in the era of «stagnation»: the beginning of the Afghanistan war, «perestroika», and, in the end, nobody should forget about globalization developing at that time extremely quickly and rapidly. That all influenced yet another distinguishing feature of the X's – pragmatism [3, p.72].

In turn, my generation of «Y's» is the exact opposite of their predecessors and the only ones with whom they can be compared is the «G.I. Generation» born at the ending of the 19th and beginning of the 20th century. It is this period of time that is characterized by a complete change of the old foundations and moral values of young people who did not know about what to expect in the near future. The so-called «Y's» are those people who were able to feel the fall of a great state, a period of crisis, wars, and, more importantly, the rapid development of information technology.

If our parents became famous for their excessive independence, then we were born and raised with the thought that everything will come with time, the main thing is to wait. And now this time of rapid development and change of not only foundations but also a life in general has led to the fact that now the "millennials" do not believe everything they hear from someone else's lips. This is the result of their rapid growth through troubled times, which at every moment could become the last [4, p. 87].

Homeland Generation is perhaps the most controversial generation of society. Many scientists are already describing this time - as a time of crisis, not just of any country, but of the whole world. In our days, there is too much information that people simply do not have time to master it. And if I started to give examples, then my little sister is an obvious representative of this time. If my peers began to dive into the world of information and technology somewhere from a more or less conscious age of 8-10 years, then today's youth began to do this literally from the cradle. Nowadays every second child of 7-8 years old has a smartphone, and every 4th child has his own profile on social networks. And if I found a time when libraries are covered with dust and cobwebs, then it seems that the "Z's" will watch the same with theaters, replaced by various services such as "Netflix", "iTunes", etc.

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VIRTUAL LIFE OF TEENAGERS

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In the world of technology –the Internet is a way to find new friends, learn more about other countries and the opportunity to study remotely. It is hard for modern teenagers to imagine how people lived before without the possibility of using the Internet. Previously, it was difficult for teenagers to learn, but now they have much information to choose from. With the help of the Internet students save time and spend less effort on writing work.[3, с.117] Thanks to the Internet students get the opportunity for quality training with advice from international teachers and professors. Teenagers can at any time be engaged in reading a scientific article or a book they need or are interested in.

It is important to note the fact that teenagers increasingly began to use the Internet for other purposes. After a while, the Internet began to have both positive and negative features. If we talk about the positive features, the Internet makes it possible to have a connection with distant relatives. Second, the Internet allows teens to share their interests with friends. Thanks to the Internet, teenagers have the opportunity to show themselves to the world, thereby it makes them free. [1, с.125]

But on the other hand, the Internet has plunged teenagers into virtual life, which has led to big problems. Teenagers are immersed in the Internet with their whole head and forget, first of all, about their studies. There are many scams on the Internet. Teenagers who do not have a good command of the Internet very often fall for scams.

Nowadays, we have forgotten about what alive communication is, plunging our whole life into the Internet. One of the negative features of the Internet is a bad influence on the mental state of adolescents. Many popular games are about murder.

Various Internet quests that a teenager must complete in life are killing. We need to think about what should be done to ensure that the Internet only benefits teenagers. If nothing is changed, then soon teenagers will forget what real communication is, plunging into the virtual world.

The main factors that contribute to the Internet addiction are: 1. Genetic predisposition - when one of the family members had any kind of addiction; 2. Difficulties in communication with peers; 3. Lack of attention, or, conversely, hyperprotection on the part of parents. Signs that the child is starting to depend on the computer and the Internet: loss of interest to the outside world; bad school performance and conflicts with peers; increase of time spent at the computer; sleep impairment, irritability; a violent reaction to a request to switch off the Internet. In order to preserve the psyche of adolescents, some countries have begun to restrict access to social networks [2, c.38]. Educational institutions have put filters on the Internet so that teenagers can use the Internet only for the purpose of learning. It is important to take into account the fact that if you restrict access to the Internet for teenagers, it will lead to large material and mental losses. The Internet represents a parallel world for both: the older and younger generations. No one is able to fight with the fact that completely detached from the Internet. There is no doubt that virtual life on the Internet is very interesting for teenagers.

If everyone thinks about what values the World Web will bring to the future generation's lives, then there are chances to solve the problem of the Internet addiction.

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INFORMATION WARFARE AS A MODERN THREAT TO SOCIETY

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Information was one of the major tools for influencing people's minds throughout the ages. The role of data (or information) has increased significantly after the transition from industrial to the information society. It has penetrated all spheres of public life.

The positive aspect of such changes can be considered the emergence of information technologies that allow you to speed up the processing of data in the industrial and social sphere, free people from boring and routine work, as well as help in choosing the best solutions. However, we must not forget about the negative aspects of this phenomenon [1, p.28].

Nowadays we often hear about information wars. What danger do they pose to society?

The information war is a complex of measures for information impact on the mass consciousness of people to change their behavior, lifestyle, and beliefs. In world practice, psychoinformational influence as an integral part of the information war has acquired special importance.

Thus, in ancient times, the methods of information warfare were reduced to two types - verbal and nonverbal (spreading rumors, arrests, executions, etc.). The essence of these methods was to influence the consciousness of people through feelings and emotions.

The subconscious is the most vulnerable area of the human psyche, a kind of "open door" for manipulation. In one's subconscious mind can lay other people's ideas, values, sentiments, tastes, patterns of behavior.

What happens in the age of information technology?

A person as an individual, a carrier of a certain worldview, mentality, culture and spiritual values are exposed to daily information and psychological impact through various means of communication. Telephone, computer, television, the Internet, and other media are integral part of the modern world. There is an imposition of false information, which makes it impossible to correctly perceive events and make the right decisions [3, p.45].

The worldwide web allows communicating with each other, making friends, learning, working and «killing" time with pleasure watching your favorite movie. But along with the positive aspects, it is worth noting the negative impact of social networks. They are full of various kinds of advertising, propaganda, which lead to the loss of human dignity and uniqueness. Today, people cannot do without data channels. They have "breaking" (withdrawal), a sense of anxiety; this indicates the development of a new epidemic of the XXI century - information hunger.

The word is an invincible weapon. To protect oneself from manipulating, one must constantly work on oneself, show strong-willed efforts, thereby forming media literacy - the main quality of modern humans.

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MONEY

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MONEY IS USED FOR BUYING OR SELLING GOODS, FOR MEASURING VALUE AND FOR STORING WEALTH. Almost every society now has a money economy based on coins and paper notes of one kind or another. However, this has not always been true. In primitive societies a system of barter was used. Barter was a system of direct exchange of goods. Somebody could exchange a sheep, for example, for anything in the market place that they considered to be equal value. Barter however was a very unsatisfactory system because people's precise needs seldom coincided. People needed a more practical system of exchange, and various money systems developed based on goods, which the members of a society recognized as having a value. Cattle, grain, teeth, shells, feathers, skulls, salt, elephant tusks and tobacco have all been used. Precious metals gradually took over because, when made into coins, they were portable, durable, recognizable, and divisible into larger and smaller units of value.

A coin is a piece of metal, usually disc-shaped, which bears lettering, designs or numbers showing its value. Until the 18th and 19th centuries coins were given monetary worth based on the exact amount of metal contained in them, but most modern coins are based on face value, the value the governments choose to give

them, irrespective of the actual metal content. Coins have been made of gold (Au), silver (Ag), copper (Cu), aluminum (Al), nickel (Ni), lead (Pb), zinc (Zn), plastic and in China even from pressed tealeaves. Most governments now issue paper money in the form of notes, which are “promises to pay”. Paper money is obviously easier to handle and much more convenient in the modern world. Checks, bankers, cards and credit cards are being used increasingly and it is possibly to imagine a world where “money” in the form of coins and paper currently will no longer be used.

Earliest Money and Its Functions

We have already discussed the movement from self-sufficiency to more specialized production requiring barter. We saw that the greater the degree of specialization in the economy, the more difficult it became to discover a double coincidence of wants and then to negotiate mutually beneficial exchanges. We should note that nobody actually recorded the emergence of money. Thus, we can only speculate about how money first came into use.

Through repeated exchanges, traders may have found that there were certain goods for which there was always a ready market. If a trader could not find a desired match or did not need goods for immediate consumption, some good with a ready market could be accepted instead. So traders began to accept certain goods not for immediate consumption but because these goods would be acceptable to others and therefore could be retraded later. For example, corn might become accepted because traders knew corn was always in demand. As one good became generally acceptable in return for all other goods, that good began to function as money. As we will see, anything that is used as money serves three important functions: a medium of exchange, a standard of value, and a store of wealth.

Problems with Commodity Money

Corn does as well as some other commodities that have served as money throughout history. But there are problems with most commodity moneys, including corn. First, corn must be properly stored or its quality will deteriorate; even then, it

will not maintain its quality for long. Second, corn is bulky, so exchange becomes unwieldy for major purchases. For example, suppose a new home cost 50,000 bushels of corn. Many truckloads of corn would be involved in such a transaction. Third, if all corn is valued equally in exchange, people will tend to keep the best corn and trade away the lowest-quality corn. The quality of corn in circulation will therefore decline, reducing the acceptability of this commodity money. Sir Thomas Gresham, founder of the Royal Exchange of London, pointed out back in the sixteenth century that "bad money drives out good money," and this has come to be known as Gresham's Law". When moneys of different quality circulate side .by side, people tend to trade away the inferior money and hoard the best.

A final problem with corn as with other commodity moneys is that the value of corn depends on its supply and demand, which may vary unpredictably. On the supply side, if a bumper crop increases the supply of corn, corn would likely become less valuable, so more corn would exchange for all other goods. On the demand side, any change in the demand for corn as food would alter the amount available as a medium of exchange, and this, too, would influence the value of corn. Erratic fluctuations in the value of corn limit its usefulness as money, particularly as a store of wealth. If people cannot rely on the value of corn over time, they will be reluctant to hold it as a store of wealth. More generally, since the value of money depends on its supply being limited, anything that can be easily produced by anyone would not serve well as commodity money. For example, dirt would not serve well as commodity money.

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MODERN COMMUNICATIONS AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON TEENAGERS

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Youth plays an important role in modern society. In difficult moments of the existence of society, youth turns out to be the most vulnerable category of the population, which is in its spiritual, closed space. In this regard, the problems of youth have become so urgent that a few years ago a social science about youth, juvenology, was created.

Throughout all time, young people and their values have changed. In my opinion, modern youth lack motivation for cultural development and lose their life values and moral standards. The relevance of the topic lies in the fact that regardless of time, youth remains the main feature of the development of the state. The further fate of the country depends only on the youth themselves and their values.

What is the sense of life? Young people have always asked this question. Modern youth is often criticized: for frivolity, rudeness, distraction, inner callousness. Their preferences are very deplorable: computer games? Alcoholic drinks, smoking, disco parties. Very few of them do sport and pay attention to your health.

The problem of the relationships of parents and children is eternal. Sometimes no one can understand teenagers . Because of this, they cannot talk about their problems and share personal things. When teenagers have a lot of freedom they develop independence, confidence, capacity to solve problems. But a lot of teenagers became disorganized, without control they break many rules. Misunderstanding often begins between them. A teenager lives with the help of parents, they take care of him, give him advice, but he makes a design independently, makes up his mind himself. Sometimes parents forbid teenager much and he thinks that to be an adult is better ,

so their child often clashes with his parents. A famous proverb says “If you want to know about parents, look at their children”. So parents need to educate their children so that they can be proud of them. Maybe our generation needs to think about their priorities and values, sometimes to be in the wide family circle. We must thank our parents in time and not after their death. If we make a mistake or offend somebody, we must be in a hurry to correct this mistake and ask for excuse.

Another important moment in youth life is doing sport. To have good health is very actual today, because good health is above wealth. Sport helps to build character, to bring up physically strong, strong – willed, courageous and energetic people. Sports are a source of recreation and pleasure for people. Physical training is an essential part of children’s development beginning with the kindergarten. To live a long happy life we must be active and energetic. It’s bad to seat at the computer or watch TV for the all evening. A popular proverb says “A sound mine in a sound body”, because sports develop not only physical but improve moral qualities. When teenagers do not play sports, they waste time and lose their chance to develop.

It’s an open secret that the Internet is gaining popularity among teenagers. Using the Internet they communicate with friends, who are in different cities in the world. Computers became an important part of our life. Some scientists say that without the computer 21 century would be impossible. Teenagers don’t have time for doing their hometask, because they spend a lot of time in the Internet. Even when friends talk to each other on the Internet, it is not a real communication. Moreover they stop reading books, they neither develop, no improve their mental abilities, also it is bad for the eyesight and health. The youth stopped going to libraries. They think that learning foreign languages is a waste of time and money. Teenagers stop to notice the simplest things and to be near with their close persons because of the Internet. Teenagers used to get necessary information or to communicate, listen to pop music, watch films with the help of the Internet. It’s much more attractive and the interesting for them than reading books. Unlike the youth for elder generation reading is the best relaxation and pleasure. Intellect is the God’s gift to a human-

being. We must remember it and take care of our brain and intellect. That's why we need to enrich our knowledge of the life and the world around us, to master languages. Thus day by day, year by year we are preparing for active and interesting. A person must make and improve his own future life, he must be a creator of his own destiny.

In conclusion I can say that every new generation is unique. It isn't better, no worse. It is just different, not the same as before. Modern youth is not very different from youth of other times. Same age, same problems. But today there are problems that were not there before, another era, different rules. They don't understand such problems as lack of products, lack of peace, lack of confidence in tomorrow. This is very bad, because the past must be respected so as not to make mistakes in the future. Modern youth can be proud of their carelessness and sufficient security, unlike other times. There is the era of great discoveries and inventions, but few can use their potential for this, because of which progress is becoming less and less, as well as candidates of science. Representatives of young people of the next generations are not lucky, because they will live in a world destroyed by their own ancestors.

СЕКЦИЯ 3. АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ СТРАНОВЕДЕНИЯ И КУЛЬТУРЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ (НЕМЕЦКИЙ, ИСПАНСКИЙ И ФРАНЦУЗСКИЙ ЯЗЫКИ)

DAS KULTURELLE LEBEN VON DER DONEZKER REGION.

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Donezk ist die „Stadt der Millionen von Rosen“. Es erhielt diesen Namen aus einem Grund: Schließlich weiß jeder, der jemals in Donezk war, aus erster Hand, wie viele Rosen in Parks, auf Boulevards, in Höfen und entlang von Straßen gepflanzt werden. Donezk ist jedoch immer noch ein großes Industrie-, Verwaltungs-, Kultur- und Bildungszentrum mit einer entwickelten Infrastruktur. Ein charakteristisches Merkmal der kulturellen Entwicklung in Donbass war die hohe Schöpfungsrate der materiellen Basis der Kultur. In der Stadt Donezk wurde ein breites Netzwerk von Kulturinstitutionen geschaffen - insgesamt 8330. Die Stadt hat drei staatliche Theater, eine regionale Philharmonie, einen Zirkus, 20 Kinos, 53 Kulturhäuser, 140 Museen und Museumsräume, darunter ein regionales Kunstmuseum, rund 450 Bibliotheken (einschließlich Schulbibliotheken), ein Planetarium.

Die Philharmonie von Donezk ist eine der ältesten Konzertorganisationen, die mit Recht auf jeden Tag Ihrer Geschichte stolz sein kann. Alles begann im Jahr 1931, als die Schaffung des Gebiets von Donezk nur geplant war. In der Zeitung "Diktatur der Arbeit" erschien die Ankündigung über die Gründung einer Philharmonie als Konzertorganisation in Donbass, die zeigen sollte, dass es im jungen Land der Sowjets einen Platz für hohe Kunst gibt.

Während des großen Vaterländischen Krieges wurde die Konzerttätigkeit der Philharmonie von Donezk aufgehört. Viele Künstler gingen an die Front: einige mit den Waffen in der Hand, und andere als Mitglieder der Front-Konzert-Brigaden. Die

Donezker Solisten und Musiker setzten fort, den Leuten schöne Musik, gute Lieder zu geben. Mit ihrer Tätigkeit haben sie zum Sieg inspiriert. Zu Beginn des großen Vaterländischen Krieges befand sich im Gebäude der Philharmonie das Hauptquartier der 383-Bergmanns-Schützendivision. Während der deutschen Besatzung druckten die Untergrundkämpfer hier antifaschistische Flugblätter aus. Davon zeugen die Gedenktafeln an der Fassade der Philharmonie. Das Gebäude selbst ist ein Denkmal des kulturellen Erbes.

Und sofort nach der Befreiung des Donbass von den Faschisten im September 1943 nahm die Philharmonie von Donezk Ihre Tätigkeit wieder auf. Am Anfang wurden die Konzerte im Gebäude des Kinihauses namens Schewtschenko. Im September 1944 öffnete die Philharmonie ihre Türen für die Zuschauer. Dort konnte man schon die wunderbare Musik von Beethoven und Bach, Schostakowitsch und Rachmaninow, die Lieder der damals berühmten Komponisten hören.

Ein besonderer Meilenstein in der Geschichte der Philharmonie von Donezk ist die Installation der berühmten, historischen Orgel im Jahr 1959. Orgelkonzerte wurden sofort populär und bleiben bis heute so. Es sollte auch erwähnt werden, dass Tschaikowsky selbst auf dieser Orgel spielte. Seit 1981 findet in Donezk das Festival «Prokofjew Frühling» statt, dessen Hauptkonzertbühne die Philharmonie von Donezk ist.

Die Donezker Philharmonie ist mit Recht auf Ihren Konzertsaal stolz. Zur Jubiläumskonzertsaison wurde ihre Bühne rekonstruiert, das Design verfeinert. Im Jahr 1991 wurde dem Konzertsaal der Name des hervorragenden Komponisten, Sergej Prokofjew verliehen, der in Donbass geboren wurde. Traditionell und beliebt sind auch die Festivals "Donezker Edelsteine», «April Blagovest», «Kristallsaiten», «Piano-Forum», "Jazz-Forum", sowie Festivals der geistlichen Musik, Kammermusik, Orgelmusik und andere.

Die kreative Biographie des staatlichen akademischen Musik- und Schauspieltheaters von Donezk begann 1927 in Charkow. Die Grundlage der Truppe des Theaters waren die Schauspieler des Theaters «Beresil», und der Gründer war

der Student von W. Nemirowitsch-Dantschenko, der berühmte Regisseur A. Зараров, aber bald übernahm der Regisseur V. Wassilko die künstlerische Leitung des Theaters.

Im Jahr 1933 ist das damals ausgereifte kreative Kollektiv nach Donezk ungezogen. Die künstlerische Tätigkeit des Theaters in der Region war von der Schaffung vieler Aufführungen geprägt, die nach ihrer Bedeutung zur Schatzkammer der Theaterkunst gehören.

Das Theater ist zum Zentrum der Theaterkultur der Region Donezk geworden und behauptete die universellen humanistischen Ideale mit Hilfe von dem nationalen und weltklassischen und modernen dramaturgischen Erbes.

Außer der Truppe von Schauspielern des Dramas arbeitet das Theater mit einem hochprofessionellen Orchester, einer Gruppe von Sängern und einer Balletttruppe. Dies gibt die Möglichkeit, komplexe Kunstprojekte durchzuführen und in verschiedenen Genres zu arbeiten. Das hohe künstlerische Niveau der Theateraufführungen wurde von vielen namhaften Theaterkritikern immer wieder betont.

Neben den Haupt-, experimentellen und Kleinen Bühnen wurde eine weitere Bühne mit 40 Plätzen (im Theaterrestaurant «Premier») im Theater eröffnet, die den Namen «Theaterzimmer» erhielt. Im Dezember 2011 wurde die fünfte Bühne «Roter Saal» eröffnet, wo das Stück «Maria Callas: ein Leben ohne Liebe» aufgeführt wurde.

Im September 2001 wurde der Titel „akademisch“, am 28. November 2009 – der Status „national“ verliehen. Nach den Ergebnissen der Arbeit für 2007 wurde Donetsk musikalisch-Dramatisches Theater mit dem Ehrendiplom und der Goldmedaille «Branchenführer» ausgezeichnet. Das Donezker Theater heißt heute das Donezker Staatlichen Akademischen Musiktheater.

Lange Zeit arbeitete das Theater im Donezker Musiktheater (seit 1947 — Donezker Opern-und Balletttheater). Das heutige Theatergebäude, das in Form eines

antiken griechischen Tempels ausgeführt ist, wurde vom Architekten E. N. Chechik 1961 gebaut.

Anatoly Solowjanenko ist ein sowjetischer ukrainischer Opernsänger. Volkskünstler der UdSSR. Das Denkmal ist eine Skulptur von Anatoly Solowjanenko in voller Größe, gekleidet in einem Konzertkostüm des Herzogs aus Giuseppe Verdis Oper «Rigoletto». Die Skulptur steht auf einem Sockel in runder Form, der auf Zylindern ruht, die die Theatersäulen symbolisieren. Das Denkmal wird aus Bronze gemacht und ist mit Blattgold überzogen. Die Höhe des Denkmals beträgt 3,5 Meter.

Während des großen Vaterländischen Krieges wurden die Teile der Truppe, in das Dorf Sazanovka in der Kirgisischen Republik evakuiert. Später, im Juni 1942, zog das Kollektiv des Theaters in die Stadt Przewalsk. Dort hat das Theater von Donetsk Konzerttätigkeit in Krankenhäusern, militärischen Gruppen, vor Arbeitern ausgeführt, und hat auch an der Schaffung neuer Aufführungen gearbeitet.

Im Juli 1943 wurde das Theater in die Frontoper Stalino umbenannt.

Ende Januar 1944 kehrten die Künstler der Leitung von Regisseur Alexander Zdichowski, Künstler Eduard Ljachowitsch ins Theater zurück und im September fand zu Ehren des ersten Jahrestages der Befreiung des Donbass von den deutschen Truppen, im Theater die Premiere von Borodins Oper «Fürst Igor» statt.

TURISMO COSTERO EN ESPAÑA

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España es un paraíso para los amantes de la playa. El mar Mediterráneo dio un clima cálido y templado inolvidable.

La soleada España está bañada por las aguas del Océano Atlántico y el Mar Mediterráneo, atrayendo a turistas de todo el mundo con una gran cantidad de hermosas playas. La costa está dividida en norte, sur y centro. Las costas más populares: Costa del Sol, Costa del Garraf, Costa Blanca, Costa Brava, Costa Dorada, Costa de la Luc, Costa Cálida, Costa de Almería, Costa Assar. Vamos a conocer las más famosas de ellas.

Costa del sol. La costa más meridional de España es la Costa del Sol, que se traduce como "playa soleada". Las vacaciones en los resorts de la Costa del Sol se consideran las más prestigiosas, especialmente en los resorts de Marbella, Fuengirola, Benalmádena, Torremolinos y Estepona. En Torremolinos vale la pena visitar el templo de San Miguel, la torre árabe del Tore, construida en el siglo XIV, y el molino de Molino de la Bovedo. Benalmádena es el hogar del hermoso puerto de Puerto Marina, el famoso Castillo de Colomares y el Acuario Sea Life, y Fuengirolle alberga uno de los zoológicos más populares de España. Cerca de Marbella se encuentra la zona de élite de Puerto Banús, un lugar para que gente famosa se relaje y yates caros. Costa del Sol tiene un ambiente andaluz especial, clubes de deportes acuáticos, hoteles elegantes y muchas oportunidades para aquellos que quieren divertirse.

Costa del Garraf: La Costa del Garraf se extiende desde Barcelona hasta Cubellas. Encantadora por su hermosa naturaleza y magnífico clima, la Costa del Garraf tiene muchas cosas atractivas para los viajeros. Este lugar combina a la perfección el rico pasado con los logros de la moderna industria del spa, se han creado condiciones especiales tanto para vacaciones masivas como de élite. En el centro de la Costa del Garraf, que se extiende al sur de Barcelona, se encuentra su balneario más popular, Sitges, (35 km al sur de Barcelona), la antigua ciudad catalana y el balneario más popular de la costa.

Costa Blanca: La costa blanca de España, la Costa Blanca, arenas blancas como la nieve tiene un clima inusualmente cálido. La arquitectura de las ciudades de la Costa Blanca está representada por monumentos de la época romana, castillos medievales y edificios más modernos de varios estilos. Los resorts más populares

aquí son Gandía, Villajoyosa, Jávea, Cullera, San Juan de Alicante, Torrevieja, Águilas, Cartagena y Mojácar. El centro de la Costa Blanca se ha convertido en la ciudad de Benidorm, famosa por sus lujosos hoteles, playas y discotecas. Cerca de Benidorm se encuentra el popular parque de atracciones Terra Mítica.

Costa Brava: La Costa Brava se encuentra en la parte noreste de España. El nombre de la costa significa "costa salvaje", y consiste, de acuerdo con su nombre, en acantilados inexpugnables rodeados de bosques de coníferas con misteriosas grutas y acogedoras bahías. Costa Brava es merecidamente considerada una de las partes más pintorescas de la costa española. Y hay algo que ver aquí: es aquí donde se encuentran el Museo del Teatro Salvador Dalí y los antiguos dólmenes, y cuando escalas las montañas también puedes ver las ruinas de los castillos. En el monte Werder se encuentra el monasterio de San Pedro de Rodas y las ruinas del castillo de Werder. Los centros turísticos populares en la Costa Brava son Tossa de Mar, Playa de Aro, Loret de Mar, Blanes, Roses y Palamós.

Costa Dorada: La Costa Dorada o Gold Coast es una parte de la costa catalana, bañada por el Mar Balear y nombrada en honor a las playas de arena dorada. El centro de la Costa Dorada es la ciudad de Salou, y los centros turísticos más populares de la costa son Tarragona, La Pineda, Reus y Cambrils. En Salou, hay un parque de atracciones Port Aventura, dividido en seis zonas temáticas y que atrae a muchos turistas con un ambiente increíble y una gran cantidad de atracciones diferentes. En La Pineda también hay un parque de atracciones, Aquapolis, aunque tiene un tamaño un poco más modesto y un delfinario. Cambrils no puede presumir de un programa de entretenimiento tan rico, pero hay un museo de esmeraldas y un par de hermosas iglesias antiguas: la Iglesia de Santa María del siglo XV y la capilla del Santuario de la Verge del Cami. En general, la Costa Daurada atrae a turistas principalmente con excelentes condiciones para practicar todo tipo de deportes acuáticos, y especialmente vela y windsurf.

Costa de la Luc: En el extremo suroeste de España, en la costa, bañada por el Océano Atlántico, en las provincias de Cádiz y Huelva, hay una zona turística. El

aliento del mar se siente en las calles de Cádiz, porque la ciudad está ubicada en una península que se conecta a la costa con solo una estrecha franja de tierra. Cádiz se divide estrictamente en dos partes. La nueva ciudad se retira del mar en lo profundo de la costa, y la Ciudad Vieja se encuentra al final de un largo asador de nueve kilómetros que sobresale en el mar. En Cádiz, el esplendor barroco de las iglesias es adyacente al concurrido barrio portuario, y las espaciosas plazas neoclásicas se encuentran con antiguos castillos y una fortaleza. Hay magníficos paseos marítimos y excelentes playas en la ciudad. Por cierto, pintorescas playas, bordeadas de pinos y dunas de arena, se extienden a lo largo de toda la costa de la Costa de la Luz.

España es un lugar donde realmente puede ahogarse en los cálidos rayos del sol cegador y en la suave arena del mar de numerosas y diversas playas. El clima, las playas, los atractivos turísticos como toda la infraestructura turística permiten desarrollar el turismo costero a más alto nivel y a todos los gustos.

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LAS NOTABILIDADES TURÍSTICAS DE MADRID

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De día, de tarde y de noche la capital de España enamora al viajero con sus mil rincones por descubrir. Se trata de uno de esos lugares que no se deben de visitar,

se deben de vivir. ¿Por qué? Porque es la mejor manera de traspasar su fina piel y de unirse a sus liturgias, a sus tapas, a su vida en la calle y a sus ruidosas terrazas.

Comencemos con la calle más famosa de Madrid es La Gran Vía. La Gran Vía es la calle que visitar en Madrid y un paseo imprescindible para todos los que visitan la ciudad. Su construcción se remonta a principios de siglo XX, en el que se construyeron grandes edificios como el Grassy, el de Telefónica o el Edificio Metrópolis, uno de nuestros favoritos que ver en Madrid. Esta calle en la que no puedes dejar de mirar a todos lados mientras andas, es famosa también por sus grandes teatros. Además, la Gran Vía es uno de los principales ejes comerciales de la ciudad, en la que se encuentran tiendas de ropa y calzado de grandes marcas nacionales y internacionales. Cerca hay un lugar de interés turístico es la Puerta del Sol. En la Puerta del Sol encontraréis tres lugares muy conocidos a nivel nacional: Estatua del Oso y el Madroño que son uno de los símbolos de Madrid, El Reloj de la Casa de Correos, Kilómetro Cero.

Otra notabilidad famosa de Madrid es La Plaza Mayor. Se encuentra en el centro de Madrid a pocos metros de la Puerta del Sol. En la construcción de la plaza intervinieron varios arquitectos, entre los que destacan Juan de Herrera y Juan Gómez de Mora, ya que fueron los verdaderos creadores. Con el paso del tiempo y los distintos incendios sufridos, la Plaza Mayor ha sido reconstruida y reformada en varias ocasiones a lo largo de la historia. En la Plaza mayor podemos encontrar tres lugares de especial interés: Estatua de Felipe III, Casa de la Panadería, El Arco de Cuchilleros, el popular Bar La Campana. Si tu visita a Madrid es en época navideña, no puedes perderte el mercadillo navideño, que se monta en este punto de la ciudad.

Es importante tener en cuenta que Madrid es una gran ciudad cultural con importantes museos de todo el mundo.

El Museo del Prado: El Museo del Prado es el museo más conocido de Madrid y uno de los museos de arte más importantes del mundo. El museo es obra de Juan de Villanueva y se inauguró en 1819. La colección del Museo del Prado se basa principalmente en pinturas de los siglos XVI al XIX. Entre sus cuadros cuenta con

obras maestras de pintores de la talla de Velázquez, El Greco, Rubens, El Bosco o Goya.

Museo Reina Sofía: El Museo Nacional Centro de Arte Reina Sofía es uno de los museos más importantes de Madrid y ofrece al visitante una extensa colección de obras de arte contemporáneo español. El Museo Reina Sofía ofrece al visitante amplias colecciones de cuadros de pintores españoles tan importantes como Pablo Picasso, Salvador Dalí y Joan Miró.

Museo Thyssen-Bornemisza: El Museo Thyssen-Bornemisza es uno de los museos de arte más importantes de Madrid y complementa las colecciones del Museo del Prado y Museo Reina Sofía. La colección del Museo Thyssen-Bornemisza se compone de cerca de 1000 obras que el Estado español compró a la familia Thyssen-Bornemisza en julio de 1993. Entre los artistas internacionales más relevantes, destacan obras de Van Eyck, Van Gogh, Caravaggio y Edvard Munch, entre otros.

Parque del Retiro, uno de los lugares que visitar en Madrid. Es uno de los principales parques de Madrid desde su inauguración en 1868. Su nombre completo es Parque del Buen Retiro. En el Retiro hay cientos de rincones que visitar y actividades que disfrutar: espectáculos de marionetas, músicos, lectores de manos, adivinos y videntes son algunas de las distracciones habituales.

Además, Madrid es conocida por sus distritos que difieren entre sí.

Malasaña: Lugar de origen de la movida madrileña durante los años 70 y 80, este barrio 'oficioso' es una auténtica joya del paisaje urbano de la capital.

Arguelles: Este barrio madrileño del distrito Moncloa-Aravaca es el lugar ideal para vivir en un entorno tranquilo, aún estando en el centro de Madrid. Todo su lado occidental es un auténtico balcón hacia el Parque del Oeste, entorno natural que arroja sobre las fachadas de los edificios un panorama envidiable.

Recoletos: Cuando uno escucha este nombre lo asocia inmediatamente al sustantivo 'lujo'. Y es que este barrio del distrito de Salamanca es parte de la famosa 'Milla de Oro' de Madrid, en la que las más renombradas firmas de moda, joyerías,

tiendas de antigüedades, galerías de arte y carísimos restaurantes se aúnan en no más de un kilómetro cuadrado.

Huertas: También conocido como 'Barrio de las Letras', fue en su momento lugar de demora de grandes literatos como Miguel de Cervantes, Lope de Vega, Góngora o Quevedo.

Chueca: Barrio extraordinario del centro de Madrid, original, cosmopolita, vanguardista, atractivo, elegante. Y es que la comunidad gay ha sabido tomar las riendas de este barrio y hacer de él un verdadero epicentro de diversidad y entretenimiento.

En conclusión podemos decir que Madrid tiene muchos atractivos, adecuados para cualquier tipo de turismo, como el gastronómico, comercial, cognitivo y muchos otros. Esto es lo que hace que la ciudad sea tan popular entre los turistas.

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LAS RUTAS TURÍSTICAS DE BARCELONA

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Barcelona es una de las ciudades más visitadas de Europa. Barcelona ofrece un gran variado programa de actividades. Aquí podemos ver calles ruidosas y acogedoras, la arquitectura del gran maestro, hermosas vistas y mucho más.

Punto de partida de la mayoría de los visitantes de Barcelona es la Plaza de Cataluña. Un lugar de encuentro para personas y palomas. La Rambla es un paseo de 1,2 kilómetros de la Plaza de Cataluña hacia el puerto, con un promedio de más de 200 mil visitantes por día. Los artistas se encuentran en la parte baja de la Rambla. Vamos más allá.

El mercado Mercat de la Boquería es uno de los mercados más bonitos de la Península Ibérica. Todos los días aquí se compran y venden miles de productos frescos.

La Plaza Real es un punto de encuentro y lugar de descanso de muchos visitantes a la ciudad y el punto de partida para excursiones en la Ciutat Vella, el centro histórico de Barcelona y las calles comerciales de los alrededores.

Barcelona está llena de descubrimientos arquitectónicos, que están en buena condición. Una Casa Batlló y Casa Mila. A que no saben que el creador de Star Wars, George Lucas, fue inspirado por las torres del edificio, e hizo que el casco de Darth Vader se viera mucho. Destacan de los edificios de Antonio Gaudí, que ha influido fuertemente en la cara de Barcelona.

Las esquinas del Ensanche tienen una forma particular. Al mirar un mapa, es fácil reconocer el barrio de Barcelona conocido como el Ensanche (Eixample, en catalán). Su patrón perfecto de cuadrícula hace que la imagen aérea sea bastante llamativa. De hecho, si miras detenidamente, notarás que las esquinas de cada bloque de edificios están cortadas. En consecuencia, tienen forma de octágonos en vez de cuadrados. Este diseño tan peculiar se tomó en cuenta para permitir que los tranvías de la ciudad pudieran girar en las esquinas de forma segura.

La mayor obra de Antonio Gaudí, la Sagrada Familia, es una basílica Católica Romana. La construcción comenzó en 1882 y es probable que completara en 2026. El que quiere visitar el interior de la iglesia debe llegar a las 9:00 de la mañana cuando se abre la iglesia. La cola es a cualquier hora del día tan larga como las colas frente a los ascensores de la Torre Eiffel en París.

El Parque Güell fue creado por Antonio Gaudí en los años 1900 a 1914 y es debido a su arquitectura y sus puntos de vista sobre la ciudad una de las atracciones principales de Barcelona [1].

Podemos observar el antiguo puerto, el acuario y las playas cercanas, son más atracciones de Barcelona. El viaje con el funicular desde el puerto hasta la montaña de Montjuic es un viaje precioso, con una vista impresionante. A unos pocos cientos de metros se encuentra un otro funicular hasta el Castell de Montjuic. Desde allí se puede disfrutar una vez más la hermosa vista sobre Barcelona.

Barcelona es conocida por ser una de las mejores ciudades playeras del mundo. De hecho, muchos turistas se acercan en verano para disfrutar del sol y la arena. Lo curioso es que Barcelona no tenía playas hasta principios de los 90. Te preguntas cómo es eso posible. Verás, para los Juegos Olímpicos de 1992, el ayuntamiento ordenó la creación de una playa artificial desde la punta de la Barceloneta hasta Pueblo Nuevo. Antes de ello, el paseo marítimo era tan solo un páramo rocoso, donde se habían levantado algunas casas de pescadores y cabañas.

Como sabéis, Barcelona es la capital del fútbol en el mundo. Tiene el estadio de fútbol más grande de Europa. El Estadio Camp Nou, es la sede del mundialmente reconocido Fútbol Club Barcelona. Este estadio es el más grande de Europa y el quinto más grande del mundo. Puede reunir a unos 99.354 espectadores, y se dice que hay planes de agrandar su capacidad de aforo. El Camp Nou es una de las atracciones más populares en la ciudad. En parte, esto se debe al Museo del FC Barcelona, que también es uno de los museos más visitados de la ciudad [2].

Barcelona es una ciudad hermosa que está envuelta en muchos secretos, y todos definitivamente deberían visitarla.

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CURIOSIDADES TURÍSTICAS DE ZUYEVKA

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El desarrollo de las direcciones perspectivas y prioritarias en la esfera del turismo de la República popular de Donetsk debe basarse en la capacidad turística existente, teniendo en cuenta las posibilidades regionales condicionadas por las características naturales, climáticas, culturales y económicas. Una de las prioridades es el turismo interno, cuyo desarrollo puede aumentar el atractivo de la región.

Objetivo: aumentar el atractivo turístico de las atracciones turísticas del Parque de Paisaje Republicano "Zuevsky" con el fin de desarrollar el turismo interior en la República popular de Donetsk.

El desarrollo del turismo interno depende en gran medida de los programas y las medidas, que tienen como objetivo el desarrollo de las condiciones modernas del descanso, que abastecen las organizaciones Resort-turísticas por la maquinaria moderna y las tecnologías.

El turismo interno es una variedad de viajes que realizan las personas dentro de su país de residencia. Incluye numerosas excursiones y excursiones por los lugares históricos; vacaciones en el complejo que permite relajarse y distraerse del ajetreo laboral; el descanso con tratamientos medicinales y de carácter profiláctico en el territorio de los sanatorios y los preventorios medicinales; vacaciones de invierno; vacaciones de verano.

Hoy en día en el territorio de cada estado se desarrolla rápidamente el turismo interior, adquiere cada día más importancia entre los turistas y trae grandes ganancias a la economía del país.

En la República popular de Donetsk muy cerca de Donetsk, en la región de Khartsyz, hay un lugar único, el poblado Zuyevka y el Parque de Paisaje "Zuyevskiy".

Aquí hay muchos lugares para descansar, realizar diferentes actividades a todos los gustos, pasar tiempo disfrutando de los paisajes magníficos, nadar en lago, visitar museo. En el territorio del parque nacional del paisaje "Zuyevskiy" se encuentran muchos lugares de interés turístico: lago de Medveja; rincón del paraíso del hombre de la familia Kachurinh; Museo de conchas y moluscos; finca y sótanos de Ilovayskiy; Embalse de Olkhov.

Todos los turistas pueden alojarse en el pequeño hotel "Campamento de la salud" donde tienen la posibilidad de degustar un menú vegetariano y tomar un masaje diario. El parque es famoso por las colinas rocosas, la estepa y los bosques, las plantas, muchos de los cuales están sujetos a la protección y el mundo animal diverso, algunos de los cuales están inscritos en el libro Rojo.

En el territorio del parque se puede practicar el turismo extremo, de aventura, cognitivo y ambiental. Muchos turistas vienen a los festivales ambientales concurren "La República Estudiantil", "La Convención de ecología y turismo", "la búsqueda de la Juventud", "Zuyevgrad". Aquí se celebran las competiciones internacionales de escalada.

El desarrollo del turismo interno en la República popular de Donetsk es una parte integral del desarrollo de la economía y el estado en su conjunto. Zuevka es un lugar perfecto para la promoción de los distintos tipos del turismo, ya que goza de una gran reserva natural. Hoy día es necesario aumentar el atractivo turístico de los lugares de interés del Parque de Paisaje Republicano "Zuyevsky" para el desarrollo del turismo interior en la República popular de Donetsk. Gracias al desarrollo del

turismo interno en Zuyevka aparecerán nuevos puestos de trabajo, un gran flujo de personas y el aumento de las ganancias, lo que tendrá un impacto beneficioso para el desarrollo económico de la región.

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LA NOUVELLE VAGUE DU CINEMA FRANÇAIS

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La Nouvelle Vague française est l'un des mouvements les plus célèbres de l'histoire du cinéma mondial. C'est un mouvement du cinéma français né à la fin des années 1950 et qui a duré une dizaine d'années jusqu'à la fin des années 1960. Il rassemble des réalisateurs qui ont tourné leurs premiers longs métrages à cette période. Les figures emblématiques en sont notamment Jean-Luc Godard, François Truffaut, Éric Rohmer, Claude Chabrol, Jacques Rivette, Alain Resnais, Louis Malle, Agnès Varda et Jacques Demy.

L'expression «La Nouvelle Vague» est communément utilisée pour décrire la nouvelle génération de cinéastes français. «La Nouvelle Vague» est en fait un véritable raz-de-marée. Ces jeunes cinéastes anti-conformistes vont bousculer les règles très établies du cinéma français et permettre ainsi à un nouveau cinéma d'émerger: le cinéma d'auteur [1].

François Truffaut ou Alain Resnais, qui, dès 1959, présentaient, pour le premier «Les quatre Cents Coups», pour le second «Hiroshima mon amour», ou bien encore Jean-Luc Godard qui signe «A bout de souffle» en 1960. Mais, bien que son apport bénéfique soit aujourd'hui unanimement reconnu, la grande liberté prise lors des tournages de ces mises en scène n'est, à l'époque, pas appréciée par plusieurs traditionalistes du cinéma, habitués à respecter un certain nombre de règles. Ce qu'ils n'admettent pas, c'est de voir ce petit groupe de jeunes critiques, désigné sous le nom de nouvelle vague, qui se lance dans la réalisation en pensant que désormais tout est possible. Or, c'est justement grâce à l'audace de ces nouveaux venus que le septième art, alors en train de lentement se scléroser, revit et découvre un nouvel horizon à conquérir. En suivant, en partie, l'exemple du néoréalisme italien, qui avait fait éruption au milieu des années 1940, la nouvelle vague française abandonne les décors de studios, bien souvent trop lourds à financer, et décide de descendre dans la rue pour y placer les caméras [2].

Ces jeunes cinéastes en herbe en ont marre de l'académisme cinématographique dans lequel s'est enfermée la France depuis de nombreuses années. François Truffaut dénonce «une certaine tendance du cinéma français» dans Les Cahiers du Cinéma en 1954 dans lequel il déplore le conformisme des anciens, «le cinéma de papa» et la surenchère à l'esthétisme et aux beaux dialogues. Il condamne le fossé entre la réalité et sa représentation à l'écran.

Grâce aux progrès techniques de l'époque (caméra légère et bon marché, pellicule sensible à la lumière du jour permettant les tournages hors studios, son synchrone de qualité), ils accèdent enfin à la réalisation. Les budgets sont souvent modestes (Claude Chabrol tourne «Le Beau Serge» grâce à un héritage familial) et ces réalisateurs de fortune n'ont aucune ou quasiment aucune expérience dans la mise en scène mais ils se lancent dans l'aventure...

Dès lors, s'en est fini des décors soignés, des tournages en studio, des beaux dialogues, des histoires irréelles, des têtes d'affiches. Place aux inconnus, aux tournages dans la rue, aux histoires simples, parfois autobiographiques, et bien

souvent à l'improvisation. On filme la vie! Le cinéma gagne en naturel et en simplicité [1].

Cinéma traditionnel	Nouvelle Vague
Tournages en studio	Tournages en extérieur
Caméra de studio	Caméra légère et portable
Beaux décors	Décors naturels
Acteurs célèbres	Acteurs inconnus
Dialogues sophistiqués	Dialogues simples, souvent improvisés
Gros budgets	Petits budgets
Grande équipe	Equipe minimale
Histoires complexes	Histoires simples, parfois autobiographiques
Beaucoup de règles	Pas de règles

Qu'importe, le public s'enthousiasme pour ces films à l'aspect amateur, si différents des films d'alors et le succès est immédiat. De nouveaux visages apparaissent sur les écrans tels Jean-Paul Belmondo, Jeanne Moreau, Jean-Claude Brialy, Bernadette Lafond, Jean-Pierre Léaud.

L'aventure économique de la Nouvelle Vague a ainsi duré six ans. L'héritage technique: caméra légère et recours à des pellicules plus sensibles permettant de tourner dans la rue sans l'éclairage des studios, durera plus longtemps, s'étendra aux pays de l'Est, au Brésil, au Canada, en Allemagne, au Japon, au

Brésil. Esthétiquement, la Nouvelle Vague se perpétue jusqu'à nos jours par la poursuite de la carrière de ses principales personnalités et de nouvelles: Desplechin, Bonitzer, Asayas, Honoré [3]. Nul ne conteste aujourd'hui l'importance historique, économique et même technique de la Nouvelle vague française. Ce qui est remis en cause et régulièrement attaqué c'est son importance esthétique.

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ANIMACIÓN INFANTIL EN LOS HOTELES DE ESPAÑA

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Hasta la fecha, el negocio hotelero es una parte integral de la industria del turismo. Las empresas hoteleras no solo ofrecen a los turistas habitaciones y comidas estándar, sino que también están interesadas en garantizar que los turistas consuman servicios y satisfagan sus necesidades sin salir del hotel. Por lo tanto, varios servicios no estándar comenzaron a desarrollarse, incluida la animación turística.

Las vacaciones son una oportunidad perfecta para descubrir nuevos destinos y pasar tiempo de calidad en familia. Sin embargo, si los niños no tienen ocasión de divertirse en el destino vacacional, esos días fuera de casa pueden convertirse en una verdadera pesadilla. Para evitar que esto ocurra debéis elegir cuidadosamente vuestro alojamiento, teniendo en cuenta no solo las comodidades que brinda sino también sus opciones de entretenimiento [1].

Animación infantil en los hoteles de España son divertidas, sofisticadas pero económicas, inolvidables y con los mejores profesionales para animar cualquier tipo de evento, fiesta infantil o celebración (con niños y/o adultos). Los animadores se adaptan a sus necesidades, a cualquier imprevisto y al tipo de evento; son creativos y saben hacer su trabajo. La animación infantil es un factor importante para disfrutar de unas magníficas vacaciones en familia [2].

Ofrecen todo tipo de entretenimiento para pasar los momentos más divertidos y entrañables; lo saben que el juego, los momentos lúdicos, la diversión sana son la esencia de la vida, de la infancia feliz y ellos forman y cuidan porque sean realmente especiales.

Los hoteles de España tienen un programa de animación único.

Este programa incluye una serie de juegos que han formado los animadores para sacar el mayor rendimiento a las animaciones, son juegos dinámicos, juegos con música, juegos musicales, pruebas deportivas, de habilidad, son juegos muy participativos.

Aparte de la cantidad de juegos que realizan animadores infantiles en los hoteles hay otras actividades muy chulas: magia, cuentacuentos, títeres, experimentos científicos, pompas de jabón... Si buscas una animación temática podrás pedir la fiesta temática que desees: fiesta de piratas, cumpleaños de princesas y príncipes, fiesta de unicornio, de magos/as, payasos/as, personajes de moda y lo que haga ilusión a tu peque [3].

Animadores infantiles hacen que toda esta cantidad de juegos se presente de forma ordenada, para que tenga sentido la animación, pero sobre todo de forma divertida.

Existen varias claves para que animaciones infantiles salgan tan bien como lo hacen: prestar muchas ganas, corazón e ilusión en todo; animaciones son educativas, los animadores trabajan con niños pequeños que están constantemente aprendiendo; animaciones coloridas, vistosas, los colores intensos ayudan a crear un ambiente divertido, animaciones infantiles muy participativas, los peques son los protagonistas y deben disfrutar de la animación al máximo.

Son animaciones infantiles de calidad, pensadas para hacer disfrutar a cualquier niño ya que se adaptan. Los animadores en cuenta las edades de los niños, las características de estos y el tipo de animación escogido. El lugar donde se realiza la animación es también un factor a tener en cuenta, ya que no posible realizar los mismos juegos en una casa que en un jardín. Las animaciones de fiestas de fin de curso o de colegios son animaciones infantiles más centradas en la música. Y las fiestas de verano, como es lo suyo, están más centradas en el agua, globos, cubos de agua, pistolas de agua...

Animación infantil desarrollada en toda España: Barcelona, Madrid, Bilbao, Sevilla, Mallorca, Valencia, Alicante, Málaga, A coruña, Vigo, Santiago, Murcia, Zaragoza, Oviedo, Gijón, Las palmas, Tenerife, Valladolid, Castellón, Granada, Córdoba, Almería...

Como conclusión, se puede decir que la animación como servicio turístico tiene como objetivo promover activamente el producto turístico y aumentar la rentabilidad del negocio turístico mediante la mejora de la calidad del servicio a los turistas y la ampliación del volumen de servicios prestados. Además, las emociones positivas recibidas por los turistas durante los programas de entretenimiento, los animan a regresar al complejo turístico.

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JEAN-LUC GODARD EST LA LEGENDE DE LA NOUVELLE VAGUE

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Jean-Luc Godard compte parmi ses rares cinéastes qui ont changé l'histoire du cinéma. Son nom est devenu une légende, ses films ont eu une influence phénoménale sur un nombre considérable de réalisateurs depuis cinquante ans. Godard, a bouleversé la manière de faire et penser le cinéma. De toutes les personnalités nées de la Nouvelle Vague, il demeure encore aujourd'hui le plus loué, étudié et respecté partout dans le monde. Ses machines à penser que sont ses films, en dépit d'une audience désormais plus confidentielle, n'ont aucun équivalent dans le paysage contemporain ou passé. Son oeuvre, construite au fil du temps, des époques, ses changements historiques, ses bouleversements sociaux, ses progrès techniques, l'évolution politique du monde, le cheminement intellectuel même de Godard, son rapport à la cinéphilie, a bâti une pensée du cinéma sans commune mesure. Il est un historien des images comme Elie Faure fut un historien de l'art. Ses films, qui chacun

tente de poser un problème à résoudre, un «comment ça va» comme disait Deleuze, forment un long work in progress dialectique du cinéma resitué dans l'Histoire et plus largement celle de la représentation. Voir un film de Godard relève d'une expérience intellectuelle fondée sur de solides régimes d'associations, de confrontations, de juxtapositions, de dialogues, de déconstructions, où le montage est souverain. Son cinéma est une pensée elliptique en mouvement, une longue discussion philosophique, théorique, critique, personnelle, où les films, les siens, ceux des autres, la peinture, les livres, la musique, s'enchevêtrent, se répondent, s'échangent, pour inventer un grand collage analytique du monde avec l'art [1].

Dès «A bout de souffle» (1959), son premier long métrage, Jean-Luc Godard s'impose par un trait novateur, en rupture totale avec les formes du cinéma traditionnel: Jean-Paul Belmondo y vole une voiture, tue un motard, tombe amoureux et meurt. Le but de Godard n'est pas de raconter une histoire, mais d'en proposer la lecture critique du genre, en l'occurrence le thriller américain. Ce film devient l'oeuvre phare du cinéma de la Nouvelle Vague, dont Godard devient l'un des représentants emblématiques. «*Le Petit Soldat*», réalisé l'année suivante, est interdit pendant trois ans par la censure en raison de son actualité brûlante: il pose les doutes d'un déserteur passé à l'OAS durant la guerre d'Algérie. Anna Karina, qui y interprète le rôle principal, apparaît de nouveau dans «*Vivre sa vie*» (1962). La prostitution, thème de ce film traité à partir de vrais témoignages, reflète le sentiment d'aliénation qu'éprouve le réalisateur au coeur du monde. «*Le Mépris*» (1963), avec Brigitte Bardot et Michel Piccoli, d'après le roman de Moravia, dénonce les dégâts d'une prostitution subtile, érigée en phénomène social à part entière. Godard continue son exploration des rapports humains régis par le monde moderne. Histoire d'un homme en quête de l'amour fou, «*Pierrot le Fou*» (1965) met en scène Jean-Paul Belmondo, nouveau héros romantique prisonnier d'une intrigue policière tragique. Ce film marque la fin de la période encore romanesque et poétique de Godard. Le réalisateur va désormais rétrécir les trames narratives au profit d'expériences formelles et de nouvelles thématiques. Dans «*La Chinoise*» (1967) Godard décrit comment un

groupe d'étudiants fonde une cellule marxiste pendant leurs vacances, sorte de préfiguration des événements de mai 68. Le réalisateur s'intéresse de plus en plus au côté politique que peut revêtir le cinéma. D'où «*Le Gai Savoir*» (1967) qui soumet toute création authentique au dénigrement systématique de l'esthétique bourgeoise. Fondu dans le groupe Dziga Vetov, qui prône de nouvelles formes esthétiques au service du message politique, le réalisateur s'oriente vers le militantisme: «*Vent d'Est et Pravda*» (1969)», ou encore «*Vladimir et Rosa*» (1970). «*Tout va bien*» (1972) signe le retour du réalisateur au cinéma traditionnel [2]. Il était provocateur, impertinent, libertaire, drôle, inventif... Inspirateur de la nouvelle vague, il a bouleversé en profondeur le cinéma français en réduisant en miettes tous les dogmes antérieurs, avec un style inimitable.

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TURISMO EDUCATIVO EN ESPAÑA

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España es un país con mucho que ver. Ciudades cosmopolitas llenas de arte, pueblos llenos de encanto y cultura y una gran variedad de paisajes hacen que España sea un destino imprescindible en la lista de lugares que conocer de cualquier viajero.

España combina armoniosamente el lujo y la grandeza de los monumentos antiguos, que el mundo entero admira hasta nuestros días. La cultura y la arquitectura del país es interesante porque fue creado por diferentes pueblos durante cientos de años, como resultado de lo cual el patrimonio histórico de España en su belleza virgen se convirtió en la encarnación de su mentalidad y color nacional.

Muchos turistas comienzan a explorar las vistas desde Barcelona. En esta ciudad se encuentra la Catedral de la Sagrada Familia. La construcción se inició hace más de 135 años y la diseñó el extravagante arquitecto español, Antonio Gaudí. Aunque sigue en construcción, este edificio religioso es una de las atracciones turísticas más famosas de España. Uno de los principales atractivos del lugar es su impresionante fachada de estilo modernista. Su interior, que parece un enorme bosque de piedra, atrae inmediatamente la atención de todos los visitantes. Además, el edificio cuenta con 18 torres: 12 de ellas dedicadas a los apóstoles, cuatro a los evangelistas, una a María y otra a Jesús.

Monte Tibidabo: su altura es de 500 metros. Hoy alberga la torre de televisión, así como un impresionante parque con entretenimiento extremo interesante y un museo que se centra en el tema de los juguetes mecánicos. Se complementa perfectamente con el templo del Sagrado Corazón, sobre el cual se encuentra una estatua de Jesús.

Muralla de Ávila: esta construcción medieval es otro destino imprescindible que ver en España. Construida con ladrillo, granito y escombros de antiguos edificios romanos de la ciudad, la Muralla de Ávila se construyó para **proteger la ciudad de los invasores** y hoy en día, **es un vestigio de la historia militar** de la ciudad y del país.

La muralla **tiene una extensión de más 2.5 kilómetros** y pese a no ser la única muralla de Europa, puede decirse que es la **mejor conservada hasta el momento** y es que pese a tener **más de 1000 años de antigüedad**, está casi intacta. Gracias a su **valor histórico y cultural**, se nombró **Monumento Nacional** en el año 1884 y **Patrimonio de la Humanidad por la UNESCO** en el año 1985.

En la isla de Homero, el Parque Nacional de Garahonay merece atención. El parque lleva el nombre de los amantes guanches Gara y Honay. Gara era una princesa en la isla de La Gomera, Honay, hijo de un rey de Tenerife. Se conocieron en el festival anual de La Gomera y se enamoraron. El día que se anunció el compromiso, el volcán Teide en Tenerife comenzó a estallar, como si desaprobara lo que estaba sucediendo. Los padres de los jóvenes consideraron esto como un signo desagradable y cancelaron el compromiso. Honay tuvo que regresar a Tenerife, pero una noche nadó a través del estrecho entre las islas para encontrarse con su amante. Huyeron a los bosques de Homero. Los padres de los fugitivos enviaron un escuadrón de búsqueda tras ellos. Pronto los jóvenes fueron alcanzados en la montaña, donde decidieron despedirse de la vida juntos.

Pasamos a otro lugar de interés turístico. Como resultado de la actividad volcánica en la isla de Lanzarote, se formó la cueva de la Cueva de los Verdes. Su longitud es de más de 6 km y la profundidad alcanza los 35 metros. Hace más de 5,000 años se formó una cueva como resultado de la próxima erupción del volcán Korona. La Cueva de los Verdes es una de las cuevas volcánicas más grandes del mundo y se considera una de las más cómodas para visitar. Debido al microclima único que se ha desarrollado durante todo el año, la temperatura del aire en la cueva se mantiene sin cambios a unos 19 grados centígrados. Se ofrece a los turistas que bajen a la cueva a través de una entrada natural ubicada en la meseta de lava de Mal País; más de 1,000 metros de túneles están disponibles para que los viajeros caminen.

En Granada, más que en otros lugares, se siente el patrimonio de los pueblos orientales. La atracción principal de Granada es el Palacio de la Alhambra, también conocido como el "Castillo Rojo". Es interesante que sus paredes puedan cambiar su color según la hora del día y el grado de iluminación. Las dimensiones del palacio son asombrosas, y muchos historiadores e investigadores lo llaman "una ciudad en una ciudad".

La ciudad provincial de Toledo, construida sobre una hermosa colina, merece especial atención. En vista de esto, fue inexpugnable durante muchos años y, por lo

tanto, se ganó el nombre correspondiente Ascendió. La arquitectura de la ciudad es diversa e impresionante con su belleza, su parte histórica en 1986 fue incluida en la Lista del Patrimonio Mundial de la UNESCO. La ciudad se ha convertido en un lugar especial para el brillante artista español El Greco, y hay todas las oportunidades para disfrutar de sus creaciones, por ejemplo, su obra "Tormenta en Toledo".

España protege con mucho amor sus páginas del pasado. Los turistas tienen muchas cosas por descubrir en este país mágico. Cada rincón de España les ofrece a sus visitantes una visita inolvidable y los deja con ganas de conocer mucho más.

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EXCURSIONES AL MUSEO SALVADOR DALI DE BARCELONA

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En Figueres, provincia de Girona, se encuentra uno de los museos más visitados de Cataluña y de toda España: el Teatro-Museo Dalí. Este peculiar museo rinde homenaje al excéntrico genio local Salvador Dalí, el gran artista del surrealismo. El museo Dalí de Figueres está localizado 140km de Barcelona y es

hogar de las fantásticas obras surrealistas de Dalí. Salvador Dalí fue un renombrado pintor surrealista nacido en Figueres en 1904 [1].

El museo fue construido a partir de las ruinas de un teatro y convertido en lo que se puede ver hoy – una bizarra pero impresionante mezcla de las extrañas y maravillosas creaciones de la mente de Dalí. El museo Dalí es el segundo museo más visitado en España, después del Prado. Ya seas un apasionado del arte o si solo tienes un interés en Dalí, esta es una visita esencial en Barcelona.

El Teatro-Museo Dalí se inauguró en 1974. Fue construido sobre los restos del antiguo Teatro Municipal de Figueres por varios motivos: por ser Dalí un «pintor teatral», por estar junto a la iglesia donde había hecho la comunión y por ser el lugar de su primera exposición. El propio Dalí diseñó hasta el más mínimo detalle del museo para asegurarse de que el visitante experimentara su obra como se merecía [2].

El museo Dalí esta muy comprometido con su personalidad única y estilo representado en el edificio y arte, lo cual lo hace único entre otros museos. Dalí diseñó el lugar hasta los últimos años de su vida, hasta el más mínimo detalle. Antes de siquiera poner un pie en el museo, el edificio prepara la escena para comenzar a explorar las piezas surrealistas de Dalí en exposición. Las paredes exteriores están cubiertas con pan Catalán hecho en yeso como decoración y la cima del museo esta hermosamente decorada con maniqués dorados y huevos gigantes. Aún aquellos que no están usualmente interesados en museos de arte no pueden evitar disfrutar de los trabajos mostrados aquí. Este es un museo sumamente divertido para que todas las familias y personas de cualquier edad conozcan.

A la entrada del museo si vas a patio, puedes ver el Cadillac, y encima del capo del coche hay una fascinante y bastante creativa escultura de una mujer. Puedes ver la pared exterior que contiene muchos más maniqués dorados. Una vez dentro del edificio en si, hay una gran pintura hecha por Dalí. Esta pintura parece tener varias figuras de la Venus de Milo, pero si entrecierras los ojos, la pintura parece transformarse en la cara de Abraham Lincoln.

Para continuar la visita hay que cruzar el escenario y descender a la planta baja. En esta parte del recorrido destaca la «Sala de las Pescaderías», donde sobresalen «Autorretrato blando con bacon frito» (1941) y «Retrato de Pablo Picasso en el siglo XXI» (1947). Y justo debajo del escenario, donde ya pudimos ver la lápida de su tumba, se encuentra la Cripta de Dalí, con su nombre, su título de «Marqués de Púbol» y los años de su nacimiento y defunción.

Hay aproximadamente 5 salas en el edificio circular, completamente llena de obras de Dalí. Ya en la salida pareciera como si se hubiera construido para que fuera difícil salir de allí, lo cual seguramente era lo que se había propuesto el artista. Puedes salir a través de la tienda de regalos en el sótano, donde puedes comprar algunos souvenirs antes de salir. También puedes visitar el Museo de Joyas Dalí, el cual se encuentra solo una esquina del museo.

El ticket de entrada nos permite acceder también a la exposición permanente «Dalí Joies», ubicada justo a mano derecha según abandonamos el museo. En este pequeño espacio se exhiben 39 joyas diseñadas por Dalí y algunos de sus bocetos originales. «Labios de rubí», «El ojo del tiempo», «El corazón real» o «El elefante espacial» son algunas de las joyas más impactantes.

El Teatro-Museo Dalí es uno de los museos más peculiares de España. También es uno de los más visitados y es que su contenido está dedicado a uno de los artistas más universales y polémicos del siglo XX: Salvador Dalí. Sumérgete en el universo de Dalí conociendo este sorprendente museo ubicado en Figueras, a una hora y media de Barcelona.

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DIE BESONDERHEITEN DER SEHENSWÜRDIGKEITEN VON DONEZK.

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Die östlich gelegene Millionenstadt Donezk ist das Verwaltungszentrum der gleichnamigen Region. Von 1869 bis 1923 hieß er in Erinnerung an seinen Gründer John Hughes Jusowka. Dann hieß es Stalin und seit 1961 hat es den modernen Namen. Die Stadt hat eine reiche Geschichte, die mit der Entwicklung der Industrie verbunden ist. Gleichzeitig ist es ein berühmtes kulturelles Zentrum geworden. Es werden offiziell über 250 Denkmäler des kulturellen Erbes registriert. Es lockt Gäste mit den besten Hotels, den modernsten Sport- und Unterhaltungsmöglichkeiten.

Unsere Stadt ist etwa 150 Jahre alt, und sie begann ihr Leben dank einem Briten – John Hughes. Als er mit seiner Familie im Alter von 50 Jahren ankam, baute er das erste Stahlwerk, um das sich Jusowka entstand.

Der Mini-Park Pervomaisky befindet sich im nördlichen Teil des Hauptplatzes von Donezk, direkt hinter dem Lenin Denkmal. Bis 1927 wurde dieser Platz Heuplatz genannt, weil es einen großen Heumarkt (am Stadtrand von Jusowka) gab.

Zum architektonischen Ensemble dieses Parks gehören:

Skulptur "Jugend",

Die Laube mit der Brücke über dem Wasser

Im August 2008 wurde hier ein neuer Brunnen eröffnet, in dessen Mitte sich eine Laube von Liebenden befindet. Dank dieser Laube wurde der Platz des ersten Mai sofort in den Platz der Verliebten umbenannt, und er wurde zum Wallfahrtsort der Brautpaare. Die Skulptur "Jugend" wurde vom ukrainischen Bildhauer Nikolay Bilyk geschaffen und am 9. Juli 2008 eröffnet. Die Höhe der Skulptur beträgt 3 Meter 15 Zentimeter, das Gewicht der Skulptur beträgt 5 Tonnen. Sie ist aus Carrara-Marmor gefertigt und ist die Figur eines halbnackten Mädchens. Dieses Mädchen ist die Heldin des Gedichts von Vladimir Matwijenko, dessen Vierzeiler auf einem Stein neben der Skulptur geschlagen werden:

Barfuß ja durch den Tau,
in einem halb gesteppten Bademantel.
Gold des aufgelösten Zopfes
die Jugend war im Morgenrauen.

Während der Stadtfeste finden hier oft Showprogramme, Festivals von Kunst und Handwerk, sowie auch die Konzerte der kreativen Kollektivs statt.

Puschkin Boulevard - eines der beliebtesten Urlaubsziele, sowohl für die Gäste der Stadt als auch für die Bewohner von Donezk, war und ist der malerische Boulevard, der nach dem hervorragenden russischen Dichter Alexander Sergejewitsch Puschkin benannt wurde. Nur wenige wissen, dass der Boulevard auf dem Gelände der Anfang der 50er Jahre zerstörten Ziegelei entstanden ist. Die Grundsteinlegung des Boulevards wurde 1947 begonnen. Im Laufe der langen Jahre hat sich das Aussehen des Boulevards ständig geändert, bevor es wirklich ein Juwel der architektonischen Landschaft von Donezk wurde.

Halbkilometer langer Boulevard ist in mehrere Themenbereiche unterteilt. Eine große Anzahl von Brunnen, üppige Bäume, bunte Blumenbeete, exotische Pflanzen, Dekorative Kompositionen, Spielplätze, Cafés und Restaurants für jeden Geschmack schmücken ihn. Aber der Boulevard ist nicht nur dafür berühmt. Einige der interessantesten und geheimnisvollsten Kreationen, die die Aufmerksamkeit der

Touristen und Bewohner von Donezk auf sich ziehen, sind die Skulpturen des Puschkin-Boulevards.

Auf dem Boulevard gibt es viele Brunnen, unter denen die geschmiedete Skulptur - der Brunnen «des Flusses Donbass» besonders hervorgehoben wird. Diese Gruppenarbeit wurde im Jahr 2007 unter der Leitung des berühmten Schmieds der Stadt Burduk V. I. auf dem Puschkin-Boulevard installiert. Die Skulptur ist in Form eines Kosakenbootes ausgeführt, dessen Segel die offenen und erhobenen Flügel darstellen. An Bord des Bootes sind die größten Flüsse der Region Donezk vorgestellt: Seversky Donez, Kalmius, Bachmut, Krynka, Mius und Kalchik.

Dort kann man auch ein sehr interessantes Objekt beobachten. Das ist die Merzalow-Palme, eine erstaunliche Skulptur in Form von Palmen, geschmiedet vom Schmied Alexej Iwanowitsch Merzalow aus einem Stück Stahl am Ende des neunzehnten Jahrhunderts. Sie hat eine Auszeichnung des Grand Prix der Pariser Internationalen Industrie-Ausstellung 1900.

Die Original- Palme wird im Museum des Berginstituts in St. Petersburg aufbewahrt. In Donezk wurde die erste Kopie 1999 in der Nähe vom Ausstellungszentrum "Expo-Donbass" errichtet, die zweite ist direkt hier - auf dem Puschkin Boulevard neben dem Gebäude von der Donezker öffentlichen Regionalregierung. Die Merzalov-Palme ist ein Symbol für die Wiedergeburt des unabhängigen und mächtigen Industriestaats. Die Herstellung der Palme wurde mit der 16. Allrussischen Industrie-und Kunstausstellung, die im Jahr 1896 in Nowgorod stattfand, verbunden.

In dieser Ausstellung wurde die Palme als eines der Exponate des Pavillons der «Noworossijsker Gesellschaft für Kohle -, Eisen-und Schienenproduktion» ausgestellt. Es wurde Ende 1895 von einem Schmied des Stahlwerks A.I. Merzalov geschmiedet. Die Arbeiter des gleichen Werks halfen ihm, besonders der Schmied Philip Fedotowitsch Schkarin.

Das Bild der Palme befindet sich auf dem Wappen der Region Donezk und ist eine direkte Bestätigung der geschickten Meisterschaft und Fleiß.

TURISMO EN EL PARQUÉ REPUBLICANO DE PAISAJES “ZUYEVSKIY”

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Hoy en día, el turismo se desarrolla rápidamente en todo el mundo. La República popular de Donetsk no es una excepción. En la República popular de Donetsk hay muchos lugares donde se pueden desarrollar diversos tipos de turismo como: el turismo de salud y bienestar, turismo de playa, ecoturismo, turismo extremo, turismo cognitivo, etc.

En la localidad de Sedovo se desarrolla activamente el turismo de playa, así como el de la salud y el bienestar debido a los baños de barro curativos que se encuentran ahí. En el pueblo de Zuevka está desarrollado el turismo ecológico, gracias a un gran parque paisajístico, esta zona cuenta también con desarrollo en el área del turismo extremo específicamente para los aficionados a la escalada, y el turismo cognitivo, ya que en esa zona está ubicado un gran Museo de conchas de almejas.

A continuación veremos de forma más detallada el turismo ecológico, extremo e informativo que se ve en la aldea de Zuevka:

Zuevka se distingue por su atrayente relieve, debido a que cuenta con un escalador natural que posee buenas características para practicar la escalada en roca, además este territorio cuenta con unos paisajes hermosos que tienen un atractivo

singular y posee grandes cantidades de agua dulce entre los cuales se puede encontrar el río Nizhnyaya Krynka y por supuesto el embalse Nizhnekrynskiy.

El ecoturismo es un turismo natural que incluye el estudio del medio (tanto natural como cultural). En este tipo de turismo los espacios naturales son protegidos por su especial diversidad y por los programas de conservación que en ellos se desarrollan. El turismo ecológico debe tener las siguientes características tanto para quienes ofrecen los servicios como para sus beneficiarios:

Contribuir a la conservación de del entorno sociocultural;

Construir el respeto y la conciencia ambiental y cultural creando asociaciones equitativas con la naturaleza;

Minimizar los impactos negativos para el medio ambiente y la comunidad que genera la actividad;

Proporcionar el desarrollo económico y sostenible en las zonas en las que se lleva a cabo la actividad;

El turismo extremo está asociado al deporte de las personas valientes, las cuales habiendo superado las dificultades prueban lo inagotables que son las posibilidades de un ser humano. El deporte extremo ayuda a forjar el carácter de una persona.

El turismo extremo tiene ciertas peculiaridades las cuales además del placer lleva un peligro muy real. Las principales características de este tipo de turismo son:

La organización es compleja. Hoy en día son muy pocas las firmas turísticas que se ocupan de la selección y la organización de viajes extremos. Por lo general, se trata de empresarios privados que no dan garantías de seguridad a los participantes.

Se necesita un instructor personal. El turismo extremo es un tipo de turismo muy peligroso y una persona sin el debido entrenamiento, para su seguridad, sin duda debe ir acompañada de un instructor calificado. Es necesario realizar entrenamientos previos ya que este tipo de turismo, requiere una buena condición física, resistencia,

exposición. Dichos entrenamientos se realizan en centros de entrenamiento especiales, bases, instalaciones equipadas para formar las habilidades necesarias.

Es necesario tener en cuenta las condiciones climáticas debido a que el clima juega un papel importante, y a veces incluso crucial en el turismo extremo. Es cierto que los seres humanos tenemos una capacidad de adaptación sorprendente, pero cabe tener en cuenta que hay límites, sobre todo cuando se trata de temperaturas y factores secundarios como pueden ser la presión, la humedad o la propia calidad del aire. El clima también afecta el estado de ánimo y el sueño.

En el ejemplo de Zuevka este tipo de turismo se da gracias al muro natural para la escalada, donde cada año se lleva a cabo "Donbass Extreme Fest" que reúne miles de personas aficionadas al deporte extremo.

El turismo cognitivo es un pequeño viaje durante el cual usted visita una o más ciudades, se familiariza con su historia, cultura, lugares de interés, costumbres y tradiciones, lo que aporta una gran cantidad de experiencias agradables. Se desarrolló debido a las peculiaridades del paisaje, las condiciones naturales y climáticas, así como la experiencia centenaria del desarrollo cultural e histórico. Este tipo de turismo abarca muchos aspectos: permite conocer la forma en que viven las personas en otros países, su cultura, sus costumbres, además de ser uno de los medios para establecer y mantener vínculos culturales y la cooperación internacional.

En Zuevka este tipo de turismo se ve gracias al Museo de conchas de almejas, Sótanos de Ilovaysk, etc.

Gracias al asentamiento de estos tipos de turismo, el flujo turístico en la República popular de Donetsk tiene tendencias a aumentar cada vez mas y mas. Como conclusión, quisiera decir que nuestra República tiene un enorme potencial para el desarrollo de diversos tipos de turismo, esto ayudara a generar una mejora en la industria y la economía de la república.

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DAS HISTORISCHE UND KULTURELLE ERBE VON DONBASS.

Die Donezker Denkmäler.

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Donezk ist das Herz von Donbass. Im Jahr 2019 wurde es 150 Jahre alt, und im Laufe der Jahre gelang es Donezk, eine Reihe von Legenden zu pflegen, seine Geschichte ist voll von Geheimnissen und Sagen, und die Straßen haben eine jahrhundertealte Entwicklung. Während dieser langen Zeit ist die Stadt gewachsen und hat viele historische und kulturelle Objekte angesammelt: Museen, Theater, Philharmonie, Denkmäler, Gassen und andere. Die Stadt ist daran sehr reich. Jedes dieser Objekte spielte eine Rolle in der Geschichte von Donezk, und wir werden heute einige davon betrachten.

Das Lenin-Denkmal in Donezk ist die Dominante des hauptstädtischen Platzes. Die Skulptur wurde 1967 zu Ehren des 50. Jahrestages der großen Oktoberrevolution geschaffen. Das Denkmal selbst ist aus Bronze gegossen.

Die Komposition, die aus dem Lenin Denkmal und dem dreieckigen Pylon besteht, der wenige Meter von ihm entfernt steht, wurde nach dem Projekt des Bildhauers Kuntsewitsch geschaffen. Die Arbeit der Architekten wurde von den Meistern Nikolai und Ivan Iwantschenko durchgeführt. Auf dem Pylon wird das Zitat von Iljitsch eingraviert "Donbass, es ist — kein zufälliger Bezirk, und es ist-der Bezirk, ohne den der sozialistische Aufbau einfach, ein guter Wunsch bleiben wird".

Die Figur von Iljitsch ist in vollem Wachstum ausgeführt, der Führer steht auf einem Granitsockel. Das Gesicht ist nach dem Süden gerichtet, der Blick ist in Richtung des Stahlwerks gerichtet, das die lange Zeit den Namen Vladimir Iljitsch trug. Zusammen mit dem Sockel beträgt die Höhe des Lenin Denkmals ungefähr 13,5 Meter. Neben der Skulptur erhebt sich ein Pylon aus Edelstahl. Seine Höhe erreicht 42 Meter. Der Pylon und Sockel sind auf einem Granit-Stylobat installiert.

Im Juni 1969 wurde das Puschkin-Denkmal auf dem Puschkin-Boulevard hinter dem Donezker Akademischen Musik- und Schauspieltheater eröffnet. Die Autoren der Komposition waren der Architekt J. I. Tomillo und der Bildhauer N. A. Ginsburg.

Das Denkmal ist eine Bronzestatuette, deren Höhe 1,2 Meter beträgt. Die Arbeiter des Eisenwerkes haben die Büste geschaffen. Das Denkmal wurde auf einem Sockel errichtet, der aus vier rechteckigen Blöcken bestand, die mit Platten aus schwarzem Granit ausgekleidet waren.

Im Jahr 2000 wurde der Sockel durch eine Säule ersetzt, und auf der Vorderseite wurde ein Faksimile von Puschkin graviert.

Die Eröffnung der Skulptur wurde mit wichtigen Ereignissen verbunden – zum 170-jährig Jubiläum des Dichters und zum 100-jährigen Jubiläum der Stadt. Derzeit ist um das Denkmal ein malerischer Platz angelegt, der eine einzigartige romantische Umgebung schafft. Vor der Puschkin Skulptur werden oft Veranstaltungen zum Tag der russischen Sprache.

Unter der hiesigen Bevölkerung, insbesondere der Jugend, wird dieses Denkmal nur als Kopf bezeichnet. Hier versammeln sich Gruppen von Skatern oder Radfahrern.

Zwölf Jahre lang galt das Denkmal für Taras Schewtschenko vor dem Erscheinen von bronzenem Wladimir Lenin auf dem gleichnamigen Platz im Jahr 1967 als das Hauptdenkmal in unserem Regionalzentrum. Es kann auch das romantischste Denkmal genannt werden, weil die jungen Leute in den 80-er Jahren des vergangenen Jahrhunderts am Fuße des großen ukrainischen Dichters ihre Datings hatten. Dieses Denkmal hat auch seine eigene Geschichte.

Das Denkmal ist eine Figur des Dichters in vollem Wachstum, aus Bronze. Die Skulptur steht auf einem Runden Sockel aus dem roten polierten Granit. Auf dem Sockel befindet sich ein Fries, auf dem die Helden der Werke von Taras Schewtschenko abgebildet sind. In der Mitte des Fries ist er selbst dargestellt, der seine Gedichte Nikolai Gawrilowitsch Tschernyschewsky und Nikolaj Alexandrowitsch Dobroljubow vorliest. Die Skulptur wurde in Kiew hergestellt und von dort nach Donezk gebracht.

Das erste Denkmal, das man das Original nennen kann, wurde um 4 Jahre früher als in Stalino, — am 1. Juli 1951 errichtet. Dieses Ereignis fand in... Kanada statt! Er erschien im Oakville Park der Stadt Toronto. Es war ein Geschenk vom ukrainischen sowjetischen Volk den Ukrainern Kanadas am Tag Kanadas und zu Ehren des 60-jährigen Jubiläums der ukrainischen Diaspora in diesem Land. Es hatte nur einen anderen als in unserer Stadt.

Doch mit dem kanadischen Kobsar ist eine tragische Geschichte verbunden. Er stand bis Ende Dezember 2006 ganz sicher im Park von Toronto. Dann passierte ihm ein Unglück, dessen Rätsel und Motive bis heute nicht bekannt sind. Stellen Sie sich vor, Taras Shevchenko aus Bronze wurde... gestohlen! Direkt von seinem Sockel! Unbekannte Täter ließen nur einen Teil des Fußes des Dichterdenkmals. Nach Angaben der Polizei in Toronto planten die Angreifer, die Statue auf Schrott zu

übergeben. Zu den damaligen Preisen konnte es für 20 Tausend kanadische Dollar verkauft werden. Dieser Akt des Vandalismus ist bis jetzt nicht aufgeklärt.

DIE HISTORISCHEN BESONDERHEITEN DER WICHTIGSTEN GEDENKSTÄTTEN VON DONBASS.

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Donezk ist eine erstaunliche Mischung: Kohlengruben werden mit Plätzen, Parks und botanischen Gärten kombiniert. Es gibt viele Orte in der Stadt, wo Sie sich entspannen können. Donezk eignet sich sowohl für Outdoor-Enthusiasten als auch für diejenigen, die einen abendlichen Spaziergang machen und die Sehenswürdigkeiten bewundern möchten. Jede Stadt hat eine Geschichte und Helden. Donezk ist eine junge Stadt und kann sich daher keiner reichen Vergangenheit rühmen. Sein offizielles Geburtsdatum ist 1869 - der Beginn des Baus einer metallurgischen Anlage. Infolgedessen ist unsere Stadt Donezk, die früher Jusowka und dann Stalino hieß, erst 150 Jahre alt. In so kurzer Zeit gelang es der Hauptstadt Donbass jedoch, auf ihren Freiflächen eine kleine Geschichte ihres „Lebens“ festzuhalten. Jetzt gibt es in Donezk 16 Baudenkmäler und 262 historische und kulturelle Denkmäler - Skulpturen, Gedenktafeln u.a. Der Lenin Platz ist der Hauptplatz in der Stadt, an diesem Ort finden Kundgebungen und Feste statt, er ist einer der Lieblingsplätze für die Erholung der Donezker Bürger.

Er entstand auf dem Gelände des Heumarktes, der sich am Stadtrand von Jusowka befand. Das architektonische Ensemble des Platzes wurde hauptsächlich von 1927 bis 1967 gebildet. Vor Beginn der Arbeiten an der Bildung der modernen

architektonischen Gestalt war der Platz von einem einstöckigen Wohn- und Industriebau umgeben.

Das Lenin-Denkmal in Donezk ist die Dominante des hauptstädtischen Platzes. Die Skulptur wurde 1967 zu Ehren des 50. Jahrestages der großen Oktoberrevolution geschaffen. Die Lage des Denkmals wurde aus ideologischen Gründen gewählt. Er sollte nicht so angeordnet sein, dass er mit dem Rücken zu Makejewka (im Osten), dem Gebäude des Ministeriums für Kohleindustrie (im Süden) und dem Gebäude des regionalen Parteikomitees (im Westen) gerichtet ist, so dass die Skulptur nach Süden und mit dem Rücken nach Norden liegt. Das Denkmal selbst ist aus Bronze gegossen.

Die Komposition, die aus dem Lenin Denkmal und dem dreieckigen Pylon besteht, der wenige Meter von ihm entfernt steht, wurde nach dem Projekt des Bildhauers Kuntzevitsch geschaffen. Die Arbeit der Architekten wurde von den Meistern Nikolai und Ivan Iwantschenko durchgeführt. Auf dem Pylon wird das Zitat von Iljitsch eingraviert "Donbass, es ist — kein zufälliger Bezirk, und es ist der Bezirk, ohne den der sozialistische Aufbau einfach, ein guter Wunsch bleiben wird".

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Neben der Skulptur erhebt sich ein Pylon aus Edelstahl. Seine Höhe erreicht 42 Meter. Der Pylon und Sockel sind auf einem Granit-Stylobat installiert.

Die Stalino-Bezirkszentralbibliothek wurde nach dem Beschluss des Präsidiums des Stalino-Bezirksausschusses vom 2. August 1926 gegründet, um die kulturellen Bedürfnisse der Bewohner der Stadt zu befriedigen. 1932 wurde die Bibliothek in eine regionale reorganisiert, und den Namen von N. K. Krupskaya trägt

sie seit 1936, was aus den gedruckten Quellen bekannt ist, aber es gibt keine dokumentarische Bestätigung dafür.

1926 hat man in den Räumen des Klubs namens. F. Engels (das ehemalige Theater der Tudor-Brüder) für die Bibliothek einige Räume bekommen. Die Fakten über die Geschichte des Gebäudes sind sehr gering, aber nach den Recherchen der Heimatforscher wurde es 1904 gebaut, das Theater der Brüder Tudorowski, Kaufleute jüdischer Herkunft, die erfolgreich in Jusowka im Schuhgeschäft tätig waren. Das Haus im Jugendstil war vor 100 Jahren einer der beliebtesten Orte vom hiesigen Beaumont. Und in den 70-er Jahren des vorigen Jahrhunderts war darin die staatliche ökonomische und technologische Fachschule von Donezk.

Während des großen Vaterländischen Krieges und der Besetzung der Stadt hörte die Bibliothek nicht auf, ihre Leser zu bedienen: in der staatlichen Archiv gibt es die Formulare der Leser von 1942-1943.

Zu Beginn Ihrer Existenz befand sich die Bibliothek an einem anderen Ort und hatte nur einen Leseraum und einen Tresor. Später hat sie nicht einmal ihren Wohnsitz gewechselt, und erst 1939 wurde der erste Flügel der Bibliothek gebaut, jetzt gehört dieser Flügel zur Kinderbibliothek, aber während des zweiten Weltkriegs wurde der Bau gestoppt und in den 50er Jahren wieder aufgenommen.

Das Gebäude im Stil des stalinistischen Empire ist durch die raffinierte Schönheit und verborgene Kraft, lebensbejahende Größe und unvergleichliche Monumentalität sehr attraktiv. Der abgewinkelte Teil der Bibliothek, der in Form einer Trommel gebaut ist, wird von korinthischen Halbsäulen umrahmt, die dem Gebäude eine nachgeprüfte Anmut und harmonische Proportionalität verleihen. Gekrönt wird das vierstöckige Gebäude durch eine Stahlkuppel.

Die Bibliothek ist das Zentrum des kulturellen Lebens der Republik, der geistlichen Wiedergeburt und Konsolidierung und der massive Komplex der Kulturveranstaltungen, die von den Mitarbeitern der Bibliothek organisiert und durchgeführt werden.

VIAJE POR LAS RUTAS DE LAS ANTIGUAS CIVILIZACIONES DE AMÉRICA LATINA

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Sudamérica tiene una historia muy amplia, la cual combina a numerosas culturas y civilizaciones. En la antigüedad hubo una gran cantidad de poblaciones aborígenes, que se desarrollaron sin contacto alguno con las civilizaciones de los demás continentes. Las más importantes de dichas poblaciones fueron los Incas.

La civilización inca es una de las más antiguas de América del Sur. Originalmente una tribu india de la familia de lenguas quechuas, que habitó el territorio del Perú moderno en los siglos XI-XIII, más tarde la capa dominante, así como el gobernante supremo en el estado Tauantinsuyu que formaron (siglo XV). Los incas no eran dueños de la rueda, pero tenían un sistema de carreteras altamente desarrollado que ayudaba a mantener la integridad del estado. Los incas realizaron operaciones quirúrgicas complejas, dominaron el arte de la momificación, construyeron edificios de piedra sin usar cemento, mientras que sus edificios resistieron terremotos en los que los edificios españoles posteriores colapsaron.

Para los incas, la división del poder y la sociedad en guerreros y no guerreros era característica. Los principales comandantes y líderes militares fueron los gobernantes del Imperio o las personas que designaron del grupo étnico gobernante: los incas. Al mismo tiempo, parece, sin embargo, había una especie de doble poder: un duumvirato completo: cuando el gobernante (gobernador) de la ciudad de Cuzco se dedicaba a las actividades económicas del Imperio, suministrando y proporcionando tropas, como el historiador Juan de Betanzos menciona repetidamente.

En la cima de su existencia, el Imperio Incaico fue uno de los estados más grandes de la Tierra. El número de súbditos del imperio alcanzó, según diversas fuentes, de 5-6 a 12 millones de personas.

Junto con Kalka, los incas también recurrieron a la llamada carta nodular, transmitiendo principalmente información económica.

Para "registrar" todo lo que sucedió, los incas usaron un dispositivo hecho de cuerdas anudadas, que se llamó "paca" y sirvió para preservar la información histórica, el censo en la provincia y calcular la cosecha. Kipu (traducido del idioma quechua - "nudo") es un cordón con una longitud de al menos 30 cm. Además, los cordones colgantes están atados al principal, además, de diferentes colores, y los hilos a su vez se apartan de ellos. Están conectados en diferentes lugares por nodos. Cada paca es diferente del resto con una combinación compleja de colores y nudos. Los europeos solo sabían que eran leídos de derecha a izquierda en el cable de la base, pasando por cada uno montado. El significado y el contenido de todo lo "conectado" aún permanece en el nivel de conjetura; Incluso los descendientes modernos de los indios fueron incapaces de descifrar el antiguo sistema Kipu.

La capital y símbolo del imperio era Cuzco, un cuento de hadas hecho de piedra y oro. Aquí estaban la residencia inca, las principales autoridades, el centro ritual y los servicios de la ciudad. Fue un importante centro económico y cultural donde se distribuyeron fondos, se hicieron impuestos y se ubicaron las instituciones educativas más importantes, donde durante cuatro años enseñaron todo lo que los incas lograron.

La ciudad es considerada una de las capitales más grandes del mundo desde la época de la conquista. En el siglo XVI. alrededor de 200 mil habitantes vivían allí y había más de 25 mil casas pintadas en colores brillantes, decoradas con mármol y jaspe, con marcos dorados de puertas y ventanas. En Cuzco incluso había fontanería y alcantarillado. La ciudad fue construida de acuerdo con un plan desarrollado previamente y fue reflexiva. Es sorprendente que una ubicación tan alta de la capital inca (más de 3 mil metros sobre el nivel del mar). El valle en el que se encuentra

Cuzco está rodeado por todos lados por montañas y solo desde el sureste está abierto a la penetración. La forma de la ciudad se parecía al cuerpo de un puma, por eso era un símbolo de la ciudad.

Es muy interesante viajar por las rutas de las antiguas civilizaciones de América Latina. Pero hay que tener en cuenta que los sitios declarados patrimonio de la humanidad por la Unesco están en riesgo. Y el cambio climático es uno de los culpables. Tenemos que entender mejor, vigilar y abordar las amenazas del cambio climático a los sitios del patrimonio mundial.

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EL SISTEMA HOTELERO DE ESPAÑA

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La calidad indispensable de la industria turística es la hotelería.

La calidad de los hoteles españoles es reconocida internacionalmente. Estos se clasifican por estrellas, de 1 a 5, siendo estos últimos los de mayor categoría además de los de Gran Lujo. La categoría se determina según el tamaño de las habitaciones, las instalaciones y servicios que ofrece, los estándares de comodidad. Los turistas pueden encontrar desde hoteles sencillos hasta los más lujosos situados en muchas ocasiones en el centro de las ciudades.

En España hay muchos hoteles de lujo, también muy modestos y económicos, y de una variedad de destinos. Generalmente es posible distinguir tres niveles de los hoteles: los hoteles en la comprensión familiar de la palabra (el hotel), los hoteles baratos (el hostel o la hostería) y el pensión. Situado en el centro y muy cerca de los principales lugares de interés, los turistas pueden elegir entre hoteles de lujo, hoteles de diseño, hoteles románticos, hoteles para familias, hoteles solo para adultos, hoteles para deportistas, hoteles para próximas vacaciones o estancia por motivos de trabajo. Los establecimientos hoteleros de España están cada vez más adaptados para personas con discapacidad.

Los precios varían según la categoría del hotel y las temporadas. Los precios de los hoteles en la costa varían según la temporada: los más altos en agosto y los más altos en otros meses de verano, y los precios para la temporada de invierno se reducen significativamente, lo que atrae a una categoría diferente de turistas[1].

Según la Confederación Española de Hoteles y Alojamientos Turísticos (Cehat), en España no existe un sistema nacional de clasificación para los hoteles sino que cada autonomía tiene su propia normativa si bien las diferencias entre las distintas comunidades autónomas son mínimas. Pero existen unos requisitos técnicos generales independientemente de las estrellas. En esta lista figura el sistema de protección de incendios e insonorización de todas las instalaciones; los precios máximos de los servicios que deben estar expuestos en la recepción en un lugar visible así como la obligación de tener una lista de precios en la habitación de los servicios extra (por ejemplo, teléfono, lavandería, garaje). El hotel además, debe exhibir en la entrada principal una placa normalizada con la categoría [2].

La mayor parte de los mejores hoteles de España se concentran en Baleares, Catalunya, Canarias, Andalucía y las comunidades Valenciana y de Madrid.

Ejemplos de hoteles:

	C antidad de	H otel	Característica
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	estrellas		
.	Una estrella	Hotel El Sid	Se encuentra en Barcelona. Las habitaciones disponen de teléfono, baño completo, aire acondicionado. Precios desde 2500 rub.
.	Dos estrellas	Hostal Venecia	Se encuentra en Valencia. Esta situado en el centro de la ciudad. Cerca del hotel hay muchas cafeterías diferentes. Precios desde 3000 rub.
.	Tres estrellas	Palacio de Santa Inés	Se encuentra en Granada .El Palacio de Santa Ines ocupa un edificio del siglo XVI en Albaixín, declarado Patrimonio de la humanidad por la UNESCO. Precios desde 6500 rub.
.	Cuatro estrellas	El Estival Park hotel	Se encuentra en la Pineda. El Estival Park hotel está cerca de la playa arenosa. El hotel cuenta con un amplio Spa con 9 piscinas y una amplia variedad de tratamientos y servicios. Precios desde 6000 rub
.	Cinco estrellas	El Abadía Retuerta Le Domaine	El mejor hotel de España según los viajeros. Se trata de un establecimiento de cinco estrellas situado entre viñedos en una antigua abadía del siglo XII restaurada con mimo, en el que los clientes encontrarán mucha tranquilidad y la posibilidad de disfrutar de la buena mesa en su restaurante con estrella Michelin. Precios desde 20 000 rub.

Apartamentos turísticos. Normalmente se alquilan por semanas, quincenas o meses. Están equipados con cocina y son muy comunes en las zonas de costa de la Península y en las Islas Canarias y Baleares. Habitualmente se clasifican por llaves, de 1 a 3 y lujo (4 llaves).

Hostales y pensiones. Son alojamientos más económicos que los hoteles y habitualmente también se clasifican por estrellas, de 1 a 3 (aunque algunas Comunidades Autónomas disponen de categorías propias). En algunas ocasiones, sobre todo en las categorías inferiores, varias habitaciones pueden compartir un mismo cuarto de baño.

Alojamientos de turismo rural. También hay muchos hoteles pequeños en el campo y en áreas protegidas. Están diseñados tanto para los españoles que desean

pasar activamente sus días libres como para los extranjeros que están interesados en las características nacionales de la vida del país.

Las casas rurales ofrecen un trato familiar con los propietarios, un ambiente hogareño y una cocina casera. Se pueden alquilar casas completas o habitaciones individuales y resultan ideales para una escapada a la naturaleza. Se clasifican según los niveles de confort y equipamiento.

En España hay algunos hoteles inusuales. Desde cuevas en mitad del desierto a habitaciones que simulan chozas o incluso la posibilidad de dormir en burbujas hinchables. Ejemplos de hoteles inusuales: Isla de El Burguillo, Ávila —alojarse en una isla privada con castillo; Marqués de Riscal, a Luxury Collection hotel destaca por su diseño vanguardista y su "espectáculo de sus formas"; Camping Otro Mundo, Albacete —dormir en pequeñas cúpulas en mitad de la naturaleza; Casas Karen, Cádiz, —chozas en las playas vírgenes de Caños de Meca; Hotel Cueva Huesca —cuevas excavadas en la montaña en el desierto de Los Monegros [3].

En conclusión podemos decir que la infraestructura turística de España está perfectamente desarrollada, tiene calidad y diversidad. Por lo tanto, el sector hotelero de España está bien desarrollado y representado por objetos de diferentes clases y diferentes formas de propiedad. Hay varios tipos de viviendas diferentes entre sí por el nivel de precios, la ubicación y la calidad de los servicios prestados.

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RONDA UNA CIUDAD AL BORDE DEL ABISMO

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Barcelona es una de las ciudades más visitadas de Europa. Barcelona ofrece un gran variado programa de actividades. Aquí podemos ver calles ruidosas y acogedoras, la arquitectura del gran maestro, hermosas vistas y mucho más.

España es un país fascinante y vibrante al cual viajar, pues tiene la suerte de contar con muchísimas ciudades bellas, es el tercer país del mundo con más lugares declarados Patrimonio de la Humanidad por la UNESCO, solo por detrás de Italia y China.

Acercarse a las ciudades Patrimonio de la Humanidad en España es acercarse a la riqueza arquitectónica, histórica y cultural de este país. Madrid, Barcelona, Granada y Valencia, estas ciudades son las más conocidas y visitadas por los turistas; sin embargo más allá de la popularidad, existen otras ciudades de una belleza incalculable y subestimada a las cuales vale la pena viajar si estás en busca de algo un poco diferente y más auténtico. Entre ellas consideramos la ciudad Ronda, ubicada al borde del abismo.

Ronda, una de las ciudades con mayor encanto de Andalucía, se sitúa al noroeste de la provincia de Málaga, a unos 113 km. Esta localidad malagueña divide su casco urbano a ambos lados del Tajo. Su casco antiguo está declarado Bien de Interés Cultural. **Ronda** es una ciudad en la que encontramos en cada esquina algo interesante que ver, por ese motivo es imprescindible dar un paseo y no dejar pasar sus atractivos turísticos.

La historia de Ronda se remonta a la época romana, pero la mayoría de los edificios que se encuentran en el casco antiguo datan de la época en que los moros conquistaron la Península Ibérica. Sin duda, el monumento más emblemático de la

ciudad malagueña de Ronda es el Puente Nuevo. Las casas en Ronda están literalmente colgando de un abismo. La ciudad está unida por el Puente Nuevo, que es el objetivo de todas las cámaras de fotos de quienes visitan Ronda. Construido en el siglo XVIII, este puente de piedra une las impresionantes paredes del cañón de El Tajo, de 120 m de profundidad. El puente conecta el casco antiguo con la parte más nueva de la ciudad.

En Ronda hay mucha historia por descubrir, que ha dejado su huella en el espléndido escenario de la ciudad. Los turistas pueden pasear por las bonitas calles y explorar sus alrededores, visitar muchos edificios, jardines y monumentos interesantes y admirar el legendario cañón por el que corren las aguas del río Guadalevín. En la parte antigua de Ronda, conocida como "La ciudad" se encuentra la Iglesia Mayor, la Iglesia del Espíritu Santo, la casa consistorial, distintos museos, los palacios de Mondragón y Salvatierra, la Casa del Rey Moro por la que se puede bajar al fondo del tajo a través de las escaleras de la mina, la Casa del Gigante, el Almirante de San Sebastián, la desaparecida Iglesia de San Sebastián, la Casa de San Juan Bosco, la Puerta de Felipe V y gran cantidad de casas-palacio, callejuelas y plazuelas.

Colegiata de Santa María de la Encarnación la Mayor La **Colegiata de Santa María de la encarnación la Mayor** se encuentra situada en la Plaza Duquesa de Parcent junto al Ayuntamiento de la ciudad. Pasando la Cuesta de las Imágenes se encuentra el barrio de San Francisco, desde el que se observa la Puerta de Almorábar y la muralla árabe que rodeaba Ronda y que llega hasta el puente árabe en cuyo pie destacan Los **Baños árabes de Ronda**, son los mejor conservados de la Península Ibérica y datan en los siglos XIII-XIV d. C. El edificio está rodeado por un muro de arcos ciegos, que forman el acueducto.

En la zona moderna se encuentra el Parador de Turismo construido sobre lo que antes fue el Ayuntamiento y el mercado de Abastos, el parque de la Alameda con su balconada sobre el tajo, gran cantidad de vegetación y nuevo Teatro Vicente Espinel; las iglesias del Socorro, La Merced, Santa Cecilia y Padre Jesús entre otras,

así como el Templete de la Virgen de los Dolores. La **Plaza de Toros de la Real Maestranza de Caballería de Ronda** es una de las más antiguas de España gracias a su arquitectura, siendo una de las más monumentales que existen. Su existencia representa un capítulo esencial en la historia de la tauromaquia. En el interior de la Plaza de Toros de Ronda se pueden visitar el **museo de tauromaquia, la Real Guarnicionería de la casa de Orleans y la Colección de armas de fuego antiguas.**

Otro lugar de interés es la calle Carrera Espinel, de un kilómetro de longitud y peatonal con nueve tramos, conocida popularmente como calle de la Bola. También en el barrio del Mercadillo se encuentra buena parte del legado artístico modernista y ecléctico de la ciudad, destacando el edificio del Círculo de Artistas o Casino de Ronda, lugar en el que Blas Infante organizó la primera asamblea andaluza.

Ronda puede presumir por su gran cultura musical, allí se celebran tres festivales anuales de música, de pintura, Feria del libro, también se celebran las fiestas tradicionales de Andalucía y otros lugares de España, como son la Cabalgata de Reyes, el carnaval, la Semana Santa, el Corpus y varias ferias y romerías. La Semana Santa de Ronda está declarada de Interés Turístico Nacional de Andalucía. Además, Ronda es una de las sedes de los cursos de verano de la Universidad de Málaga.

Así que, visitar Ronda brinda la oportunidad de entrar en contacto directo con la historia de las civilizaciones. Sus calles, sus monumentos, su cultura, sus fiestas, su gente, su gastronomía y toda la naturaleza que la envuelve hace de esta localidad una de las más emblemáticas de España. Si además aprovechar para explorar su gastronomía, acercarte a sus costumbres y participar de sus fiestas locales, la experiencia será completa y el viaje inolvidable.

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EI SISTEMA DE TRANSPORTE DE ESPAÑA

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España es uno de los países europeos más desarrollados económicamente. Actualmente, España tiene uno de los sistemas de transporte más potentes y óptimos con empresas de infraestructura y transporte en España. Los principales factores que influyen en el esquema de desarrollo y ubicación de los objetos del sistema de transporte de España son: la posición geográfica de España en el mapa mundial, el terreno, la ubicación de la capital en la parte central del país, el acceso al mar, el nivel de desarrollo económico de España, así como la dirección del desarrollo de otros sectores de la economía española.

España tiene diferentes modos de transporte: avión, tren, metro, autobús, etc., que puede elegir de acuerdo a sus necesidades. También puede viajar en taxi o alquilar un automóvil o scooter si tiene una licencia de conducir válida. El transporte turístico está disponible en las principales ciudades, como los trenes y autocares turísticos.

La mayor parte de España tiene acceso al mar, lo que tiene una gran influencia en el desarrollo del sistema de transporte general del país. Históricamente, es una de las principales potencias marítimas del mundo. Los puertos españoles reciben constantemente carga del Mediterráneo y de partes remotas del mundo.

Alrededor de los grandes puertos de España, se han creado sistemas logísticos que incluyen una gran cantidad de almacenes para la consolidación de la carga marítima.

Por separado, debe tenerse en cuenta la orientación turística de la economía local. El papel del turismo aquí es tan grande que su influencia es muy notable en casi todos los sectores de la economía. Todo esto afecta la infraestructura del transporte marítimo. Los principales puertos marítimos del país están bien adaptados para aceptar barcos de pasajeros, y están llenos de prestigiosos cruceros de pasajeros en la "temporada alta"

España tiene muchas compañías aéreas, así como aeropuertos regionales e internacionales. Todas las principales ciudades españolas tienen su propio aeropuerto. Por lo tanto, las compañías aéreas también ofrecen vuelos nacionales y regionales, además de vuelos internacionales [1].

Pero también puede encontrar trenes regionales clásicos, así como trenes turísticos, que le permiten explorar los maravillosos paisajes del país durante los viajes largos. El AVE (Alta Velocidad Española) es el tren de alta velocidad de España que conecta las principales ciudades como Madrid-Barcelona.

El sistema de transporte de España se está desarrollando dinámicamente. Cada ciudad o isla importante tiene un aeropuerto, y los vuelos internacionales llegan a Madrid, Barcelona o Sevilla. En la década de 1980 La reconstrucción de la red ferroviaria comenzó y se completó con éxito, lo que la convirtió en una de las mejores de Europa [2].

En conclusión, podemos decir que el sistema de transporte de España está muy bien desarrollado, en este sentido, el país es visitado por muchos turistas de todo el mundo, ya que puede moverse rápidamente entre ciudades en España. Puede viajar de ciudad en ciudad en tren, y en autobús es más rápido y fácil llegar a ciudades pequeñas. En las zonas rurales, el transporte no va bien, es más fácil llegar en coche. Con las Islas Baleares y con muchos puertos europeos, España está conectada por barcos marítimos.

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EL TURISMO EN COLOMBIA

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Colombia se ubica en noroccidente de América del Sur, es bañado por aguas del Mar Caribe y el Océano Pacífico; además es atravesado por la cordillera de los Andes y la selva amazónica, por eso su biodiversidad es incomparable. Atraídos por sus playas, el abundante patrimonio artístico y cultural del país y la variedad de ofertas gastronómicas millones de turistas acuden cada año. Pero no siempre fue así.

A inicios y mediados de los años 80 la cantidad de turistas que visitaban el país era alrededor de 1,4 millones de extranjeros. Más adelante este numero se redujo a más de la mitad debido a la incrementación de la inseguridad del país. El renacimiento del turismo en Colombia se dio gracias a “La seguridad democrática” que fue una política gubernamental de Álvaro Uribe (Presidente de Colombia del 2002-2010) y las llamadas “Caravanas turísticas” que proporcionaban protección militar a los grupos turísticos que llegaban a los lugares de interés. En el 2002 el turismo en Colombia empezó a tener un notable incremento del 10% anual hasta alcanzar para el 2006 cerca de 1,9 millones de turistas. En el 2018 el país recibió 4,3 millones de visitantes. La mayoría de los turistas extranjeros que visitan Colombia provienen de países vecinos de Latinoamérica y el Caribe, Norteamérica y Europa.

El gobierno del país ha designado varios distritos turísticos como Santa Marta y Cartagena, el archipiélago de San Andrés y Providencia, además los parques nacionales naturales de Colombia y los Territorios Indígenas. Gracias a su gran

variedad de climas, paisajes y exóticos lugares hacen del país un fabuloso lugar. En la Lista de Patrimonio Mundial se encuentran 981 sitios y ocho de ellos (dos sitios naturales y seis bienes culturales) se encuentran en Colombia: **Puerto, Murallas y grupo de Monumentos de Cartagena de Indias, Parque Nacional Natural de Los Katíos, Centro Histórico de Santa Cruz de Mompox, Parque Arqueológico de San Agustín, Parque Arqueológico de Tierradentro, Santuario de Fauna y Flora del Malpelo (Julio de 2006, Paisaje Cultural Cafetero (2011). Patrimonio compartido: Qhapaq Ñan (Sistema Vial Andino). Entre el Patrimonio Cultural Inmaterial de Colombia se destacan:** el Carnaval de Negros y Blancos, las procesiones de Semana Santa de Popayán, el carnaval de Barranquilla.

Uno de los lugares mágicos de Colombia es el Caño Cristales – el río más bonito del mundo, conocido también como el río de 5 colores. Está ubicado en el departamento del Meta, y es una de las joyas naturales del país, uno de los lugares que visitar y un excelente plan **que hacer en Colombia** cuando lo visites por primera vez.

Otro lugar de mucho interés turístico es el Eje Cafetero y sus palmas de cera. **Valle del Cocora**, es el hogar de las palmas más grandes del mundo con más de 60 metros de altura y el símbolo nacional de **Colombia**. Aquí vas a poder experimentar toda la tranquilidad y la belleza de la que dispone el lugar y también disfrutar de los maravillosos paisajes que regala el Eje Cafetero, reconocidos como **Patrimonio de la Humanidad**. Además de eso, el **Valle del Cocora** es la antesala del Parque Nacional de los Nevados y el hogar de una gran Reserva de Colibríes.

Cuando visites **Colombia por primera vez**, tienes que **visitar una perla marítima, la ciudad Santa Marta** que cuenta con uno de los parques naturales más espectaculares que tiene Colombia, y ese es el **Parque Tayrona**. Tiene también más de cien playas donde destacan Bahía Concha y **Playa Cristal**. Entre las montañas se encuentra **Ciudad Perdida**, apodada como la Machu Pichu de **Colombia** y es el **mejor trek de Suramérica**. Otro atractivo es **Minca**, un paraíso en las montañas que debes conocer. Y además de todo eso, **Santa Marta** cuenta con una gran y

excelente oferta de **sitios históricos** y **museos** para visitar, y una variada oferta nocturna para **comer, beber y bailar**. En definitiva, aquí vas a encontrar mucho **que hacer en Colombia cuando la visites por primera vez**.

Guatapé es un pueblecito paisa, de lo más lindos que tiene **Colombia**. Está lleno de casas de colores, y una inmensa roca llamada **el Peñol**, la cual es uno de los principales atractivos del pueblo. Esta gigantesca piedra tiene muchísimas leyendas acerca de su posición en ese lugar, pero lo que realmente sorprende, no son los 700 escalones que hay que subir para llegar a la cima sino los paisajes tan espectaculares que se pueden divisar desde allá arriba. Este es un excelente plan **que hacer en Colombia**, en tu visita a Medellín.

En Colombia se encuentra la capital mundial de la salsa y la feria, es la preciosa ciudad Cali, y no es para menos, ya que todo el mundo sabe bailar y es el hogar de las mejores escuelas de salsa del país, muchas de las cuales son reconocidas mundialmente, pero, esta ciudad ofrece mucho más y aumenta la cuota de los planes **que hacer en Colombia**, como visitar el monumento a Cristo Rey, el hermano del Cristo Redentor del Corcovado en Brasil, subir el Cerro de las Tres Cruces, recorrer el paseo del gato, visitar la casa de Jorge Issacs en el barrio histórico de San Antonio, caminar por el Bulevar del río y bañarse el río Pance. Una excelente temporada para visitar la ciudad es en la Feria de Cali.

Esas y muchas más curiosidades esperan a los turistas que viajan a Colombia. Sin duda, en Colombia hay posibilidades para desarrollar diferentes formas del turismo. La diversidad climática, gastronómica, cultural y de los paisajes, la gente alegre y amable, las tradiciones y huellas históricas, el sistema de los hoteles y restaurantes bien desarrollado, las rutas ecológicas permiten hacerlo y pasarlo muy bien. ¡Bienvenidos a Colombia!

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FRANÇOIS TRUFFAUT, L'UN DES INVENTEURS DE LA NOUVELLE VAGUE

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A la sortie de la Deuxième Guerre mondiale, le cinéma français est en crise. Les jeunes cinéastes ont du mal à trouver leur place, et c'est par le biais de la critique qu'ils expriment leurs revendications. De l'autre côté de l'écran, pour le grand public des années 50, les films au cinéma sont le divertissement par excellence.

François Truffaut d'abord critique de cinéma, il s'oriente vers la réalisation et la production. Partisan d'un cinéma plus libre et moderne, il est l'un des initiateurs du mouvement de la Nouvelle Vague. En quelques années, François Truffaut, avec ses comparses de la Nouvelle Vague Jean-Luc Godard, Eric Rohmer, Jacques Rivette, Jean Douchet, entre autres vont intellectualiser le cinéma en ayant recours aux moyens habituels de l'avant-garde artistique: une critique sévère du passé (parfois injuste en particulier avec les acteurs), l'apologie d'un petit nombre de précurseurs (Hitchcock, Murnau, Rossellini, Fuller, Renoir) et l'expérimentation de méthodes nouvelles de tournage et de production. Tournant le dos à l'académisme qu'ils dénoncent, ces jeunes critiques, devenus scénaristes et réalisateurs, engagent de jeunes acteurs (parfois des amateurs), profitent de la généralisation des caméras légères (inventées pendant la guerre pour les besoins des actualités militaires) et tournent en extérieurs et en décors naturels des films parfois brouillons mais toujours inspirés, où le rejet des conventions s'exprime souvent par un jeu d'acteur décalé, une

caméra très mobile et un montage peu conventionnel. Les sujets surtout recourent les préoccupations de cette jeunesse de la petite bourgeoisie mal à l'aise dans la France post-coloniale qui peine à oublier la collaboration. Un habile compromis entre les codes narratifs de l'avant-garde et la tradition de la comédie de mœurs à la française donne à François Truffaut, réalisateur, une place à part dans la Nouvelle Vague [1].

En 1959, son premier long-métrage, «Les 400 Coups», s'inscrit dans la mouvance de la «Nouvelle Vague». Le film, qui obtient le prix de la meilleure mise en scène au Festival de Cannes en 1959, marque le début d'une longue collaboration avec l'acteur Jean-Pierre Laud. François Truffaut a ralis vingt-et-un longs-mtrages -  raison d'un tournage par an jusqu'en 1982 - parmi lesquels figurent: «Tirez sur le pianiste» en 1961 avec Charles Aznavour, «La nuit amricaine» en 1973, qui lui vaudra l'Oscar du meilleur film tranger, et «Le Dernier Mtro» en 1980 [2].

Rtrospectivement, et malgr sa diversit, toute sa carrire nous parat extrmement cohrente. Il est en tout cas peu de projets qu'il n'aura pas russis,  force de tncit, grce galement  l'autonomie que lui donnait sa structure de production,  mener  terme. Toujours prt  monter en premire ligne dans l'intrt suprieur du cinma franais, fort de ses succs et de sa situation, de fait, de «patron».

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VIAJE POR LA RUTA «CAMINO DE SANTIAGO» EN ESPAÑA

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El Camino de Santiago es una antigua ruta de peregrinación que atraviesa Europa hasta la ciudad española de Santiago de Compostela. Durante su existencia, millones de personas han recorrido esta ruta. Está catalogado por la UNESCO y es un tesoro nacional de España.

La longitud total del sendero es de más de 800 kilómetros. Anteriormente, la ruta era exclusivamente para fines religiosos, pero ahora para inspirarse y disfrutar de un viaje a Portugal, España y Francia. Cada año, el Camino pasa cerca de 250 mil peregrinos de todo el mundo. Santiago de Compostela es considerado el tercer santuario para los católicos después de Roma y Jerusalén. La ruta corre a lo largo del océano, a través de pueblos tranquilos y pintorescos, prados, bosques frescos y termina en la maravillosa ciudad de Santiago de Compostela. Aquí puedes respirar el aire del océano, que lleva el viento, y visitar la hermosa Catedral de Santiago.

No hay un punto de partida oficial para el Camino, pero hay 4 variedades principales: francés, norteño, primitivo y portugués. La ruta francesa es la ruta más popular y, en consecuencia, llena de gente con una infraestructura muy desarrollada. Por lo tanto, se considera una buena opción para principiantes, aunque es la más larga de todas. Comienza en el oeste de Francia, en la pequeña ciudad de Saint-Jean. La mayoría de los peregrinos comienzan desde allí. La ruta del norte se llama la más pintoresca, ya que la mayor parte pasa a lo largo de la costa del Océano Atlántico en el norte de España. El camino primitivo es el más corto, y el portugués es el único que se ejecuta principalmente fuera de España.

El estilo de vida y la vida de los peregrinos es duro y ascético. Levántate en la oscuridad a las 5-6 horas, tarifas, empacando la mochila, desayuno (a menudo pasa sin ella, reemplazando solo con una taza de café). A las 7 en punto comienza. A las 8 a.m., los Albergs cierran para limpiar y prepararse para la recepción de los siguientes peregrinos: durante el día, cada distancia individual es de 7-8 km para alguien, 50 km para alguien. En promedio, toma de 6 a 8 horas completar el curso con descansos, refrigerios y una siesta por la tarde. Algunas personas prefieren ir casi sin parar, otras disfrutan cada kilómetro. Todo depende de los objetivos y motivos del viaje. Luego, regístrate en Alberg en un albergue, ducharse, almorzar / cenar, descansar, "curar heridas", hablar con otros peregrinos, visitar las atracciones locales. En las grandes ciudades, por regla general, se quedan dos o más noches. Cuelgue a las 9-10 en punto de la noche.

Por supuesto, la elección de la distancia que los turistas viajarán individualmente por día. Pequeños pueblos y ciudades se encontrarán cada 3-4 km y harán señas con su color. Puedes quedarte en cualquiera de ellos. Existe la oportunidad de elegir un pueblo tranquilo a orillas del río, relajarse y avanzar con renovado vigor.

No tenga miedo de pasar el Camino de Santiago solo: cada segmento está muy bien marcado con flechas amarillas o conchas doradas, indicarán la dirección correcta en las bifurcaciones o en los lugares donde desaparece el camino. Sin embargo, encontrar una empresa en el camino no es difícil. De otros peregrinos, uno puede esperar historias interesantes, historias sobre lo que los llevó al Camino y lo que quieren recibir al final. Los residentes locales siempre están listos para ayudar y apoyar en los momentos en que desea dejar todo antes de llegar al final.

Casi todos los días, el paisaje a su alrededor cambiará, pero cada vez será fascinantemente hermoso. Después de los Pirineos franceses, uno debería esperar una larga caminata a lo largo del montañoso País Vasco y una caminata aún más larga a lo largo de las estepas de Castilla. Habrá pequeñas ciudades y pueblos desiertos, casi abandonados, entre las estepas quemadas por el sol, cientos de kilómetros de hierba

seca. Será árido y caluroso, pero muy atmosférico. Esto debe ser experimentado, porque luego comenzará la Galicia verde y muy rural, en la que, al parecer, el número de vacas supera a la población local en decenas de veces. El camino estará envuelto en bosques de eucaliptos, en los que es agradable y fácil de respirar, y luego, en las montañas, donde se pueden encontrar los amaneceres más increíbles.

En la parte occidental de Galicia se encuentra adyacente al Océano Atlántico, por lo tanto, se perseguirán pescados y mariscos en este territorio. El plato tradicional es el pulpo, un pulpo cocinado de varias maneras. Vale la pena probar este plato en una de las "pulpas": habrá un mar de impresiones. En los bares rurales más discretos se puede degustar la comida más deliciosa, porque se cocinan mucho en España y con alma.

El lugar más esperado en el Camino es el océano. Santiago está a solo 100 km de distancia, por lo que muchos peregrinos, después de haber recibido un certificado de peregrino y haber notado bien la finalización de su Camino, no lo terminan aquí, sino que van a pequeños pueblos en la costa de Mushia y Fisterra en el Cabo Finisterre.

Hay varias razones para pasar el Camino de Santiago. En primer lugar, establecer una conexión más sutil con uno mismo, la voz interior, la intuición. Para reconocer mejor las señales y sus verdaderas necesidades. Entiende lo que necesitas decir que sí y por qué no. En el Camino, en silencio, en meditación, en movimiento, se fortalece la conexión con uno mismo. En segundo lugar, ampliar los límites de sus capacidades. En primer lugar, el camino es superar el miedo: puede ser el miedo a caminar solo, el miedo a caminar en el bosque, condiciones incómodas, insectos y más. La superación te hace más audaz, aumenta la confianza. Vas a un nuevo nivel de energía. La última razón para fortalecerse físicamente. Caminará una gran cantidad de kilómetros diariamente, su cuerpo se acostumbrará y continuará pidiendo esa carga constantemente. Al regresar a casa, podrá realizar actividades físicas, en este momento para pensar sobre decisiones importantes o simplemente escucharse a sí mismo. Entonces siempre estará en buena forma y lleno de energía.

En el camino, ¡cada momento sientes que estás viviendo! Sientes tu cuerpo, tus pensamientos, te comunicas con personas de edades y visiones del mundo absolutamente diferentes. El camino enseña a ser más simple y muestra que una persona necesita muy poco para ser feliz: tener, dónde dormir, qué comer y personas con ideas afines. Toda la vida es el camino, y vamos a un punto. Lo único importante es que cada individuo, con su propio ritmo, miedos y expectativas. Y lo más importante: es importante ir, no detenerse, confiar en el mundo y vivir el momento.

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EXCURSIÓN POR LA ANTIGUA SALAMANCA

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Salamanca es un pueblo pequeño en España. Te invitamos a descubrir Salamanca. Si no has venido nunca, prepárate para sorprenderte; si ya la conoces, dejáte asombrar una vez más. Te espera una ciudad alegre, universitaria y viva. Es la diversidad de gente: estudiantes, turistas y los propios salmantinos, uno de sus

principales atributos, y son ellos los que otorgan a la ciudad un agradable ambiente, fresco y joven. La ciudad está siempre abierta, dispuesta a acoger y entregar la riqueza de su patrimonio, su cultura y su gastronomía. La ciudad es Patrimonio de la Humanidad, y tiene multitud de rincones y edificios históricos; todos ellos están concentrados en el centro histórico, por lo que la visita se debe realizar a pie.

Por supuesto, es inevitable empezar la lista de notabilidades con la Plaza Mayor de Salamanca. Sin duda, es uno de los emblemas de Salamanca y posiblemente el lugar más transitado por ser punto de encuentro entre los salmantinos. Fue diseñada por Alberto Churriguera en el siglo XVIII y está considerada como una de las plazas más bonitas del mundo. Los principales objetos de interés en esta plaza son Pabellón Real, Pabellón de San Martín, Pabellón de Pretineros, La Mariseca.

Salamanca tiene dos catedrales. La Catedral Nueva es una de las dos catedrales con las que cuenta la ciudad de Salamanca. Ya que la ciudad creció y creció, sobre todo con la fama que poco a poco iba adquiriendo la Universidad de Salamanca (allá en el XVI). Pronto se quedó pequeña la «vieja».

Por cierto, si te acercas probablemente veras a un grupo de gente muy cerca de la piedra, haciendo fotos a algo muy muy curioso. ¿Sabes qué hay en el lateral? - ¡Un astronauta!. El famoso astronauta de la Universidad de Salamanca labró a piedra en 1992 durante una de las reformas de la catedral. Ahora es uno de los iconos más famosos que ver en Salamanca.

La Catedral Vieja es la más antigua de las dos catedrales de Salamanca y está consagrada a Santa María de la Sede. Su construcción fue iniciada en el año 1140 y terminó un siglo después. Es de estilo románico casi en su totalidad, aunque las bóvedas son de transición al gótico.

Caminando un poco más, disfrutando de las antiguas calles de Salamanca, verás otra atracción. Esta es La Casa Lis. Las vidrieras de la fachada sur de la Casa Lis no se olvidan fácilmente. Este edificio modernista fue creado a principios del

siglo XX sobre la muralla de la ciudad. Desde el año 1995 se aloja el Museo de Art Nouveau y Art Decó. Por cierto, los jueves puedes entrar gratis. Hoy en día es otro de los lugares importantes que ver en Salamanca, aunque mucha gente llegue a la ciudad sin saber que está.

El siguiente objeto que debes ver en Salamanca es conocido no solo en la ciudad, sino en todo el mundo. Esta es la Universidad de Salamanca. La Universidad de Salamanca es actualmente la universidad más antigua de España, fundada en 1218 por Alfonso IX. Su lugar más emblemático sin duda es la fachada, tallada en piedra. Seguro que veréis a un montón de gente buscando a la famosa rana, posada sobre una calavera en la parte derecha de la fachada. Es muy difícil encontrarla a simple vista, y hay gente por todos los lados tirándose de los pelos buscando la dichosa rana.

Dice la leyenda que los estudiantes se congregaban en la puerta para buscarla, ya que, si la encontraran, aprobarían la carrera. Muchos se tiraron más tiempo buscando la rana que en frente de un libro, pero bueno, eso es otro tema. Merece mucho la pena dar una vuelta por los alrededores de la universidad, y ver tanto el patio, como el Paraninfo.

Entre la Universidad y la Plaza Mayor, se encuentra esta mansión señorial de finales del siglo XV. La Casa de las Conchas. La casa debe su nombre a las más de 300 conchas de la fachada, de estilos mudéjar, gótico y renacentista. La leyenda dice que debajo de una de las conchas está el mapa de un tesoro, y que por eso algunas están rotas.

No se puede dejar de visitar otro lugar de interés turístico es El convento de San Esteban.

Sin duda otro de los lugares míticos que ver en Salamanca es el convento de San Esteban, de Juan de Álava. Es de mediados del siglo XVI y se considera un claro ejemplo de arquitectura plateresca aunque al tardar casi un siglo en terminarse adoptó características del gótico final hasta el barroco. Por cierto, cuenta la leyenda

que Cristóbal Colón se alojó en este lugar (en realidad en el convento anterior, destruido para construir este) cuando visitó la Universidad de Salamanca y estudiar junto a los geógrafos la posibilidad de llegar hasta las Indias por el oeste [1].

Otra notabilidad famosa es El Colegio Real de la Compañía de Jesús. El Colegio Real de la Compañía de Jesús es un imponente edificio que mandó erigir la reina Margarita de Austria, esposa de Felipe III y que comenzó a construirse en 1617, cuando ya habían pasado seis años de su muerte. Una de las mejores vistas que encontrarás de la ciudad de Salamanca es sin duda desde las Torres de la Clerecía (6€, salvo los martes de 10 a 12h, que es gratis). También se pueden subir a las Torres de la Catedral, pero estas suelen estar más llenas de gente, por lo que un buen salmantino siempre os recomendará las vistas de la ciudad desde la Clerecía (Real Clerecía de San Marcos). Está al lado de la Casa de las Conchas.

En conclusión, podemos decir que Salamanca es una de las ciudades más bonitas de España. Es Patrimonio de la Humanidad por la UNESCO desde 1988 y destaca por sus monumentos y por su Universidad, la más antigua del país. Es un lugar perfecto para realizar deferentes tipos del turismo. ¡Ven a Salamanca!

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